

THE WRITTEN YORUBÁ POETRY
(1949-1989):
A STUDY IN THE SOCIOLOGY OF LITERATURE

BY

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ABSTRACT

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This study which complements Olabimtan's earlier efforts, attempts a critical study of the sociology of the Yorùbá written poetry from 1949 to 1989.

In order to achieve our objective, some poets (still alive), and selected critics were interviewed for the purpose of updating our data and subsequent analysis. In all, twenty major poets were interviewed and over fifty poems were examined. A theoretical framework informed by the sociology of literature which defines the place and importance of the artist, his society and his art foregrounds the study. Since our choice of perspective recognizes that a work of art is not independent of its author, the study takes cognisance of authorial intention and audience in the analysis of the themes of the selected Yorùbá written poems.

It is discovered from our analysis that modern Yorùbá poets reflect in their works the changing Yorùbá world-view on such topical issues as economic, political and technological developments. This conscious representation accounts for the major difference between the early and the modern Yorùbá poetry. However, the style that is

evident in the works of early Yorùbá poets is not significantly different from that of their modern counterparts.

While it acknowledges the reciprocity which exists between the modern Yorùbá poet and his audience, the study concludes that no literature can transcend its informing sociology.

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DEDICATION

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Dedicated to my dear children:

Muyiwa,

Lanre,

and

Sinmisola

CERTIFICATION BY SUPERVISOR

I certify that this work was carried out
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CHAPTER ONE

GENERAL INTRODUCTION

1.0 Background to the study

Before the Yorùbá language was reduced to writing, literature in the language was oral. The oral form has been handed over from generation to generation and this has sustained its continuity. From time immemorial, the purpose of oral mode of performance was mainly for entertainment in the royal palace (Finnegan 1970:82; Babalola 1973). But nowadays, oral mode of performance has moved out of the palace.¹ The socio-economic situation has driven many of the surviving poets to fend for themselves.

Eventually, the Yorùbá language was reduced to writing through the untiring efforts of the missionaries who did a scholarly study of the Yorùbá language between 1800 and the 1880s (Awoniyi 1978:25-30). The first Yorùbá verses were published in 1848 (Olabimtan 1974a:5) and written poetry, among others thus came into being.

1. For more on the activities of the oral poets outside the palace, read (Finnegan, R. (1970)).

The growth of written Yorùbá poetry became remarkable in 1961 when Egbé Ikéwí (Society for Yorùbá poetry) was inaugurated at Ibàdàn. This society blossomed into Egbé Ijìnlẹ̀ Yorùbá which later started publishing OLÓKUN, a Yorùbá periodical. Most of the poets that published their works in this periodical, particularly Fálétí, Qlábímtán and Babalqlá show their familiarity with the poetry of foreign land from the way they allude to English poems in their works.

While some poets were publishing their poems in books and journals, another novel has been evolved in the development of written Yorùbá poetry. Other poets now read their poems on radio and television while some put their poems on disc. It is on the basis of this new development that we would group the poets under study into three according to the mode of presentation of their poems:

- 1) Poems that are printed in books, journals and periodicals.
- ii) Poems that are read over the radio and Television
- iii) Poems that are recorded on disc.

From this development, two groups of poets have emerged:

- a) academic poets
- b) commercial poets.

1.1 Academic Poets

They are academic because they are literate poets. This group consists of poets who publish their poems in books, journals and periodicals. This category of poets saw the need for 'ewi' poetry written in Yorùbá. They can be subdivided into:

- 1) occasional-poets: These are poets that were invited to write poems in Ewi Iwòyí for the advancement of Yorùbá literature. Two of such poets are Wáńdé Abímbólá and Adéagbo Akínjógbín. Many of these occasional-poets never wrote any other poem besides their individual contributions in Ewi Iwòyí, edited by Adéagbo Akínjógbín. But not all the contributors in Ewi Iwòyí are occasional poets. Afqlábí Qlábímtán, Adébóyè Babalqlá and Adébáyò Fálétí have all published their poems individually in poetry books. They are grouped under another category of poets.
- 11) Critic-poets: most of these are academics who are exposed to poetry of other lands. They include Adébóyè Babalqlá, Afqlábí Qlábímtán and Akinwumi Işqlá.

They are distinguished University scholars who have written critical works on poetry in particular and other aspects of Yorùbá studies.

iii) teacher-poets: these are practising teachers in Colleges of Education, Polytechnics and Secondary Schools. Some of them are J.F. Qdúnjọ, Túnjì Qpádòkun, Oyetunde Awóyẹlé, Débọ Awẹ and Oyedemi Oyerinde.

iv) journalist-poets: These are poets who worked as journalists either with electronic media houses like Adébáyọ Fálétí, Lánrẹwájú Adépọjù and Túbọsún Qládàpọ or with certain Yorùbá newspapers with regular columns in these newspapers for their poems. Olúsanjọ Bọlárín and Olú Ònákọyà-Adebayọ have published several poems in Gbohùngbohùn while the Ìròyìn Yorùbá poetry columnist under the pen-name 'Atíálá ọmọ Àtìòro' writes poems in the newspaper regularly.

v) artisan-poets: these are freelance poets who engage in poetry because of their patriotic zeal for the promotion of the beauty of their mother-tongue. Abdullai Awọlúmátẹẹ, who because of lack of money could not complete his secondary education, is a poet of note. He joins two

other poets to publish a poetry book, Àarò Mèta (1991).

1.2 Commercial-poets

These are poets who read or perform their poems through the electronic media. They are tagged 'commercial-poets' because of the commercialization of their art. Those who read their poems on radio get paid for each poem read and the poets on discs also make money out of their recordings (Ọlátúnjì 1982c: 128). Prominent among them are Àlàbí Ògúndépò, Fáyẹmí Ẹlẹbu-Ibọn, and Wale Àásànl whose poems are patterned on Yorùbá traditional modes of chanting. Others include, Káyòdé Àrẹmú, Oyelakin Ọladèèbó (now deceased) and Adémọlà Adélabú. Both Ọlanrewaju Adépòjù and Ọlátúbòsún Ọládàpò who adequately fit into the journalist-poets are also in this group. Though Adepoju, the initiator of poetry on disc (Ọlátúnjì 1982c), published some of his poems in his collection, Ìrònú Akéwí (1972) his major contribution to the development of written Yorùbá poetry is in his several poems on discs.

A critical look at these two categories; academic-poets and commercial-poets shows a distinctiveness in the characteristics of their respective poetry. The basic

factor responsible for this is seen in the mode of presentation of their poems. While the academic-poets are 'akq-ewì' (i.e. a kq ewì) (writers of poems) the commercial-poets are 'akéwì' (i.e. a ké ewì) (chanters of poems).

Since the poems of the commercial-poets are performer-based, their texts may not be stable. The performer, like an oral poet, deviates from what he is reading or chanting as he interpolates other issues during a live performance. In a production therefore, either on radio or television, a whole production may lack unity of ideas, rhythm and thought. Since the production comes to us through the audio, its fixation is difficult. But despite this, audio disc poetry is by far more popular in a predominantly less literate society. Furthermore, there is also the atmosphere of spontaneity and the oral effect of disc poetry as opposed to the coldness and the passivity of the printed poetry text.

1.3 The growth of written Yorùbá Poetry

The period, 1949-1959 could be said to be a preparatory period for the in-coming modern Yorùbá poets. Nigeria was then preparing for her independence from the

colonial rule and so, attention shifted to how Nigeria would assume full responsibility for the running of all her own affairs. As Nduka (1964:114) rightly observes,

Between 1946 and 1957, there was a prodigious political leap forward in Nigeria, a leap which left our economic and educational activities plodding far behind.

It was during this period that the then Western Region of Nigeria took giant steps in her political and educational developments.¹

With the introduction of Free Universal Primary Education (UPE) in January 1955, the Western Region which was then headed by Chief Obáfẹ́mi Awólówọ̀, enrolled as many as 400,000 children in her primary schools (Nduka 1964: 117). Our main concern here is that, it is out of the products of this free primary education that emerged literate poets who were to surface either as free-lance

1 For instance, out of its total expenditure of £12,807,000 in the period 1951-60, its expenditure on education alone was £4,052,221 which was 31.6 percent of the total expenditure (Nduka 1964:116).

poets or middle class¹-poets who published their poems in books after Nigeria's independence. Most of the poets considered in the present study are in the two categories.

In the course of these developments, the Western Regional Government again envisaged the need for higher education sooner or later for her manpower needs and so planned to establish a University of her own. To this end, scholarships were awarded to some deserving Yorùbá students to study overseas. Notable among the beneficiaries of this scheme were Adébóyè Babalólá, Qlánpèkún Fsan, Afqlábí Òjò, Adéagbo Akínjógbín and a host of others. It is this group of eminent scholars that spearheaded the formation of several Yorùbá Associations for the purpose of promoting the Yorùbá studies. They include the Yorùbá Historical Research Scheme which was founded in 1958. Consequently, ODU was published by the General Publications Section (GPS) of the regional Ministry of Education, Ìbàdàn. The Journal accommodated articles on written Yorùbá poetry. The second Journal of equal importance is OLÓKUN, this we have mentioned earlier. It is pertinent

1 What we termed middle class poets here are academic poets who are teachers either in the Universities or College of Education.

to note that the maiden edition of OLÓKUN in 1959, published 'Ijamba Odò Ọba', a poem written by Fálétí, one of the poets under study (Ọlátúnjí 1982c:xiii).

The period 1949-1959 turned out to be a period of gestation for the poets who, expectedly, almost immediately after independence started publishing their poems in the emergent poetry books and journals. Besides Fálétí, other poets who can be termed precursors to the written Yorùbá poetry also published their works in OLÓKUN. They include, Adébóyè Babalọlá, Afọlábí Ọlábímtán and Akínwùmí Iṣọlá among others. Most of the poems in OLÓKUN were later published in Ewí Iwòyí 1969 edited by Adéagbo Akínjógbín.

The establishment of the Western Nigerian Literature Committee, a Government committee, was also very relevant to the development of Yorùbá studies, including poetry. This Committee founded AWORERIN, a Yorùbá periodical published once in two months between the fifties and seventies. Like OLÓKUN, the General Publication section of the Ministry of Education, Ibadan published AWORERIN. Several written Yorùbá poems appeared in different editions of AWORERIN. For example, Fálétí published

several poems in this Periodical. His poems 'Alágbára-ilé àti Alágbára-oko' appeared in the 3rd edition, 'Agbódórogun' in the 7th and 'Ọjọ́ Iláyèfun' in the 9th edition; all in 1958 (Ọlátúnjì 1982c:xiii). All these poems were later published in Ewì Adébáyò Fálétí, Ìwé Kínní and Ewì Adébáyò Fálétí, Ìwé Kejí 1982 by Ọlátúnjì.

Aworẹrin was basically designed for school children, this informs the didactic nature of the poems it carried. The titles of such poems unambiguously portrayed the didacticism in their contents. For example, 'Afarawé ọ̀ sunwọ̀n' (Imitating others is bad) appeared in the March/April, 1970 issue while 'Má Fòwúrọ̀ Şeré' (Make Hay While the Sun shines) and 'Olẹ̀ Kò Dára' (Stealing is not good) appeared in the May/June, 1971 and September/October 1971 issues respectively.

Government's efforts in the development of written Yorùbá poetry in particular, and the Yorùbá studies in general, culminate in the production of ODÙ, OLOKUN and AWORERIN in which many Yorùbá poems were published.

Besides these journals and Periodicals, the Yorùbá newspapers also contributed their own quota to the development of written Yorùbá poetry before and during

our study period. Ogunṣinà (1988 and 1992) similarly highlights the role of the early Yorùbá Newspapers in the development of Yorùbá creative writing. Iròyìn Yorùbá, a weekly Yorùbá Newspaper which was founded in 1945 is now published by the Nigerian Tribune which was founded by Chief Obafemi Awolowo on November 16, 1949. The Action Group, (AG) intra-party crisis of 1962 broke the party into two factions giving birth to the Nigerian National Democratic Party (NNDP) led by Chief Samuel Ládokè Akintólá. It was Akintola's Government in the Western Region that founded the Daily Sketch on March 31, 1964 which later started publishing Gbohùngbohùn, another weekly Yorùbá Newspaper. Unlike the early Yorùbá Newspapers, both Iròyìn Yorùbá and Gbohùngbohùn came as a result of political crisis in the former Western Region of Nigeria.

Our interest in this development, however, is the contributions of the two Yorùbá newspapers, 'Iròyìn Yorùbá and Gbohùngbohùn to the growth of written Yorùbá poetry. For example, there is a regular column in each of the two newspapers for written Yorùbá poetry. One Olúsanjò Bólárín, a columnist in Gbohùngbohùn wrote poems

regularly. An example is 'Aiye Titun' (New Life) in the February 23-February 29, 1972 issue, while another poet Olú Ọ̀nákọ̀ya-Adébàyọ̀ wrote 'Ibà fáwọ̀n tó máyẹ̀ dùn' (Salute to those who make life comfortable) in the March 6-March 12, 1985 edition. Similarly, in Ìròyìn Yorùbá, its poetry columnist whose pen-name is 'Atiòro ọmọ Atiálá' wrote poems regularly. One of such poems is 'Ayé lóko Atiòro' (Life in Atiòro village) which appeared in the January 18-January 24, 1989 issue of Ìròyìn Yorùbá. Some of these poems are to be examined in the present study.

The significance of the contributions of these two newspapers to the written Yorùbá poetry lies in the fact that they (newspaper) constantly bring poetry to the reach of their numerous readers. By the time these papers started publishing poems, there were very limited number of Yorùbá poetry books in the market. So, the newspaper poems complement the few available poetry books which were seldom patronized by the generality of the people. As Ọ̀gúnşínà (1992:3) rightly observes:

In Nigeria, most people read to pass examinations rather than for literary pleasure.

The newspaper therefore provides, in addition to an up-to-date news, opportunity to read poetry.

We must emphasize also that when written Yorùbá poetry started, most of the poets, Šóbò Aróbfodu in particular, were pre-occupied with Christian ideals (Ọlabintan 1974, Ogunšina 1980). This is so in view of the preponderance of Christian teachings in their poetry. Perhaps this was so because the Missionaries who brought the art of reading and writing did so mainly to convert the people and propagate the Christian faith. In other words, written Yorùbá poetry then (1848-1948) was used largely for Christian evangelism.

However, thirty eight years after independence, available data shows a growing awareness of the importance of culture to the overall development of the child. Furthermore, the selected poets for the present study tend to de-emphasize foreign culture, including religion. It is the contention of the poets that the missionaries took our culture from us and replaced it with the white-

man's religion. This attitude of protest against imported religion as exhibited by the poets is a post-independence phenomenon, hence foregrounded by the fact of Nigeria's political independence and a subsequent change in the social, economic and literary perspectives.

This general survey of the development of written Yorùbá poetry from its beginning to date, has presented the true perspective of a developing African literature. It shows the emergence of the written Yorùbá poetry and its rapid development after the attainment of Nigeria independence. This is perhaps the general phenomenon of the developing countries. Most of the factors that influenced this rapid growth were not in place in the earliest beginnings. The only medium of spreading the written poetry then was through the print media which in itself was very limited. Apart from the Ègbá Printing Press that published selected poets' works, most of the poems written during that period first came out in the existing newspapers (Ogúnṣinà 1976, 1980, 1992).

1.4 Purpose of the Study

There are in existence several scholarly works on Yorùbá poetry over the years. For instance, Babalólá (1966) worked on Yorùbá Ijálá, Abímbólá (1968) on Ifá, while Finnegan (1970) and Qlátúnjí (1978) have individually examined, in detail, different Yorùbá oral poetic genres. Karin Barber (1979) on her own part did an indepth study of oríkì, using the sociology of literature for her analysis. These works are, no doubt, useful because, among other things, they offer an insight into the repertoire of the vast Yorùbá oral poetry. No doubt, oral poetry is a significant macro sub-generic unit of Yorùbá poetry which has enjoyed a well deserved critical attention, the written form on the other hand, has not been given adequate attention by scholars. Qlabimtan (1974a) acknowledged this critical gap and therefore pioneered the first critical study of the written Yorùbá poetry, 1848-1948. After Qlabimtan (1974a), there has been no other indepth study on written Yorùbá poetry until Qlátúnjí (1982) did an analytical study of Adebayo

Fáléfí, a foremost leading Yorùbá poet. Qlatúnjì's work is, no doubt, a seminal contribution to the study of written Yorùbá poetry. However, as illuminating as his work is, it is concerned with only one poet. His work, therefore, cannot be an adequate parameter to assess all other Yorùbá poets. The need for the present study is therefore imperative.

Furthermore, unlike the written poetry, substantive ground has been covered on the other generic forms of Yorùbá literature; prose and drama. Ôgúnşínà (1976) traced the literary history of the Yorùbá novel from its early beginnings to 1975, while Işòlá (1978) examined the writer's art in the modern Yorùbá novel. Similarly, the Yorùbá drama has enjoyed some degree of critical patronage. Clark (1974) surveyed the professional theatre of Hubert Ogunde dating back to 1944. Ôgúndeji (1988) also shed more light on Yorùbá plays with his work on Dúró Ladífpò's plays. We are of the opinion that written Yorùbá poetry deserves a much wider scope and depth in its critical analysis than it has hitherto been given. This foregrounds our intention in the present study. This is more so when viewed against the

background that there has been no work, to our knowledge, that has appeared on written Yorùbá poetry between 1949 and 1989 within the perspective of the sociology of literature. This study, a pioneering effort, is intended to be one of the first elaborate works on Yorùbá modern poets (written poetry) to which the theory of sociology of literature is applied.

The last three decades of our chosen period for the purpose of this study, 1960-1989, fall within the post-independence era in Nigeria. It is a very significant sociological marker in the development of written Yorùbá poetry. This study is an attempt to highlight the differences in the critical sensibilities of selected Yorùbá poets covering the four decades. The study intends to take cognizance of the effects of the major social, political and cultural changes which took place during their period and how these have affected the language, style and poetic perception of their society.

The study is also intended to attempt a comparison of the themes in the earlier poets' works with those of the latter poets to see the trend in the growth and development of written Yorùbá poetry from its beginning

to 1989. Our analysis of the poems is aimed at bringing to the fore the styles of presentation by the latter Yorùbá poets which seem to have revolutionalized the entire written Yorùbá poetry. This study will enable us have a deeper understanding of the society in the colonial and post colonial Yorùbáland. It will enable us understand the impact of the political, social and economic changes on the Yorùbá poets in the pre-independence era.

1.5 Significance of the study

This study is intended to bridge the critical gap in the existing study such as areas of lapses and areas of omission. Besides complementing major works like Qlabimtan's sociological study of written Yorùbá poetry (1848-1948) - the first one hundred years of the written Yorùbá poetry, our work succeeds in bridging a critical gap in the next forty years (1949-1989) that the Yorùbá poetry scholarship had suffered gross neglect.

1.6 Delimitation of the study

According to Qlabimtan (1974a), the period 1848-1948

marks the first era in the development of Yorùbá written poetry. He chose this period because;

1848 was the year the first Yorùbá verses were published and 1948 was the year of the death of Denrele Qbasá who was one of the early writers of Yorùbá poetry.

If 1848 was the year the first Yorùbá verses were published, it is logical to trace the development of written Yorùbá poetry from 1848, but it is not enough to use 1948 as the end of an era solely because of the death of a single poet, Qbasá. Although Qbasá contributed so meaningfully to the development of Yorùbá poetry then, there were other equally prominent poets of his time such as Oguji, Ajíşafé, Ajàó and Johnson among others whose contributions were no less invaluable. Besides, the year 1948 was not the end of Yorùbá poets' protest against colonialism. Therefore, the death of Qbasá could neither be the end of the political philosophy he represented nor should mark the end of an era. Apparently, the philosophy of protest was very evident even after the death of Qbasá.

Nevertheless, the chosen period for the purpose

of this study quite naturally commences from 1949 where Olabimtan (1974a) stopped, and ends in 1989, forty-one years after Olabimtan's period and twentynine years after Nigeria's independence. A period of four decades is substantial enough as basis for assessing the trend of the development of the happenings during this period.

1949, our starting point is very significant because it, among other things, marked the year 'Egbé Ikéwí Yorùbá' (Society for Yoruba Poetry) which later metamorphosed into 'Egbé Ijinlẹ Yorùbá' was inaugurated in London by the Yorùbá scholars abroad. It was founded partly to ameliorate the nostalgic home feelings of those patriotic Yorùbá scholars and, more importantly, to facilitate the growth of Yorùbá language (Gbadamọṣi 1992:14). There had been in existence several other associations for the propagation of Yorùbá studies here in Nigeria long before the inauguration of 'Egbé Ikéwí Yorùbá'. These include 'Egbé Olùfẹ Ilẹ Ibí Wọṅ' (1883) (Society For Lovers of their Fatherland), 'Egbé Onífẹ Ilẹ Yorùbá' (1907) (Society For Lovers of Yorùbáland) and 'Egbé Agbà ọ Tán' (1908) Society of Elders (Olabimtan 1974a, Gbadamọṣi 1992). However, 'Egbé Ikéwí

Yorùbá', as the name suggests, specifically focused on written Yorùbá poetry and it later on, according to Babalola (1973:53),

flowered into an association with wider aims embracing the entire scope of Yorùbá language, literature and culture.

But for the birth of 'Egbé Ikéwí Yorùbá in 1949, probably the development of written Yorùbá poetry would not have reached the present stage of its development. To us, 1949 is significant to mark the beginning of another era. It led to the publication of the first collection of what we would call modern written Yorùbá poetry, Ewí Iwòyí, edited by Adéagbo Akínjógbin in 1969. In addition, the choice of 1949 supports the logicality in ensuring continuity with Olabimtan (1974a) who stopped in 1948. It is therefore considered very appropriate and justifiable to commence the present study from 1949.

Our intention to limit the scope of our study to

1989, is not arbitrary either, it is significant to note that more Yorùbá poetry books were produced during the last decade of the period of our research interest (1980-89) than during the first three decades, 1949-1979. This is due to the awareness of the poets on the need to produce more poetry books. For instance, five Yorùbá poetry books were published in the first decade, five in the second, nine in the third and twelve in the last decade, 1980-89. This apparent accelerated prolificity of poetry textbook production during the 1980-89 period largely drew our attention and served as one of the determinants for the demarcation of our choice of periodization. Besides, 1989 marks the fortieth and terminal year of our chosen study period. The number forty is symbolic as it serves as a landmark in the life of man suggesting maturity.

1.7 Methodology

Relevant Yorùbá poetry books including journals, magazines and newspapers published between 1949 and 1989 are used for this study.

We also interviewed most of the poets under study

(who are still alive) to determine the influence, if any, which their life history has on their poetry.

For the historical accounts of what aided the rapid growth of Yorùbá studies in general and poetry in particular shortly before and a little after Nigeria's independence, we interviewed the surviving personalities including Professor Adéagbo Akínjógbin who was the Secretary of the Yorùbá Historical Research Scheme that gave birth to the publication of ODÙ and Pa Adégbóyèga Şóbáńdè, the Editor of OLÓKUN, a Yorùbá periodical founded by the 'Ègbè Ijìnlè Yorùbá. We also visited the Nigerian Tribune, Publishers of Iròyìn Yorùbá and the Daily Sketch, Publishers of Gbohùngbohùn.

We also recorded some poems from Radio Stations in the Yorùbá-speaking States where poetry is used to transmit certain programmes. These Radio Stations include, Ondo State Radio Corporation, Akúré, Broadcasting Corporation of Oyo State (BCOS), Ibàdàn, Radio Lagos, Ikòyí and Broadcasting Corporation of Oşun State (Radio Oşun), Oşogbo.

CHAPTER TWO

2.0 REVIEW OF THE LITERATURE

In this chapter, we will examine the existing works on written Yorùbá poetry and also discuss the theoretical frame-work that we will adopt for the analysis of our work.

Ọlabimtan's (1974a) work on the early Yorùbá poets serves as a springboard for the present study. His work which focuses on the first one hundred years of the written Yorùbá poetry identifies three phases in its development:

i) poetic writing in Christian hymnal form (mission poetry). Yorùbá poets in this group include those whose poetry is patterned on the Christian English hymns and their content informed by the various themes which are foregrounded in Christian doctrines. Lijadu represents this group.

ii) poetic writing in Yorùbá oral poetic form: i.e. 'compromise poetry'. Both Şóbò Aróbíodu and Oyeşilé Kẹribo belong to this group. To Ọlabimtan, the orin-àrùngbè mode employed by the poets to propagate their

Christian faith is a sign of compromise. This is so because the poets were indifferent to the use of orin-àrùngbè mode (a traditional chanting and singing mode) for their poetry as long as they achieve their desired evangelical goal.

iii) poetic writing in both Yorùbá indigenous and foreign poetic forms. Ọlabimtan identifies three different types of poetry in this group:

- a) poems by the 'compromise poets' (see (ii) above)
- b) the 'colonial poetry' of Yorùbá poets whose poetry showed apparent influence of the English poetry both in form and diction. Ajaó, Ajişafe and Johnson belong to this group of poets, and
- c) 'protest poetry'. Poets in this group employ poetry as a means of showing their indignation to disapprove of wrongdoings. Ọbasá and Ọdúnjọ fall into this category.

Further to our observation of the three phases identified by Ọlabimtan (1974a) is the fact that propa-

gation of the Christian doctrines is a typical feature common to them all. This is so because most of the poets were products of Christian mission schools.

As illuminating as Qlabimtan's pioneering work is, there is an observable critical gap: the influence of printing technology, as well as the role of the print media in facilitating the development of written Yorùbá poetry during the same period, 1848-1948. The print media occupied a significant position in the development of written Yorùbá poetry because the Press it was that introduced the works of some of the poets to reading public. For example, the Ègbá Printing Press printed Şóbbò and Lijadu poems while Longman published the poems of Qdúnjò. Qbasá even had his own Press, the Ilarè Press, that published his poems. His first poetry book, Iwé Kinni ti Awon Akéwi (Yorùbá Philosophy) came out in 1925 (Ogunşina 1980:44). This was followed by the second book, Iwé Keji ti Awon Akéwi (Yorùbá Philosophy).

The advent of the Printing Press in Yorùbá community led to the establishment of some Newspapers.

The significant implication of the role played by the newspapers is the spread and popularisation of the written Yorùbá poetry. Notable among them were: The Yorùbá News, Elétí Ofẹ, Eko Igbẹhin and Akede Ekó (Ogúnşínà 1980:44). The Yorùbá News spearheaded the crusade of printing Yorùbá poems weekly.

The first known Yorùbá poem appeared in Iwé Iròhin in December, 1860. It was written by someone in memory of one Francis Allen. Other poets were encouraged by the publication. They include Joseph Babatunde Vincent who published a poem on April 15, 1890 in Iwé Iròhin Ekó in memory of A. C. Willoughby, a police officer (Ogúnşínà, 1980:41). The appearance of Yorùbá poems in the weekly Newspapers, no doubt, stimulated the reading habit of the Yorùbá of that period. This development later encouraged the publication of G. A. Şówùmí's poems into an anthology of poems, Iwé Aròfò Alóyín-lóhùn, Apá Kini àti Apá Keji in June, 1950 (Ogúnşínà 1980:45).

It is therefore, apparent that the contribution of the early newspapers to the development of written

Yorùbá poetry is a very significant one. It brought written Yorùbá poetry to the reach of the people.

Besides, Olabimtan's study is not based on any specific theoretical framework, but the present study which is informed by a deep concern for an appropriate assessment of, among others, the relationship between the Yorùbá poet, his art and his society in the colonial and post-colonial Yorùbáland shall be based on sociological interpretation of literature and, in this case, poetry.

Another major work on written Yorùbá poetry as mentioned earlier is Olatúnjí's Adébáyò Fálétí, A Study of His Poems (1982a). Though Olatunji makes a brief survey of other notable contemporary Yorùbá poets, his work is specifically on Adébáyò Fálétí. It is an interpretative analysis of the poems of Fálétí. However, since Fálétí does not represent the whole of Yorùbá poets, Olatunji's study is partitive and lacks the comprehensiveness intended in the present study.

A number of critical works on selected Yorùbá poets bear relevance to our work. For instance, Oso (1977) and Idowú (1978) provide useful information on

the contributions of radio and disc poets respectively to the development of written Yorùbá poetry. Apart from their being didactic in their presentation, Qlátúnjí (1982a:128) rightly observes,

most of the radio and disc poets do not strike their audience as convinced artists but rather as poetic businessmen who are not interested in the affairs of their fellowmen.

This present study takes cognizance of the issue of commercialization of art which informs our preference to refer to some poets as 'emergency poets' in the course of our present discourse. We must add, however, that Qlátúnjí's remark that the poets 'are not interested in the affairs of their fellowmen' may not be taken in the absolute. These poets, we must emphasize, have different objectives they all express sociological concern but the degree of commitment differs from one poet to another. For example, Qlátúbọsún Qládàpò is far more committed to the promotion of cultural values than any other consideration. Qlanrewaju Adepoju, on the other hand, is more

politically inclined, therefore he often casts his poetry along the traditional Yorùbá praise singer.

Akinyemi's (1986) analytical study of Qbasá 1927-1945 is not within the purview of our period but it will be of immense value to our comparative study. Arẹmú (1988) examined the content and form of Qlabimtan's poems in Aádóta Aròfò and Ewì Orísirísi. Incidentally, Qlabimtan is one of the poets whose works will be considered in our study. Besides Qlabimtan's poems in the two poetry texts which Arẹmú (1988) critiqued, his poems in Akójopò Ewì Abáláyé Ati Ewì Apilẹkọ which he edited will be examined also.

Qlagbemi (1980) worked on the disc poetry of Qládàpò. Fortunately, Qládàpò has put most of his poetry in printed texts which makes them ready material for the present work. However, some of Qlagbemi's data would facilitate our analysis.

Finally, though both Barber (1985) and Akínyemí (1991) adopted the sociology of literature to analyse Yorùbá oríkí, their analysis has direct relevance on the present work. Their emphasis is on the relationship of the artist, his art and the society. Ogúnşínà (1987)

also used the sociology of literature to analyse some Yorùbá novels.

2.1 Theoretical Framework

2.1.0 Introduction

There are different approaches to the study of literature. Some of these include, Formalism, Structuralism, Semiotics and Hermeneutics. Each of these approaches has its strong and weak points. Taking Formalism as an example, its limitation lies in its strict adherence to only the 'internal' properties of a poem in its interpretation. Therefore, since the Formalists believe that the meaning of any literary work is in the text and the text alone, Formalist would not be enough for this study. Evidences can be adduced for our rejection of other approaches mentioned above.

The general inadequacy of these 'foreign' theories, as far as Yorùbá written poetry is concerned, is the little attention given to the role of society in the production of a work of art. We therefore need a cultural based approach for our analysis. Such a study

of the sociology of written Yorùbá poetry would benefit from a good knowledge of the sociology of literature.

2.1.1 Sociology as a Discipline

With the agglomeration of people in towns, the rise of the family and the subsequent growth in industrialization which facilitated division of labour, 'sociology' as a discipline began to take root. A number of sociologists have been involved in the development of sociology as a discipline. For example, Ibn Khaldun (1332-1406) recognizes the society rather than the individual. Ibn sees man as a social animal who needs the co-operation of others for a meaningful existence. His emphasis is, therefore, on social cohesion for a continual existence of the society. His "new science", sociology or the Science of Society, earns him the tag, 'Founder of Sociology' (Atéré and Olagbemi 1997:24). Equally notable among the founding fathers of sociology is Auguste Comte (1798-1857) who carved the word 'Sociology' from the earliest name Social Physics. Comte also acknowledges society as essential for man for interaction and survival. Other Sociologists that contribute to the development of

Sociology as a discipline include Herbert Spencer (1820-1903) and Emile Durkheim (1858-1917) (Atéré and Qlagbemi 1997).

Sociology is concerned with people's customs, habits, organizations, institutions and points of views. It looks at each group and examines how the collective influences individual's behaviour. According to Elbert W. Stewart (1981), Sociology informs on actions which are considered private but which are socially shaped and determined. In Yorùbá society, for example, the sound of a certain bird may suggest a bad omen to a person. In another society, the sound may lack any significant reference to warrant any attention. It is in the light of this that Stewart (1981:4) opines,

The groups and societies in which we live and act continually influence our interpretation of ostensibly private beliefs and actions.

And this question of the individual in the group relationship, according to Stewart (1981) is the specific realm of sociology. In other words, sociology places premium on the interaction of the individual in the society.

We can define and compare the sociological scene with the scene of other sciences. As a discipline in the social sciences, Sociology has its own distinct identity. Sociology focuses on societies, human groups and interactions. From all ramification, Sociologists are interested in a wide range of questions about the society, social change and social interaction.

Today, Sociology is recognized as an academic discipline throughout the world. As a discipline and a field of practice, Sociology deals with the understanding of human societies and the various institutions that constitute as agents of stabilization.

Down the ages, the application of sociology has enhanced its development. Each group of people that makes up the society has different roles to play for the smooth running of the society. The leaders, the followers, the elders and even the youths, all have specific roles to play in the society.

From the foregoing, one could see that the knowledge of sociology will enable us to understand the flow of process of activities in the society. Almost everything in life is sociologically inclined and, or informed. It

informs our choice of approach in the present study.

2.2.0 Sociology of Literature

There had been sociology of religion, education, politics, sports, knowledge, language and many other disciplines in existence before sociology.¹ This shows that sociology of literature is relatively new. Taine, the French philosopher (1828-1893) was the exponent and the originator of the term, sociology of literature. The establishment of sociology of literature is to achieve a goal, that is,

to submit literature and art to the same research methods as those employed in the physical and natural sciences.

(Ogunşina 1987:16)

Thus, the term, sociology of literature is a combination of two distinct disciplines, sociology and literature. Sociology studies the origin, history and constitution of human society. It also studies the social organizations

1 The Encyclopedia AMERICANA, International Edition, Vol. 25, Grolier Incorporated, 1829.

and institutions including man's behaviour and interaction and his relationship to the larger social group. In general terms, sociology is the study of man in relation to the society in which he lives. The Encyclopedia Americana describes sociology as

the scientific study of the social behaviour of human beings, or the study of human groups (1988:275).

The task sociology sets for itself is how to understand the society in a scientific way. It is not surprising therefore that Oğunşınà (1987:18) states:

This is achieved through a **rigorous** examination of the social institutions, religious, economic, political and filial, which together constitute what is called a structure.

This, in effect, will offer an insight into the behaviour and role of man in society for the purpose of appreciating his contributions to the progress of the society. But sociology does more than this. It also gives an intuition into the changes that go on in the society and the effect

these changes have on the social structure.

Literature is an institution which concerns itself with man and his society. Wellek and Warren (1949:94) view literature as

a social institution, using as its medium language, a social creation.

This view is corroborated by Dasylva (1995:81) when he says,

experience, imagination and the exploitation of the resources of language (and music in the case of poetry) are the basic components of literature.

In other words, literature uses language to explain the society. The literary artist is part of the society, he produces literature, using structure of words and ideas that are understood and shared by the society. All the norms and conventions and all other traditional literary devices such as symbolism and metre which are inherent in the language are society-based. Indeed, literature is

society's property. This same property, that is, literature, is used to expose, criticise, change and moderate the experience of the people where it evolves. Dasylva (1995:82) illuminates this point when he writes,

Literature discusses life by reflecting and, or refracting what may happen or what might (have) happen(ed), or what ought to (have) happen(ed), and not necessarily what had actually happened or is happening now.

But the influence is reciprocal, as the literary artist influences the society, the society in turn, influences him. This point is also highlighted by Amuta (1986:1) when he says,

The challenge of a rigorous sociology of literature is primarily that of understanding the intrinsic complexity of both society and literature with a view to re-establishing their dialectical connectedness.

It is not even just the society and literature alone,

the artist is inclusive in the 'complexity' Amuta is referring to in the excerpt above. The three, society, literature and the artist are bound together, one cannot be understood in isolation. For a sociological analysis of a work of art, the three components of the triangle must be involved. In essence, the poet, his art and the society depend on one another.

It is therefore clear that the main preoccupation of Sociology of Literature, among others, is the understanding of the relationship between literature and society. A literary artist cannot ignore the influence of the society on his work. The special language of poetry belongs to the society. The poet uses all the ideas he collects from the society in his work, including language.

The prevalent socio-political, religious and economic factors of the poet's time determine largely the content of his work. He himself, his poetry and the influence of the society on him have to be considered together for a meaningful critical analysis of his work. Using the novel as an example, Ogunṣina (1987:22) puts

this view in its proper perspective when he says,

The sociology of the novel sees the novel, the novelist and the society as inextricably bound together, such that neither the novel, nor the novelist, nor the influence of society on both can be considered in isolation. Rather, to understand one fully, there is need for constant reference to the other two components of the triangle.

This is also true of the poetry text or poet. The poet being part of the society therefore has no alternative than to draw his materials from his immediate society if he expects his art to have direct bear on the society. It thus becomes imperative for the critic, therefore to delve into the culture of the people the poet is writing for to be able to grasp the full interpretation of his (poet's) message.

2.2.1 Society and Literary Artist - Marxist Theory

The Marxist believes that in the interpretation of literature, the study of the society that owns such

literature is imperative. It therefore recognizes man and his activities in the society as this will help us to understand him. The society determines the form of its literature. It is the argument of the Marxists that each society has its own literature with its own distinct peculiarities. David Forgacs (1982:167) sums it up in one of Marxist concepts that a literary theory should take into cognizance the influence of both the society and the history behind the writings on a work of art. By this, Forgacs submits, the theory will be able to explain what literature really is. This shows how strongly the Marxists believe that literature cannot be divulged from society. To them, literature is better explained in relation to society that produces it.

The Marxist critics believe that ideology underlies the attitude and actions of man in the society and this is manifested in the society's superstructure. This superstructure includes politics, art, religion, literature and law. Literature as a part of the superstructure is manipulated by the ruling class to perpetuate their views. Economy is the basic structure

and it determines to a large extent, the ideological stance. In a class society, the ruling class has the economic and political power. This is used to their advantage to determine other structures. The poor masses are therefore exploited by the bourgeois who are the ruling class. This is what operates in a capitalist state like Nigeria. But consciously or unconsciously, allegiance of the oppressed is more often than not pitched with the oppressor as he (oppressed) adopts the ideology of the oppressor. For instance, many of the poets under this study write to praise superior class.

2.2.2 Approaches to Sociology of Literature

Out of the various approaches for the study of literature, two are very relevant to our study: The Mirror Image, and Publisher-author-audience.

2.2.3 The Mirror-Image Approach

The 'mirror image' approach sees literature as a reflection of the society (Lowenthal, 1957). The French philosopher Louis de Bonald (1754-1840) who was one of the apostles of this approach, believes that literature depicts the on-goings

in the society. The exponents of this approach argue that if one studies the literature of a society closely, one would be able to visualize the past of that society. For instance, one could read from Isaac Delano's novels, Lójó Ojóun and Aiye Daiye Oyinbo the picture of Yorùbá society whose traditional institutions, values and practices have been utterly devalued and bastardized. The two novels are caricature of what was happening in the Ègbá community of Yorùbá society at that time. It is a reflection of the outcome of processes of social modernization.

This approach confirms the strong belief that art and society are inseparable. In other words, the society produces the art and since the artist himself is part of the society, he attempts, through his art, to reproduce the society literary world (fictional world). The approach sees literature as giving a complete picture of what the society is, its specific historical periods, its definite social facts and in fact, in all its facets. The literary sociologist should therefore transform all imaginary characters in a work of art into social situations since the approach believes that

literature reflects the norms of the society that produces it, the analyst should give a one to one interpretation of a work of art and the on-goings in the society.

The flaw in the 'mirror image' approach lies in the fact that the artist's account may not be a true representation of the society and it may even be a distortion of what happened then. Again, the artist's account whose extra-literary addition cannot be verified is a one-man presentation and as Ôgúnşínà (1987:27) rightly puts it,

The approach greatly limits the critical appraisal of a work of art to only a person who has knowledge of the structure of society from other sources than literary, to find out the adequacy or inadequacy of the specific social meanings in a literary work.

Again, the author's presentation of the society may be his own imagination or his own creation which is not authentic. Wellek and Warren (1949:95) also express their own view on the inadequacy of the 'mirror image'

approach when they argue that,

A writer inevitably expresses his experience and total conception of life; but it would be manifestly untrue to say that he expresses the whole of life - or even the whole life of a given time - completely and exhaustively.

But it is to the credit of this approach for establishing the fact that art and society are inseparable. Their relationship will help our analysis of **the selected poems**. Art is not created in a vacuum, it owes its existence to the society from where it takes its root.

2.2.4 Publisher-author-audience approach

This approach lays emphasis on the production, distribution and consumption of a work of art. One of its exponents is Robert Escarpit (1971) who argues that the position of the artist, the cost of production and the marketing must be taken into account for the analysis of a work of art by the critic. Emphasis is therefore shifted from the work of art itself. The artist tries

to write in a way that would be acceptable to both the audience and his publishers.

This approach, otherwise known as Escarpit's approach, argues further that the market economy is an important factor in the production of literary work and should be considered in the criticism of a writer's work (Escarpit 1971). For instance, for economic reasons, the publishers place great premium on the audience/reader for the acceptability of the content of an artist's work. This could be illustrated with the works of some of the poets under study. It is this publisher-author-audience relationship that determines Şasanya's (1987) language and style in Ewi Qmòdé and Qladapq's Aròfò Qmòdé (1989). Both poets had their target audience, that is, school children in mind. Their poems are specifically for children. The poets therefore compose simple lyrical poems couched in language appropriate to the age of school children. Not only are the poems lyrical, they are equally instructive. The style is determined by the poets and also the demand of the publishers as well as the desire of the audience, that is, school children.

Thus Escarpit's approach is very useful for the analysis of a work of art in the sense that our knowledge of the socio-economic factors under which the art is produced would make its meaning robust. Nevertheless, the approach has the disadvantage of overdependence on extraneous factors, giving little attention to the literary text itself. But as we have noticed earlier, no literary approach is flawless. We hope this approach, sociology of literature, will increase our awareness of the interrelationship of the artist, his/her society and a work of art.

2.3.0 Interdependence of Sociology and other literary Theories.

The sociology of literature is greatly indebted to a few of the existing literary theories, that is, structuralism, Semiotics and Hermeneutics.

Structuralists' holistic way of looking at the world, including man, is closely related to sociology of literature's belief in the interrelationship of art and society. Scholes (1974:4) says of structuralism,

in its broadest sense, structuralism is a way of looking for reality not in individual things but in the relationship among them.

It could be seen from this that the basic principle of structuralism lies in the interrelationship of structures or events in a system. This same principle is obviously cardinal to the sociology of literatures' doctrine which establishes dialectical relationship between a work of art, the artist and the society.

Semiotics also has a link with sociology of literature. According to Guiraud (1975) 'Semiology' was conceived by F. de Saussure as the science which studies the life of signs in society while Peirce also conceived 'Semiotics' as a general theory of signs. Today both terms refer to the same discipline. Saussure sees each sign as being made of a 'signifier' and a 'signified' and that the relation between 'signifier' and 'signified' is an arbitrary one. Each sign in the system has meaning only by virtue of its difference from the others (Eagleton 1983:97). Peirce, in his own, made a useful distinction between three types of sign: the 'iconic', the 'indexical', and the 'symbolic'.

It is the 'symbolic' where the sign has an arbitrary relation to its referent: for example, language that is relevant to our work. It resembles Yorùbá 'àrokò' (sign) which is the property of the society. The Yorùbá 'àrokò' also communicates and infers meaning. The interpretation of the 'sign' is societal based and to the sociologists, society plays an important role in the analysis of a work of art.

Central to the Hermeneutic theory is the spiritual unification between the author and the audience, for there exists a permanent relationship (Bauman 1978:13-14). Both the author and the audience are products of their society hence, Adeleke (1995:68) says:

The playwright (in our instance, poet) - audience relationship has its basis in the spiritual unification (or the unity of the inner spirit). Through this spiritual unification the members of the audience are able to re-discover, interpret and understand the message of the playwright (poet).

Thus the hermeneutics theory takes cognisance of authorial-intention and audience in the analysis of a work of art.

The artist inquires into the norms and customs of the society and this he depicts in his work. This is also the message of sociology of literature, that is, the relationship of the author to his society. Also, like sociology of literature, hermeneutics believes that the experiences of an author cannot be more than his knowledge about the society, customs and his work. He is part of the society he is writing for and he uses the language of this society. In the light of this, therefore, our emphasis in this study shall largely be on the topicality and sociological significance of the selected poems.

Approach we adopt

In our introduction to our theoretical framework, we indicate that no literary approach is flawless. This is validated in our brief survey of approaches to the study of sociology of literature. Nevertheless, it is the 'mirror image' approach and the Escarpit's approach under the sociology of literature that we will adopt for our analysis. We cannot ignore Escarpit's point that an understanding of the writer's position in the book industry is necessary

for the interpretation of his work. The content and form of the artist's work is largely determined by his audience and also the publishers. This is evident in several of the poems under study. The criticism of overdependence on extraneous factors by this approach at the expense of the attention to the literary text itself will be compensated for by the 'mirror image' approach which lays emphasis on the work of literature itself.

It is clear that no single approach provides answer to literary sociology. Yorùbá poets reflect their society. In sociology of literature, the artist does not merely reflect. Reflectionism is not an end, it is a means to achieving a definite end. His reflection may be to endorse, oppose, reject, amend or correct. This approach will help us see the impact of each poet's work on the society. It is our belief that this approach that we have adopted will give us a richer and fuller understanding of the society, the poet and his poetry.

CHAPTER THREE

TOPICALITY AND SIGNIFICANCE I

3.0 Introduction

The next two chapters shall attempt an examination of the topical issues raised in some of the works of selected poets for the purpose of locating their sociological significance. No doubt, the thematic preoccupations of the poets as expressed in their works are various and varied and are informed by sociological factors. It is, therefore, believed that the present examination will, among others, help to determine and define the poets' social and artistic vision, as well as relevance.

3.1 Agriculture

Five poets discussed agriculture in their works. They include Ọdúnjọ (1949), Atiládé (1961), Ọlabimtan (1969), Fálétí (1969 and 1982) and Ọládàpọ (1975). When agriculture was first discussed by Ọdúnjọ in 1949, which falls in the first decade of our study period, the Yorùbá society as an agrarian encouraged farming. It was one of

the oldest occupation in the society. It also turned out to be the mainstay of the economy at that time. It is not surprising therefore that while Oḍúnjọ is emphasizing the importance of education, (as it will be seen later in our discussion), paradoxically, he also makes a case for the indispensability of the farmers in the society. His poem, 'Ágbẹ̀' (The Farmer) shows the socio-economic importance of the farmer who is self-sufficient in his farming enterprises: agricultural crops and animal husbandry and hunting expedition:

Ágbẹ̀ loníjẹ àmóḍún

- - -

Bo ti n fiṣu ṣọlá

Ló n fi yangan ṣakọ

- - -

Èranko to ṣẹṣẹ pa ló n se lóbẹ

Àkùkẹ tó tákùkọ

Iwọ lò n níruú rẹ lóḍḍẹ¹

(Oḍúnjọ 1949b:35)

It is the farmer that reaps something yearly
 - - -

As he can boast of plenty of yams

He also has surplus corn
 - - -

It is also fresh bushmeat that he cooks

Cocks that are extra big

It is you that have such at home.

(Our Translation)¹

Apart from the fact that the farmer is self-sufficient, he eats his farm products fresh. It would seem the poet is full of admiration for the farmers who are not liability to the society in food production. Their efforts would definitely facilitate the economic growth of the society.

Even at the time Ọdúnjọ was a teacher, the school placed premium on farming like the community. Every primary school had a farm developed within the school compound or on a parcel of vacant land not far from the school. Further, each class in the school, particularly the senior classes had Gardening on their School Time-

1. All other translations are ours except otherwise stated.

table at least once a week. This no doubt, had encouraged a song which was popularized by Honourable Dr Nnamdi Azikiwe, President of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, among the school pupils:

Iṣẹ́ àgbẹ̀ niṣẹ́ ilẹ̀ wa
Iwé kíkọ́ láá sí ọkọ́ àti àdà
Kòì pé o kòì pé o.

Farming is native to our land
Whoever does not work will steal
Education without farming
It is not complete, it is not complete.

As an advocate of an education with self-reliance, Ọdúnjọ in an interview with the Happy-Home Magazine states as follows;

Our education must be re-orientated to make the children want to work, want to use their hands ... if education is to be useful then, anybody studying agriculture must not only be overwhelmed with the theory of the course but this theory should be coordinated with practical know-how. (p. 41)

This shows the importance Qdúnjọ attaches to agriculture which was formerly the back-bone of Nigerian economy. At the time Qdúnjọ wrote this poem, only few of the educated elites could boast of the comfort the farmer he depicts in the text has. This was the enviable position of the farmer in the fifties. Unfortunately, now, the lands have been over-cultivated. At the time of Qdúnjọ's poem, most farmer could spend less money on the farm and still get an amazing returns. The land was naturally fertile.

Qdúnjọ's use of indigenous Yorùbá names for some agricultural products does not show him as someone that is familiar with the farm alone but that he identifies himself with the farmer. Such agricultural products he mentions are yangan, ewùrà and èsúró. Yangan (maize) is an exclusive indigenous and poetic name for àgbàdo (a more common name), while ewùrà and èsúró are varieties of yam. All this makes the poem very rich.

Agriculture also played a significant role in the economy of Nigeria during the 1960-69 decade of our study period. By then, cotton and groundnut came from the North,

palm products from the East while cocoa was produced mainly in the West. Each of these export crops had had its own fluctuating fortune at different times. Cocoa, for instance, was the toast of the Nigerian farmers in the fifties and sixties. In his own contribution on the importance of agriculture on the Nigerian economy, Atiládé in his poem, *Agbàdo Àti Iṣu Dità Sí Baba Olóko'* (Maize and Yam Conspire Against the Farmer) states:

Kòkó, kòkó igi owó dé
 Ni gbogbo àgbè ba p'agbó run;
 Iṣu àtàgbàdo dohun àsáti:
 Igi owó lómọ araiye mba lọ
 Igbó odò wa di bánki kòkó
 - - -
 Gbogbo'lẹ àtátà ló ti bágbà kòkó lọ
 1áá'

Cocoa, cocoa, the cash crop has arrived
And then all farmers cultivated all the forest
Both yam and maize were neglected
It was the cash crop that was followed by everybody
Fertile riverbanks became the custody of cocoa

- - -

All arable farmlands had been utilized for cocoa.

In this poem, the poet is reacting to the insatiable urge by the farmers for cocoa which was in great demand in the fifties and sixties. It was a valuable revenue generating agricultural product. It, indeed made the former Western Region of Nigeria economically bouyant. For instance, the Western Region was the first Region out of the former three Regions in the Federation to introduce free primary education which was comparatively very successful (Nduka 1964:116-118). Obviously, good vision, good planning coupled with the heavy revenue from cocoa made this possible. No doubt, cocoa brought substantial cash income, both to the Government and the farmers. But this high demand for cocoa was at the expense of actual food production by farmers as reflected

in the text above.

Cocoa farmers left their less fertile farms in their villages "in search of land to rent or buy more fertile, thickly forested Ondo and Ijẹṣa areas of the South and East" (Barber 1991:48) Barber here, refers to cocoa farmers from Òkukù, a town in Òṣun State some few kilometres north of Òṣogbo, the State Capital. This observation is also true of other towns in the old Western Region of Nigeria. Many cocoa farmers had travelled far from their towns to acquire "new" land for cocoa plantation. This is reflected in Atiládé's poem under reference;

Kòkó, kòkó, igi owó dé
Ni gbogbo àgbè bá pa gbó run

Cocoa, cocoa, the cash crop has arrived
And then all farmers cultivated all the
forest.

Socially, cocoa farming turned round the fortune of the farmers during this period. Cocoa farmers were the richest in the towns. Cocoa completely changed the

orientation of the people, hence the rendition of the popular song that gained ground in the fifties and sixties:

Kòkó n̄ ẹ̀e n̄nkan
 Kòkó n̄ ẹ̀e n̄nkan
 Ẹ̀lẹ̀wù kan dẹ̀lẹ̀wù méjì
 Kòkó n̄ ẹ̀e n̄nkan

Cocoa is performing wonders
 Cocoa is performing wonders
 A man with a single dress now has two
 Cocoa is performing wonders

Perhaps, the economic importance of cocoa compels Atiládé to state;

Kòkó, kòkó igi owó dé

Cocoa, Cocoa, the cash crop has arrived.

Another point is the poet's reaction to too much premium been placed on acquisition of money by the Yorùbá society. It is no surprise then that the poet cried out that the farmers concentrated too much on cashcrop (cocoa) to the detriment of food crops (maize and yam) and this

was bound to spell doom for the economy and indeed, it spelt the doom. This prompts the poet to say:

Owó, owó lawó ké, ké, ké
 Tó fi dará'nu 'gbó:
 Owó l'àwọn bōkinní wá lọ s'Ókè Odò
 Tí gbogbo wọn fi baiye lọ

It was the persistent cry of money by the
 guinea-fowl

That made it become an inhabitant of the
 forest

It was money that the noble went in search
 of in far away places

That made all of them go astray.

The poet's concern here as contained in the line above is the apparent general error of judgement on the part of government and the cocoa farmers to have abandoned everything else in favour of cocoa business. It is implied that it is a people unwittingly opening its doors to famine and preventable starvation. The poet, in an allusion to the guinea-fowl, warns on how greed and error

of judgement brought disaster upon it:

Owó, owó lawó ké, ké, ké

Tó fi dará'nu'gbó:

It is the persistent cry of money by the
guinea-fowl

That makes it become an inhabitant of the
forest.

It is true cocoa is very valuable and it is a strong revenue generating crop but the foodcrops should not be neglected. The view expressed by the poet shows his support for a balanced agrarian life which recognizes the importance of food production.

Atiládé's warning on the need for a balanced agrarian life though timely, was hardly heeded. Besides the implications of monoculturism and the fact that the cocoa business was and still, is subject to vagaries of weather, foreign market forces and other economic variables, cocoa has lost its past glory as a leading export crop in Nigeria. Nevertheless, the effect of the neglect suffered by food crops in those days lingers on.

Most of the arable land used for cocoa is not easily convertible to growing food crops. Most of the cocoa farms of the fifties have stopped production, thus leaving the land unserviceable for other crops.

It is pertinent to note that what Atiládé predicted in this poem in 1961 about the negative effect of deforestation for the plantation of cocoa at the expense of food crops is re-echoed by Qládàpò (1975) in these lines:

Bá à bá tètè

Ká tójú oko

- - -

Tí a bá òfowó dẹ̀ngbẹ̀rẹ̀ múşẹ̀ oko ẹ̀

Àfàìmò o -

Kiyàn ó má ja wá o - Àfàìmò (p 229)

If we do not act fast

And enhance farming

- - -

If we continue to handle farming with levity

It is doubtful

That we would not experience famine - it is
doubtful.

All the thick forest that gave way for cocoa planting in the fifties has laid bare the once fertile land. The land is now vulnerable to severe ecological degradation and denudation. The Government's acknowledgement of the full implications of this development has led to recent campaign encouraging the masses to plant trees.

Ọlabimtan (1969) and Fálétí (1969), in their separate works, place premium on the importance and indispensability of farmers to the society. In 'Ọbalolo', Ọlabimtan writes;

Mo dádé ílá, adé àgbàdo
 Mo wẹ̀wù oyè, ẹ̀wù bàbà
 Mo wọ̀ bàtà oyè, awọ ẹ̀tu
 Mo ñse bí í Kábiyèsí, Ọba láàfin
 (Ọlabimtan 1969:9)

I put on a big crown, crown made of corn
 I put on a chief's garment, garment made of
 guinea-corn
 I put on a chief's shoes, made from the
 Duiker's leather
 I begin to act like an Ọba in the palace.

This poem shows the pastoralist feeling of a poet in celebrating the self-sufficiency of a farmer's life. To the poet, a farmer is an "Ọba" who lives a regal life that nature endows him with. In this text, the poet depicts a typical indigenous Yorùbá farmer that harnesses nature fully to his advantage. There is an air of contentment exhibited by the farmer in the poem. He is never in want of what to eat. He gets all his food-stuffs readily. The poet gives the example of 'àgbàdo' (corn) and 'bàbà' (guinea-corn). Apart from the abundant bushmeat he gets, he also gets leather from the animals which he makes into shoes. He says:

Mo wọ bàtà oyè, awọ ẹtu

I put on shoes of a chief made from
the Duiker's leather.

One of the many products of animal husbandry is the animal's rich skin for leather works including shoe-making and handbags. The farmer also has different types of vegetables within his reach. Because of his closeness to nature, the agrarian farmer has mystical power. He is surrounded on the farm by different leaves used for herbs

by the Yorùbá. He says:

Mo pe èédégbèrún ewéko, nwón jé mi

which literally means he is in control of different types of medicinal leaves. It shows the ease with which the farmer gets numerous leaves that he could use for medicine. In Yorùbá tradition, every farmer is a potential medicine man. He knows at least which leaf to look for to treat simple ailments such as stomach ache, headache, fever and the like. The farmer therefore feels secure to stay on the farm. This is one of the reasons he is happy to make the farm his home. He says:

Mo fadaiyeba ògèrè ilẹ̀ sẹ̀'bùsùn

I use the ordinary ground as my bed.

Usually the Yorùbá farmer has two types of farmsteads. There is oko itòsì (nearby-farm) where he goes and returns daily. There is also oko-ìwájú (distant-farm) where he stays for some days because of its distance from the town. He builds a hut where he stays and comes home occasionally either on market days to sell his farm

products or to attend meetings (family or communal rites/festivals.) With the provision of where to lay his head on and all his needs within his reach, the farmer feels contented with the agrarian life. It is interesting to note that Christopher Marlowe one of the great English pastoralist poets had expressed similar idea in "The Passionate Shepherd To His Love". The two poets though belonged to different ages and cultures have achieved the same goal.

Qlabimtan is no doubt, on the side of the farmer. He writes to attract more people to the farm. The negative attitude of the society to subsistence farming in the sixties had affected the socio-economic equilibrium of Nigeria. The concern of the poet was to see more people return to the land in order to enhance the country's economy. The poet does this by employing the use of repetition, particularly, of first person pronoun, 'Mo' (I) to make his appeal more definite. This personal experience is aimed at convincing the people of the need to support foodcrop farming. His listing of some agricultural products such as 'àgbàdo' (maize), 'bàbà' (guinea

corn), 'ilá' (okro), 'ikàn' (garden-egg) also goes to show the extent of his familiarity with the farm, and which in turn helps his campaign to revive farming.

Fálétí also reiterates the importance of the farmer to the society in his poem, 'Iṣẹ̀ Àgbẹ̀' (Farming) in these lines:

Bágbẹ̀ bá kọ̀ tí kò ṣàgbẹ̀

- - -

Kíni kí gbogbo wa o máa jẹ?

- - -

Iṣẹ̀ àgbẹ̀ ló pé, fáàrí kò pé

Ẹ̀ jẹ̀ ká fọ̀lá fẹ̀ni tí ńroko

(Akínjógbín (ed.) 1969:119)

If the farmers refuse to farm

- - -

What will all of us be feeding on?

- - -

It is farming that is profitable,
ostentation does not pay

Let us respect those who farm.

In this text, the poet raises the position of farmers in

the society high as it is obvious that the society cannot do without the farmers. He goes on in the poem to portray a picture of a hardworking farmer backed by a benevolent nature that supplies rain to the farm, thereby giving out a bumper harvest. This is seen in

--- wata bó ti pón lọ

--- wẹ̀pà tó ta kalẹ̀ lẹ̀bẹ̀!

Wàgbàdo ti gbómọ pọ̀n láàrin oko

--- woşu bo ti tóbi lọ! (p 119)

--- see the ripe pepper in great numbers

--- see how the groundnut has fared in
the heaps

See the corn bearing corbs on the farm

--- see how big the yam tubers are!

This picture is an attractive portrayal of the richness and beauty of farm life. By that time, the farm had been neglected in favour of petroleum that was already dominating the economy of Nigeria. It is this trend that the poet is reacting against.

But the suggested threat in,

Ti nwọn dẹiyẹ sáwa ti kí í ẹ̀gbẹ̀

Ti nwọn kò tájà fún wa mọ nkọ -

(And they decide to do away with those
that are not farmers

And they stop selling their products
to us -)

cannot be taken seriously. We do not subscribe to such threat. If the farmers stop selling their products to the society, what will happen to their products? The farmers cannot consume everything they produce by themselves and more importantly, the farmers need money to settle other essentials of life. The farmers cannot be an island to themselves. What we should emphasise is the need for everybody to take farming serious.

But Ọládàpọ (1975), seeing the deplorable state of farming in Nigeria, quickly cries to the Government to improve the system of agriculture in Nigeria in order to encourage the so-called educated elites to farm. Having examined why farming in Nigeria has failed, Ọládàpọ

offers his suggestion for improvement in the following lines:

Bá à bá tètè mọ̀nà ọ̀lájú
 Tárá asálẹ̀ nífi ní ẹ̀gbẹ̀ ńròrùn
 Bá à bá tètè
 Ka tọ̀jú oko
 Kálákọ̀wé ó lẹ̀ roko
 Tá a bá ńfọ̀wọ̀ ẹ̀ngbẹ̀rẹ̀ múşé oko ẹ̀
 Àfàìmọ̀ o
 Kíyàn ó má jà wá o - Àfàìmọ̀ (p 229)

If we do not hasten to find modern ways
 That people in arid land use to farm with ease
 If we do not make haste
 And give attention to farming
 So that the civil servants could farm
 If we continue to handle farming with levity
 It is doubtful
 That we would not have famine - it is doubtful.

It is obvious that mechanized farming is the answer as suggested by the poet in the poem. Both Ọ̀dúnjọ̀ (1949), Ọ̀labimtan (1969) and Fálétí (1969) wrote on the glorifica-

tion of farming when the farmer was a king on the farm because of his food sufficiency. Those were the days of subsistence farming. The economic situation of the present day has made Qládàpò (1975) take a radical stand to advocate for mechanized farming. Therefore to enable the farmers engage in this, government would have to come to their aid.

3.2 Census in Nigeria

What can be termed the first census in Nigeria was conducted in 1866, and this was followed by another one in 1871. The National Population Commission (NPC) further reveals,

thereafter censuses were conducted on decennial basis except for the disruption in 19th1 due to the second world war. Most of these earlier censuses were, however, mere population estimates. The census of 1952/53 was the first elaborate population census in the country¹

1 1991 Population Census Enumerator's Manual, National Population Commission, Lagos, Oct. 1991, p.1.

The first post-independence census in Nigeria was conducted in 1963. This was followed by another one in 1973. The exercise was so politicized and characterized by deliberate inaccurate census figures that it was finally declared unacceptable. A most recent headcount was in 1991. It was also politicized and believed in many quarters to be far from reflecting the true figures.

The implications of overpoliticization of the census figures and the deliberate inadequacies for planning and policy implementation by the government are very grave to warrant the attention of the poets. Essentially the Nigerian society is largely illiterate. It was therefore assumed by most people that the reason for the headcount was for tax purposes. Hence many people ran away from being counted. Some politicians who saw the advantage of number in any democratic election deliberately encouraged falsification of census figures. Some ethnic groups, particularly the Yorùbá, are culturally forbidden from counting their children, it was a taboo to do so. Some of the poets therefore took it upon themselves to educate the masses on the purpose and advantages of an accurate headcount.

All the poets that discuss census in their works enumerate the socio-political and economic uses of census. These poets include, Qládàpò (1973), Fálétí (1973) and Qpadótun (1976). It is significant that all the three poets wrote their poems in the third decade, 1970-79 of our study period. This was the decade that another census took place in 1973. Qládàpò in 'Kààyàn-Kààyàn' (The Enumerator), says:

Torí, bí nwọ́n bá fẹ́ kọ́lẹ́ ẹ́ẹ́ fún wọ́n nílẹ́
Igbón

Nwọ́n a ní, nwọ́n ọ́ kúkú to ñńkan kan
Bí nwọ́n sí fẹ́ tẹ́lẹ́-íwé fún wọ́n lónà Arẹ̀sà
Nwọ́n a ní, nwọ́n ọ́ pọ́ tó gbalé-íwé
Kí nwọ́n ó máa kọ́mọ́ wọ́n bọ́ nílẹ́ Ịbàdàn
Bí nwọ́n sí tún fẹ́ kọ́lẹ́ ẹ́wòsàn ọ́fẹ́
Fún wọ́n gbádùn nílùú àlẹ́mọ́kan
Nwọ́n a níwòsàn ọ́fẹ́ ọ́ sí
È jẹ́ a lẹ́ kọ́ wọ́n sílùú ràbàtá
(1973:36)

For, if government decides to establish
factories at Ilé-Igbón
It would be said they are not tangible in number

And if it is a school that government plans to
establish at Arẹ̀sà

It would be said they are not numerically strong
to have a school being cited there

They should send their children to Ibàdàn

And if the government wants to build hospital
for free medical services

For the use of the unenlightened populace .

They would say there is no free medical service

Let us transfer it to the big towns.

Here, the poet indirectly enumerates the importance of census to the society. However, through the ignorance of the people and their negative attitude to census exercise, they were deprived of basic social amenities. It is obvious from Qladapọ's stance that the data from census are used for social planning purposes.

In a vein similar to Qládàpọ (1973), Fálétí (1973) also reiterates the need to be counted for adequate information for good planning. In 'Ìsìrò Ní Gbogbo Nùkan', he says:

Ó níhun tọ́ba rí
 Kọ́ba ó tó sọ pé kí wọ́n ó kani
 Kí lànfààní ọ́ba tí ò lénlyàn?

- - -

Ọ̀pọ̀ ọ̀mọ̀ lẹ̀pọ̀ 1yí
 Ọ̀pọ̀ ènlyàn lẹ̀pọ̀ ànfààní
 Jẹ́ kí wọ́n ó kà ọ̀ mégbẹ́ rẹ́
 Àgbẹ́ tí yóò bẹ̀lùbọ̀
 Ẹ̀ sẹ̀sírò 1şu
 Kómi ó má pọ̀ jọkà lórí iná

(Ọ̀latúnjí 1982b:69).

The Ọ́ba has his reasons
 For asking the people to be counted
 What is the benefit of an ọ́ba that has no
 followership

- - -

The more the number of children the more
 is one's honour
 The more the number of people, the more the
 benefit
 Allow yourself to be counted with others
 A farmer that desires to prepare yamflour

Will consider the cost of yamflour
So that the water will not be too much for
the flour.

Fálétí, in this text, explains why census is desirable. He goes into the animal world, using the goat and the monkey satirically, to disabuse the mind of those who, because of culture would refuse headcount.

From the points raised by Fálétí, his posture is seen in his blame for the people who, owing to ignorance, deprive themselves of the social amenities they deserve. Fálétí explains this using simple analogy that the people are familiar with. He says:

Jé kí wọn o kà ọ mégbéè rẹ
Àgbè tí yóò bẹ̀lùbọ̀
È ẹ̀şẹ̀şirò ịşu
Ọşùwọ̀n èlùbọ̀ lalámọ̀là í fí í díwọ̀n ọkà
È moye èlùbọ̀
Kómi ó má pọ̀ ọkà lórí iná

Allow yourself to be counted with others
A farmer that desires to prepare yamflour
Will consider the cost of yamflour
The quantity of yamflour will determine the
quantity of ọkà

You must know the quantity of yamflour
 So that the water will not be too much for
 the flour.

This allusion to "èlùbọ" and "water" in the preparation of "ọkà" - meal is the poet's explanation of what the government does with census. It is when the government has the correct census figures that will be able to make adequate provision for the citizenry through prudent management of its available resources. This is an indication of the poet's support for the government programme on headcount.

The imaginary story of the two animals, the goat and the monkey exemplified by Fálétí in the poem is to show his displeasure of the culture that forbids counting of children. He says:

Ìwọ ò bímọ tó pọ tó tẹmí

Èmí ò bímọ tó pọ tó tíẹ

- - -

Ọrọ yí náà ló díyàn láwùjọ ẹranko

Níjọ ewúré n sùnkún ọmọ lágbo

Tọbọ n yọ ẹẹẹẹ wí pọmọ òún pọ

Lẹnikan bá wò sùnsùn

O ní ẹ má jẹẹ kọrọ ó pé

Ẹ jẹ ká kamọ tóníkálùkùù yíu gbogbo
(Ọlatunji 1982b:69-70)

You have not got as many children as mine
I have not got as many children as yours

- - -

It is this issue that brought about the argument
among the animal world

The day the goat was lamenting in public over the
issue of children

Suddenly, someone thought of a solution.
He asked them not to prolong the matter
Let us count everybody's children

It is a satire of the politics of census in Nigeria.

Every ethnic group wants to inflate its numerical figure in order to get a larger share of the national 'cake'. A major ethnic group is metaphorically referred to as òbọ (monkey) while the other is represented by ewúrẹ. The choice of 'ewúrẹ' (goat) and 'òbọ' (monkey) is culturally informed. Both animals are characteristically

heady and intransigent. The story as summarised in those few lines of the poem confirms this. One inflates the number of its children, the other would not agree that its children be counted. A true reflection of the regional attitude to census. A Yorùbá saying states;

A ì í ka omọ fólómọ

It is a taboo to count one's children.

It is this old traditional belief that makes the 'goat' (Yorùbá) plead to be exempted from counting her children. The point Fálétí is trying to make is that failure to get counted could result in under-estimation of a particular ethnic group.

Fálétí's conclusion shows his rejection of that Yorùbá traditional belief that one's children should not be counted. He expects the Yorùbá to emulate the goat in the poem that changes from its hardline stand on counting of one's children and surrenders himself and the children for enumeration.

Similarly, Ọpádòtun (1976) spells out the various complaints of the people about their basic social needs

that are lacking. In 'Ìkàńyàn' (Nigerian census), he says:

"Ilú mi ò níná"

"Àdúgbò mi ò lẹ̀rọ omi"

"Títì abúlé wa ò lódà lórí"

(p. 13)

"My town has no electricity"

"Our quarters has no pipe-borne water"

"The road to our village is not tarred"

- - -

In this text above, Ọpádòtun indirectly enumerates why census is a necessary exercise for any government that must succeed. The provision of these amenities, to a large extent, depends on the existing population of each area. This is one of the reasons why such amenities are concentrated in the urban areas where the population is thick. If the various governments provide amenities in the rural areas, it will stop the problem of rural-urban migration and census falsification will be reduced to the bearest minimum.

Common to these poets on the subject of census is

the fact that they all try to enlighten the society on the need for a reliable census. The Yorùbá poets as the mouthpiece of the people take it as a duty to re-orientate their fellow compatriots who have misconstrued the census exercise to be a means to exploit the populace through revenue generation.

3.3 Politics

The post-independence politics in Nigeria is by far different from the colonial era when there was an imposed colonial government. The reason is obvious, the principal actors in the two phases are different; one is colonial and the other is indigenous. What really agitated the minds of the poets before independence was how to emancipate the people from colonial bondage through their writings. Immediately after independence, the poets shifted their critical focus to the activities of the self-government. They considered their roles as complementing Government's enlightenment efforts, as government advisers and as the mouth-piece of the people. Several of them began to suggest ways of improving the lots of the people and also the need for the unity of the

people to move the country forward.

Political theme runs through the works of most of the poets that published their poems during these three decades 1960-69, 1970-79 and 1980-89, of our study period. These poets include, Atiládé (1961), Qdúnjọ (1961), Qlabimtan (1969, 1974, 1988), Fálétí (1969), Qpádọtun (1987) and Adépọjù (1985, 1986, 1987).

Atiládé is one of the foremost poets who wrote immediately after the attainment of the Nigerian independence. His main concern was the unity of the country, considering the heterogeneity of the numerous ethnic groups that make up Nigeria. In his poem, 'Ayọ Òmìnira Nigeria' (The Joy of Nigeria Independence), he says:

- - -

Ẹ ba mi gbe'di fúu Lugardi,

- - -

Tó wó àsíá Ẹgbẹ Royal Niger palẹ

Tó sí gbé ti Ìjọba Gẹsi ró

- - -

Baba oníkálàmù Ìbọn, onímọràn idà

- - -

Ó fọ'gbón so'run 'wájú

Pọ mọ típàkọ

- - -

Ó mú Yorùbá 'Wọ Òrùn:

Ó mú Ibo ní'là Òrùn:

O pa wọn pọ mọ Hausa Òkè Odò Qya;

(Atíládé 1961:122)

- - -

Let us give respect to Lugard,
That revoked the Royal Niger Company Charter
And raised the British Government's flag

- - -

The man with the pen of gun, a sharp adviser

- - -

He used his sense
To cause confusion

- - -

He chose the Yorùbá in the West
He chose the Ibo in the East
And put them together with the Hausa of
the Upper Niger

This poem which was written in 1961 immediately after the Nigeria independence, highlights the political achievement of Sir Frederick Lugard, the founder of

modern Nigeria. Nigeria came into being in its present form in 1914 when the Northern and Southern protectorates were amalgamated by Sir Lugard. This amalgamation did not take into cognizance the fact that the people differ widely in customs, in outlook and in their traditional system of government. Despite the apparent idiosyncratic differences among its various component groups, Nigeria became a sovereign federation on October 1st, 1960. It is this historical account of Lugard's amalgamation of the South and the North that the poet refers to in the poem. This diversity in culture, in religion and general outlook, made some critics including the British who created it (Nigeria) to doubt the survival of Nigeria as a political entity. This is the stand of the poet as reflected in the lines below:

Ó fọgbón so'run'wájú

Pọmọ tipàkọ

which literally means he tactfully ties the hair of the forehead with that of the occiput. Whoever does this, to the Yorùbá, is a confusionist because a situation so created is an uneasy union. The result could be very

agonizing. Politically, Nigeria now still suffers the pains of that amalgamation of 1914. The poet's observation is a reflection of the socio-political situation of Nigeria in 1961, which still persists till date. His language shows that he opposes the amalgamation of the South and the North when he says:

Ó fọgbọ̀n so'run 'wájú
Pọ̀ mọ̀ tipàkọ̀

He used his sense
To cause confusion

It is this same socio-political situation in the Nigeria of 1961 that is reflected in lines of the poem. The people mentioned, Awolọwọ, Balewa, Akintọla, Okpara, Azikiwe and Sardauna were the first pre-independence Nigerian leaders representing the three major political groupings. Awolọwọ and Akintọla were the leaders of the Action Group Party which had its base in the West; Azikiwe and Okpara from the East, represented the National Council of Nigeria and Cameroons (NCNC) Party while the third group is led by Balewa and Sardauna who were the leaders of the Northern Peoples Congress (NPC)

Party. The NPC and the NCNC formed a coalition Government leaving the AG in the opposition. Alhaji Abubakar Tafawa Balewa became the Prime Minister and Dr Azikiwe, the leader of the NCNC became the Governor-General of the independent federation on 16th November, 1960. Chief Obafemi Awólówò remained the Leader of Opposition in the Federal House of Assembly.¹

This was the political situation when the poem under reference was written. With this arrangement, it needed the cooperation of the leaders to make Nigeria survive as a nation. The arrangement of the combination of the leaders was not an accident, it was intentional. For example, the first line,

FAwólówò ati Balewa

Balewa was the Prime Minister, the leader of the Government in the House of Representatives while Awólówò was the leader of Opposition. In the second line,

FÁkíntólá àti Okpara,

¹ For further reading on the politics after independence, see Michael Crowder, The Story of Nigeria, Faber and Faber, London, 1962.

Akintola was the Premier of the Western Region while Okpara was the Premier of the Eastern Region. And in line three,

FÀzikiwe àti Sardauna,
Azikiwe was the Leader of the junior partner in the coalition government while Sardauna was the Leader of the senior partner.

The poet had earlier in the poem made another historical allusion to the Royal Nigeria Company where he says:

È bá mi gbédi fun Lugaṛddi
Ọkùnrin ọlọgbón, ọkùnrin ológun
Tó wó asia Ègbé Royal Niger palẹ

Let us give respect to Lugard
The man with wisdom, the military man
That revoked the Royal Niger Company's Charter.

The mission of the Royal Niger Company to Nigeria was mainly economical. It established and nurtured the Palm-oil Trade in the Niger Delta. Its leading architect and patron was Sir George Taubman Goldie. The Company later ran into problems with Lugard over 'monopoly' and threat to easy colonization and its consolidation. The

Charter of the Company was therefore withdrawn.¹ It is the revocation of the Charter of the Royal Niger Company that the poet refers to in the lines quoted above. Amalgamation of Nigeria and the attendant problems since 1914 constitute the bulk of the poet's concern in "Ayọ̀ Ọ̀minira".

In this poem, Atiládé makes extensive use of metaphor. For instance, he ways:

Tó fikuku jàkùmò ká ehín ikokò

Tó fèkáná àwòdi tú ifun àşá

That used the fist of the wildcat to remove
the teeth of the hyena

That used the nails of the special kite to
remove the intestines of another kite

In using these figurative utterances, the poet is covertly commenting on Lugard's high-handedness in his administration of Nigeria. The same high-handedness is depicted by the poet's use of animals and birds of the same family to destroy each other in describing Lugard's absurd political arrangement for Nigeria. Both jàkùmò and

¹ For further information about the activities of the Royal Niger Company in Nigeria, see K.O. Dike, Trade and Politics on the Niger Delta, London, 1956.

ikokò are in the same animal family. Apart from their identical features, dangerous and wild-looking, they are carnivorous animals. So also are àwòdì and àsá which are birds. This arrangement is analogous to what happens in:

Ó mú Yorùbá 'Wọ̀ Òrùn
 Ó mú Ibo nílà Òrùn
 Ó pa wọn pọ̀ mọ̀ Hausa òkè odò Ọya

He chose Yorùbá in the West
 He took the Ibo in the East
 And merged them with the Hausa of the
 Upper Niger.

The use of figurative language is also evident in:

Ó fòlù bàmbà
 Wó òjé pọ̀ mọ̀ bàbà
 - - -
 Ó fẹ̀wiri ogbón àlùmọ̀kọ̀rọ̀yín
 Fínná rọ̀ orílẹ̀-èdè Nigeria titun
 (Atiládé 1961:122)

He used heavy mallet
 To grind the metal lead with the copper
 - - -
 He used the bellows of mischief

To smelt the new Nigerian nation.

'Ojé' (metal lead) and 'bàbà' (copper) are used by the Yorùbá blacksmiths to manufacture different objects. Both òjé and bàbà are never mixed together. The mixing together of the two symbolizes incongruity in Yorùbá worldview. Putting people of different ethnic groups together, thereby causing disharmony is what Lugard cleverly did. These metaphorical expressions are very effective. They bring out the intended meanings more clearly, that is, merging incongruous people together.

Qdúnjọ (1961) joins Atíládé (1961) in stressing the importance of unity in 'Nipa Irépò Ilú Naijiria' (About the Unity of Nigeria). He says:

Irépò ní so ilú ró
 Bí a ba pín léyọ ogun ní
 Şùgbọn wíwà pọ nikan kò tó;
 Ó yẹ ká fífẹ pẹlú:

(Qdúnjọ 1961:85)

It is unity that sustains a country
 If we are divided, it is war that will result
 But coming together is not enough
 It is pertinent that we should add love to it

Ọdúnjọ's nationalist spirit is demonstrated in his love for his mother-tongue that culminated in his publication of several Yorùbá readers that were mentioned earlier in this work. He was once the Assistant Secretary-General of the Nigerian Union of Teachers from 1942-1951. Ọdúnjọ was taken to be one of the architects of the Nigerian independence. It was in recognition of these immense contributions to nation building that he was made Minister for Lands and Natural Resources in the Old Western Region of Nigeria from 1952-1956. Ọdúnjọ's experience as a Minister would have enabled him to recognise the need for unity which he emphasises in his poem.

The poet uses Yorùbá philosophy to demonstrate the importance of unity in these lines:

E wo eyọ ẹgbálẹ ti ó rọ ti o si tin-in-rin
 Pẹrẹ-pẹrẹ ni ayé í ẹẹ wọn;
 Ẹ̀gbọ̀n bí wọ̀n bá dí pọ̀
 Kò sẹ̀ni tó lẹ̀ tẹ̀ wọ̀n ẹ́
 Típẹ̀-típẹ̀ ni wọ̀n í rọ̀ gbogbo

Imagine a stick of broom that is very thin
 Easily it is broken into pieces

But when they are tied together
 No one can break them
 They stick to one and so tightly

He shows how easily a single broom stick could be broken into pieces against the impossible task of attempting to break a bundle of broom sticks. This analogy is taken from a very common Yorùbá saying. Therefore, it makes the message clear.

Like Atiládé whose poems on politics we have just examined, Ọdúnjọ further elaborates on what unity could achieve in the traditional Yorùbá philosophy informed by natural phenomena:

Ọpọ̀ gírí ẹ̀sẹ̀ ní í yẹ̀'nà
 Ọpọ̀ ẹ̀sú a máa yagí
 Ọpọ̀ ọ̀jò a di àgbàrá
 Ọpọ̀ àgbàrá a di odò ńlá
 Ọpọ̀ odò níf dòkun

It is the multitudinous trampling of feet
 that clears the path

A gathering of locust could break down a tree
 A gathering of rain become a flood
 A gathering of floods become big rivers
 A gathering of rivers join together to
 become an ocean.

These are small elements that combine to perform enormous task. Qdúnjò's society is familiar with these observations. It is a Yorùbá philosophy that emphasizes what unity can achieve. In other words, it is concerted efforts that could bring about positive results.

It was unity, among other things that Nigeria needed most in 1961 when this poem was written, to be able to move forward as a nation. The timing of the poem is significant. First, the Federal election of 1959 brought about a lot of rancour that could jeopardize the fragile unity of the country. Second, the independence had just been achieved on October 1, 1960 and the colonialists had just handed over the baton of governance to the Nigerians. The need for unity was therefore very imperative.

The other poet that comments on politics during the 1960-69 decade is Qlabimtan. Unlike Atiládé, Qlabimtan

himself was a politician. He was known to be an ardent supporter of Chief Qbáfẹmi Awolówọ, the leader of the defunct Action Group (AG). He could not show this support openly then because, as a civil servant he was by ethics, prevented from doing so.

Qlabimtan writes several poems on the political intrigue between the leader of the party in control of the old Western Nigeria Government and his deputy between 1960 and 1965. These poems which are couched in powerful imagery include 'Ìjà Ọ̀ṣùpá Pẹ̀lú Oòrùn', 'Ọ̀tẹ̀-ò-lówọ, 'Ọ̀tító Pẹ̀lú Èké' and 'Ìjà Ọ̀mìnira'. In all these poems, the poet's bias against the deputy of the leader of the party is obvious. We shall illustrate this with 'Ìjà Ọ̀ṣùpá pẹ̀lú Oòrùn' (The Fight Between the Moon and the Sun). It says:

Ọ̀yájú ọ̀ṣùpá, tẹ̀nikẹ̀ni kò jọ lójú
 Ló yájú sójú Oluwa ọba
 Ló fọwọ́ fahun tí kò tó dání
 Lògúnná gbòngbò, aragajigijigi,
 Ọ̀gbóná-mọ̀lẹ̀, kirúnmọ̀lẹ̀ kẹ̀ riri
 Ba bínú wọ̀lé lọ̀sàn-án

Ni gbogbo wa ba bọ sóókùn biribiri
 - - -

Şùgbón kàkà kómọ wéwé b'óşùpá

Oòrùn ni nwọn íforin bẹ kiri

Nwọn ní: Oorùn fàşùpá 'lẹ o

àlìjanjankíjan

Oòrùn fòşùpá 'lẹ o

àlìjanjankíjan

B'o o bá fòşùpá 'lẹ o

àlìjanjankíjan

'Wa gbà yín funrarẹ

àlìjanjankíjan

- - -

(Ọlabimtan 1969:13)

The intransigent moon that had no respect for
 anyone

That insulted our Creator, the King
 And by so doing, outstepped its bound

And so the mighty huge flaming-brand
 That-which-is-so-powerful to frighten the
 Earth's spirits

Grew annoyed and set in the mid-day.

As a result, we were all thrown into darkness

- - -

But instead of the children castigating the moon
It was the sun that they were appealing to with
their song.

saying:

Sun forgive the moon
àlìjanjankíjan
Sun forgive the moon
àlìjanjankíjan
If you do not forgive the moon
àlìjanjankíjan
It will be a self-honour
àlìjanjankíjan

The whole poem is presented and fashioned along Yorùbá folk-tale narration. This is particularly evident in the popular folk-tale song incorporated into the poem for effective audience participation. Personification which is an important ingredient in folk-tale narration is employed by the poet in the use of 'sun' and 'moon'.

On the surface, the whole account as expressed by the poet, is a scene of an eclipse which in a Yorùbá mythology is a fight between two heavenly bodies - the sun and the moon. But it goes beyond that, it is a satire of the political wrangle that took place in the former Western Region of Nigeria between 1960 and 1966. An

eclipse ordinarily brings a temporary darkness but the strife between the two leaders under reference and which the eclipse symbolises, set in motion a chain of events that culminated in the first military coup in Nigeria on January 13, 1966. The 'triumph' of the sun over the moon in the poem is perhaps the death of the deputy leader of the party, Chief S.L. Akintola in the military coup of January 13, 1966; and the subsequent release of the leader of the party, Chief Obafemi Awolowo from prison in August, 1966.

It is glaring that Olabimtan's society, his social class and the Yorùbá world-view foreground his social vision in these poems. The folk narration technique which the poet employs effectively is rooted in the Yorùbá traditional society. Like in the world of folk-tale, the poet uses personification to achieve his goal. The two main characters, the 'sun' and the 'moon' are personified and they are symbolic: the 'sun' is believed by critics to represent Awólówò, the leader of the defuncted Action Group (AG) party while the 'moon' is also believed to represent Akíntólá, his deputy. An eclipse is a common phenomenon which is the poet's depiction of an obvious

eclipse in Yorùbá political history. It was a fierce feud between the two leaders and what followed was a catalogue of woes for the Yorùbá in particular and Nigeria in general. The ripples of the 'darkness' caused by the 'eclipse' are still visible even till today in the Nigerian political system.

Ọlabímtán's poems have shown the poet as a lover of Yorùbá tradition and customs. He shows in the poem under reference that the Yorùbá are religious people. For example:

Onífá ńgbópón ifá kíákíá
 Alájà ńlájà woroworo
 Gbogba àwòrò òàṣà ńpabi f'ólúwà wọn
 Yemọja wi, wi, òṣùpá kò gbọ
 Ọràn-án-yàn fọ fọ, òṣùpá kò gbà
 Imàle ńkẹwú, ịgbàgbọ ń pe Jesu tantan

(Ọlábímtán 1969:13)

Ifá worshippers brought out their ifá divining
 trays quickly
 Those that worship the beneficent spirit (àjà)
 started using their rattle
 And all òrìṣà priests began to offer kolanuts
 to their gods
 Yemọja pleaded with the moon to no avail

Ọràn-án-yàn also pleaded but the moon
refused to listen

The Muslims intervened, the christians call
the name of Jesus.

The use of repetition in

Yemọja wí, wí, ọ̀ṣùpá kò gbọ
Ọràn-án-yàa fọ, fọ, ọ̀sùgbá kò gbà

wí, wí pleaded

fọ, fọ pleaded

also adds colour. It heightens the incorrigibility exhibited by 'ọ̀ṣùpá', thereby exposing 'ọ̀ṣùpá' as bad. The use of language here clearly condemns 'ọ̀ṣùpá'. This enables the poet to achieve his aim, to present 'ọ̀ṣùpá' as the enemy of the people.

This shows that most of the religious practised by the Yorùbá were involved in finding enduring solutions to the political problems of the old Western Nigeria but to no avail. The intensity in the use of repetition wí wí (pleaded and pleaded) and fọ, fọ (pleaded and pleaded) heightens the unyielding attitude of 'ọ̀ṣùpá' (Moon) to the pleadings of the various religious groups.

Songs in this poem are made to play their traditional

role. In the traditional Yorùbá setting, songs are to serve different purposes: to entertain, to warn, to commend, or to condemn. The efforts of the different religious bodies could not make 'the sun' shift ground but the songs of the little children did.

Although Qlabimtan succeeds in transmitting his message to his readers, the message is not convincing. Qlabimtan is apparently subjective in his analysis of the political situation in the then Western Region. His sympathy for 'the sun' in the poem is not in doubt. This is evident in his use of language, symbol and semantics:

Qyájú Ọ̀sùpá, ténikéni kò jọ lójú

- - -

Ñtorí àifẹ̀nipeni òmùgò ọ̀sùpá

It was the intransigent moon that had no
respect for anyone

- - -

All because of the disrespect exhibited by
the foolish moon.

Qualifiers like "ọ̀yájú": intransigent and "àifẹ̀nipeni òmùgò": disrespect and foolish show the condescending attitude of the poet towards the "Ọ̀sùpá": moon, that is

Akintola. The "moon" is again presented as someone that is heady and who would never listen to people's pleadings. This is shown in the following lines:

Yemọja wí, wí, Ọ̀ṣùpá kò gbọ́
 Ọ̀ràn-án-yàn fọ́, ọ̀ṣùpá kò gbà

Yemọja pleaded with the moon to no avail
 Ọ̀ràn-án-yàn also pleaded but the moon refused
 to listen.

Whereas, 'òòrùn' is presented as someone that is kind-hearted and cool-headed and very sympathetic to the cause of the masses represented by the small children. This is depicted in:

Igbà oòrùn gbọ́'gbẹ ọmọdé
 Lorí oòrùn bá wú
 Ló bá gbóṣùpá mi pátápátá
 Nimólẹ́ bá bókùnkùn mólẹ́ birikiti

When the sun heard the cry of the children
 She became elated
 And she eclipsed the moon completely
 And darkness gave way to light.

The victory of the 'sun' over the 'moon' is seen as a victory of light over darkness.

From our analysis of this poem, Olabimtan is seen as a committed commentator, though obviously partial, on the politics of the old Western Region of Nigeria. The same partiality is exhibited in his other political poems in which he represents politics of the sixties in Aádóta Aròfò. However, his attitude on political development in the 1970-79 decade of our study period is quite different. This decade is a military era.

The military era sees the Yorùbá poet a changed man who writes with an independent mind. A number of factors were responsible for this new attitude. For example, the military government is a unitary

government with no political parties, therefore the question of belonging to political parties which often were hoisted on ethnic alignment was no longer there. Similarly, education has brought an enhanced awareness too. The Yorùbá poet is no longer a "yes-sir" man as he is now brazenly outspoken. The poet therefore writes freely on both the military and the academics. The seeming cordiality between the military and the academics is shown in the political appointment offered some academics across the country. For instance, both the current Vice-Chancellor of the University of Ibadan, Professor Qm̄q̄niyi Adéw̄q̄ye and Professor Jubril Aminu, formerly of the University of Maiduguri were once at different times Ministers under the Military regime. Professor Af̄qlabi Q̄labimtan was also appointed the Commissioner for Local Government and Information under the military in Ogun State between 1976 and 1978.

The military's respect for the academics is borne out of their love for education. Many of the serving and the ex-military men found their ways into the classroom as students during the 1970-79 decade. Even General Gowon, a former Head of State of Nigeria, went back to the University to begin as an undergraduate after his exit from the Army. He now holds a Doctorate degree.

The poets have not closed their eyes to this mutual development between the military and the academics. For instance, both the military and the academics are eulogized by Olabimtan in his anthology of poems, Ewi Orisirisi. The poems he uses are fashioned along oriki bọ̀rọ̀kinní. Normally, oriki bọ̀rọ̀kinrí, which is a Yorùbá oral genre, is a celebration of a notable citizen.

In Ewi Orisirisi, Olabimtan gives the oriki of ten personalities. Most of these eulogies are politically motivated and so are considered in the present study as political poems. In 'Oriki Lóogun LÉkòró', the poet writes:

Lóogun lÉkòó
 Okúnrin jiganjigan
 Aşebélé-sòkè-dilẹ̀

Atidí-aláṣejù-bepo-'gbóná

Abánijà-má-faniya-bí-aṣọ

Odógun gbéyàwó

Lóógun lÉkòó

Akéré-má-ṣeéyànje

Qmọ ọdọ àgbà

(Ọlabimtan 1974:49)

The Lóógun lÉkòó

The powerful man

He-who-uses-tactics-to-subdue-mountain

He-who-fights someone-and-will-not-destroy him

He-who-married-when-the-war ranged on

The warlord

The small one-who-cannot-be-cheated

One-who-stays-always-with-the-elders.

As we have revealed earlier, Ọlabimtan is in the same political camp with Awolọwọ. It was Gowon,¹ who, as the Head of the Federal Military Government that released

¹ Yakubu Gowon joined the Nigerian Army in 1954 and was commissioned at Sandhurst in 1956. He attained the rank of Lt. Col. in 1963. After the counter coup of 29 July, 1966 which saw the exit of the then Head of State, Major-General Aguiyi-Ironsi, Lt. Col. Gowon became the Head of State on August 1, 1966. He successfully led Nigeria through the Civil War of 1967-70.

Awólówò from prison in 1966 where, he (Awólówò) was serving a ten-year jail for treason. The role Gowon played in his release endears Gowon to the poet. The poet therefore singles out Gowon to highlight the politics of the Civil War.

The poem, Oríki Lóógun lÉkòó depicts Gowon's achievement during the Nigerian Civil War. The meaning of the first line, Lóógun lÉkòó (Warlord), an appellation, is a testimony to the militariness of the subject, that is Gowon. The term was coined from the description of the appearance of the West African Frontier Force (W.A.F.F.) in Lagos in 1897 which was referred to by the Yorùbá as "Lóógun lÉkòó", a term which literally means "warrior in Lagos". Since that time, "Lóógun lÉkòó" has become a common Yorùbá saying to describe an unusual person; a queer person; a trickster; and a looter. The lines of the poem justify all this. To have married while a war was on is unusual of a General; to have a small stature and yet cannot be ill-treated is queer; to fight someone without destroying him makes him a trickster; and a looter by virtue of being a soldier. Nevertheless, it is important to note also that since the poem is panegyric,

it is a celebration of greatness not necessarily of virtues.

The accomplished formidable task in,

Aṣebẹlẹ-sòkè-dilẹ

Atídí-aláṣejù-bepo-gbóná

(He who-uses-tactics-to-subdue a mountain

He who-puts-the obstinate-in-hot oil)

is meant for the brave. It presents a war-like picture. The phrase 'Lóogun lÉkòó' is repeated in the poem to heighten the intensity of the intended message of the poet. The Nigerian Civil War that the poet is referring to was not an easy task to accomplish. It took the whole Federal government over three years to subdue the Biafrans. In the excerpt, 'sòkè dilẹ' in 'Aṣebẹlẹ-sòkè-dilẹ' shows the magnitude of the war. 'Sòkè-dilẹ' literally means to level a hill. Indeed, the Nigerian Civil War of 1967-70 turned out to be an uphill task.

After the opening of the poem, with an image of war which 'Lóogun lÉkòó depicts, the poet piles up other nominalisations which are significations of toughness. These nominalisations and nominal phrases are features of

oríki which reveal more of the personality of Gowon.
These are evident in:

Aṣebélẹ̀-sòkè-dilẹ̀
Atídí-aláṣejù-bepo-'gbóná
Abánijà-ma-faniya-bí-aṣọ
Odógun-gbéyàwó
Akéré-máṣèéyànje
Ayọmẹrẹn-wonú-ití
AfÈdùmàrè-ṣàtilẹhin-hùwà-àgbà

He who-uses-tactics-to subdue-mountain
He who-puts-the-obstinate-in-hot-oil
He who-fights one-and-will-not-destroy-him
He who-married-when-the war raged-on
The small one-who-cannot-be cheated
One who-stealthily-finds-his-way-into-safety
One who-makes-God-his shield-to-act-like-an-elder

The first two lines show the military might of Gowon.
Though Gowon did not go to the war-front, he was the
Commander-in-Chief of the Nigerian Armed Forces and the
Head of the Military Government. The third line describes
the humane way the war was prosecuted. The soldiers were

instructed to fight the war with minimum destruction of human life particularly the civilians. This is borne out of the fact that both sides are Nigerians.

The choice of these nominalised words is a testimony to the poet's artistic sensibility, as well as cultural awareness. The indigenous Yorùbá is familiar with the use of ití as a place of safety for animals. The adaptation of its use for the Head of State is quite appropriate here.

One of Gowon's major achievements as a Head of State is the creation of twelve States for Nigeria from the long-existing three Regions - North, East and West on May 27, 1967 as shown in the lines below:

Ó lómọ mẹta ò tó mú saiyé,

Ó sọmọ mẹta dèjilá

He said that three children were not enough
to make one comfortable in life

He increased the number to twelve.

The poet ends the poem with an adaptation of the Nigerian war-period slogan, "To Keep Nigeria One, is a Task that must be done".

He says:

Èni ò lórin méjì àfi

Kàn-ń-pá ni

Kàn-ń-pá ni

Kàn-ń-pá ni

Kàn-ń-pá ni

Ilẹ̀ yí ò gbọ̀dọ̀ tú o

Kàn-ń-pá ni

He-who-has-no-other-song-than

It is a task

It is a task

It is a task

It is a task

This country must be made one

It is a task.

This slogan which was very popular during the war, created an awareness and the zeal to subdue the rebellion and served as a unifying force for the soldiers to press on in order to accomplish the task of winning the war. Similarly, it generated needed awareness in the civilians and facilitated their support for the government's execution

of the war.

Again, whatever might have informed Olabimtan's one-sidedness and sense of judgement has also betrayed his political leaning. This may not be far from Gowon's involvement in Awolowo's release from prison and his patriotism which makes him support Gowon's cause to keep Nigeria one.

This patriotism is evident in another poem, 'Oríki Oyeniyi' (Praise-poetry of Oyeniyi). He says:

Adá-ńlá ti mbégi nígbó táriwo ń gbagbó
 Okò ribiti tí mbọ sómi ti gbogbo ẹja ń pariwo

- - -

Asọ-gbogbo aiye-dafénifére

Işé kí ni ọlẹ lè şe?

Ọjà wo lẹlẹ lè tà?

Atojà àtòwò gbogbo rẹ déédé

Gbogbo işé ní í walágbára şe

Adekaiya-ó-já-ọkọ Idòwú

Agbónáránkíránkí, baba Oluşẹgun

(Olabimtan 1974:60)

The mighty cutlas that cuts trees in the
forest and is accompanied by a loud noise

The big stone that drops into the river and all
fishes shake with fear.

- - -

He who unknowingly confides in a liar

He who regards everybody as dependable

What type of work can the indolent do?

What trade can a lazy fellow do?

Jack of all trade master of none

All types of job suit a hardworking man

He whose presence makes one tremble, the
husband of Idowu

One that is very tough and uncompromising,
the father of Oluşegun.

The whole poem is an account of Chief Ọbafẹmi Awolówò whose middle name is Oyenyi but he was rarely addressed as such. His full name is Jeremiah Oyenyi Ọbafẹmi Awolówò. The choice of the obscure middle name, Oyenyi, by the poet is deliberate. Perhaps, the poet in his characteristic way does not want to be too direct in order that he may comment freely on controversial issues; or that the poet intends to

show the degree of his intimacy with Chief Awolòwò. In Yorùbá culture, it is only those who are very close to an individual or who were at the naming of such individual, that would be able to call or address one with the orúko àbísò (christening name), not an outsider. The poet goes further to mention Chief Awolòwò's children by names: Oluşẹgun and Tólá.

This poem touches distinct landmarks in the life of Awolòwò, spanning through his tribulation period, 1962-1966, to his rise to stardom (1966-74). We are introduced to his chain of misfortunes at the beginning of the poem. First, was the death of his eldest son, Oluşẹgun. The poet says,

Èni a tori rẹ́ òkè tó m̀bẹ́ ni
 Ó ní 'Béyi ò ẹ́, òmí lè ẹ́
 Bómi bá d̀nù bagbè ò fọ́, ẹ́ dúpẹ́

He who people weep for but chooses to
 pacify them

He says, "if this did not happen, other
 calamities might surface

If it is the water that is wasted and
the gourd is unbroken, let's be
thankful.

When Awólówò was in detention standing trial for the
treasonable offence in 1962, his first son, Oluşẹgun
died in a ghastly motor accident in an unusual circumstance
while travelling from Ibadan to Lagos. This sad loss
coming at this critical period was enough to shatter many
people but Awólówò was unruffled. Sympathisers wept un-
controllably and it was alleged that it was Awolowò
himself who ironically consoled the people:

Bomí bá dànù bágbè ò fọ, ẹ dúpẹ

If it is water that is wasted and the
gourd is not broken, let's be
thankful.

This is the Yorubá cultural way of consolling someone that
loses a child: omi (water) that is wasted is the child
that is dead while agbè (gourd) that is unbroken is the
mother.

Shortly after this loss, Awolowò was sentenced to ten

years imprisonment for the treasonable offence. It is this incarceration that is referred to in:

Nwọn ní ẹ jẹ a ti kiní yìí mápoti

They said; let's cage this thing in the box.

This literally means let us imprison him. It is the prison that is metaphorically referred to as àpótí (box) and kiní yìí (this thing) is Awolọwọ. It is alleged that all the travail of Awolọwọ was politically motivated so as to get rid of him (Awolọwọ). To corroborate this allegation, the trial judge, Justice Şowẹmímọ, remarked before sentencing him that his "hands were tied".

Before the judgement was passed, there was a dialogue between the judge and Awolọwọ. This is expressed in the poem:

Ó ní "Ẹ fẹ tiná mọlé, ẹ ò ro tòkùnkùn"

Nwọn ní "Bíná bá kú ñkọ enia a kú ni"

Ó ní "Bíná ò sì kú ñkọ, kini'na ò le e ẹ"?

(p.60)

He said, "You want to lock up the light,
you don't take into consideration the
darkness"?

He said, "And what if the light is kept on, what can the light not do"?

The "light" in these lines represents Awolowo himself and the "darkness" is his imprisonment. This dialogue above emanated from Awolowo's last statement before he was sentenced on 11th September, 1963:

It is therefore, with a brave heart, with confident hope, and with faith in my unalterable destiny, that I go from this twilight into the darkness, unshaken in my trust in the providence of God that a glorious dawn will come on the morrow.

(Awolowo, 1981:5)

This prediction came to pass as the poet points out:

Eni a yọ lógbun¹ tán tó tún áre sánmọ.

He that is lifted from the bottomless pit and heads for the sky.

It is Awolowo's release from prison (lowly state) and his immediate appointment as the Federal Commissioner for

¹ Ogbun (bottomless pit) in this text refers to the ten year jail term that Awolowo was serving.

Finance and also as the Vice-Chairman of the Federal Executive Council (not just a Commissioner but the most important commissioner) that is figuratively referred to in the above.

The poet goes to reveal more of Awolowo's tribulations. He alluded to the Coker Inquiry of 1962, following the political crisis in the Western Region in 1962 a state of emergency was declared in the West. At the instance of the newly appointed Administrator, Dr Moses Majekodunmi, the Federal Government instituted an inquiry into the activities of six statutory corporations of Western Nigeria, by Justice G.B. Coker. In the report of the Coker Commission released in December, 1962 and Chief Awolowo was indicted. It is this indictment that the poet refers to in:

Eni a ló jí kòbò tí a gbégbèrún tí

The person that was accused of stealing
one kobo and is now entrusted with
thousands of naira.

'kobo' literally means very little amount of money (because it involves just six statutory corporations of only the Western Region) as compared with the whole

Federal Ministry of Finance that controls egbegbèrún (thousands of naira) with which Awolowo was entrusted as the country's Commissioner for Finance. By implication, the poet is saying that it will be unthinkable to make one that was alleged to be a thief a Commissioner of Finance. This shows that Awolowo has been vindicated. This is further strengthened when the poet says

Ó tójú kóbò, ó di náín

Ó fọgbọ́n sọgọ́jì dígbá

Ajagunṣégun-májẹ gbèsè

He saved one kobo to make nine pence
(nine kobo)

He used his brain to make a profit on
forty (naira) to become two hundred

He who executed and won a war without
incurring any debt)

This testifies to the capability of Awolowo as the Finance Commissioner during the Civil War that lasted three years. It was revealed at the end of the war that Nigeria did not borrow a kobo to execute the war.

Finally, the poet uses this poem to extoll the virtues

of Awolqwo as a political giant. For instance, he alludes to Awolqwo's relationship with Akintola covertly when he says:

Afaimqfinú-hèké

Asqgbogbo-aiye dafénifére

Afaimq-finú-hànkà

Asq-gbogbo-aiye-dolódodo

The one-who-unknowingly-confides-in-a-liar
The-one-who-thinks-all-people-are-progressives

The-one-who-opens-his-mind unknowingly
to-the-wicked

The one-who-believes all people are sincere

Èké (liar) and ikà (the wicked) in the text above would seem to refer to Akintola already mentioned early in this chapter. Ademoyega (1981) sheds light on the root cause of the feud between Awolqwo and Akintola:

Unlike Awólqwo who really favoured a radical solution to the problems of Nigeria . . . Chief Akintólá favoured the conservative approach and was more concerned with sharing the spoils of

office with the NPC Government at the centre. (12)

This shows it is on principle that the two leaders differ. But Qlabimtan, the poet, appears to take side with Awolowu, the leader of the party. Akintola was more concerned with the immediate position of the Yoruba in the scheme of things rather than the long-term principles and rights that seem dim in the unpredictable future which Awolowu stood for. We feel the poet should concede the different postures to the two leaders.

The militarization of the country's political history during this decade, 1970-79 is sustained in the type of language employed. All the nominalized words testify to this. For example,

Adá-ńlá-tí-ńbẹgí-ńígbó-tariwo-gbagbó
 Òko-ribiti-tí-ńbọ-sómi-ti-gbogbo-ẹja-
 ńpariwo
 Adekaiya-ó-já, ọkọ Idowú
 Agbóná rankírankí, baba Olúşẹgun
 Arógunmátidí, ọkọ Idòwú

The-mighty-cutlass-that-cuts-trees in the
forest and is accompanied-by-loud-noise

The-big-stone-that-drops-into-the-river-and-
all-fishes-shake-with-fear

He, whose-presence-makes-one-tremble, the
husband of Idowu

One-that-is-very-tough-and-uncompromising,
the father of Olúṣégun

One-who-is-not-afraid of war, the husband of
Idowu

All these point to the bravery and unusual ruggedness of Awólówò which is in line with the spirit of the military decade. It also shows the poet's mastery of the Yorùbá language. For instance, Adá ñlá (mighty cutlass) and òkò ribiti (enormous stone) refer to the invincibility of Awólówò's political will and influence. During his life time, whenever he made a political statement or any statement for that matter, the whole country would react for days. The phrases, "... táriwo ñgbagbó" and "... ti gbogbo ẹja ñpariwo" are figurative expressions showing how the people, including the government had dreaded Awólówò's utterances or comments on political issues in the country.

For example, his reaction to the 1973 census in a detailed rejoinder led to the cancellation of the exercise. The nominalizations employed by the poet are associated with oriki, a property of the Yorùbá culture.

The dialogue incorporated into the poem is a dramatic touch that keeps the poem alive. The Yorùbá philosophical hermeneutics in which the dialogue is couched compels a spontaneity characteristic of Yorùbá "oríki". For example;

Bíná ò sì kú ñkọ, kíní'ná ò le è ẹ?

"What if light is kept on, what can the
light not do"

reveals the capability of light as something that has limitless power when it survives all odds. Whereas the other side that favours the destruction of "light" also holds force when it is argued;

Nwọn níná kì ibẹ lápátí ká fi ríran

Bíná sì mbẹ ti ò róòrùn

Bó pẹ títí iná a funrarẹ jó rọrun

They said, the light that is covered is not
useful

And if there is light that is covered
from the sun

In due course, the light on its own will get
quenched.

But if light could be destroyed anyone that is an elect
of God should therefore not be taken for granted by his
enemies;

Èni Olú dá ò ẹ́ ẹ́ fiwé'ra ẹni

One who God supports cannot be compared
with oneself.

This is Yorùbá philosophy of life and their strong conviction in the invincibility of whoever God is with.

There is no denying the fact that Ọlabimtan is a politician himself. He uses his poetry to praise a great politician. This is in line with the role of literature and the Marxist view of class consciousness; a politician (Ọlabimtan) praising another politician, (Awolọwọ).

Ọlabimtan also comments on the politics of the decade 1980-89 which is the last decade of our study period. This decade witnessed two military coups which we have mentioned earlier. Nigerians are apprehensive

of the alternating military and civilian governments since 1960 when Nigeria had her independence. The military which claims to be a corrective government whenever it seizes power, is not better either. The poets were therefore worried over the political wind of uncertainty blowing over Nigeria.

In 'Èwà Ọ̀lẹ̀' (The Glory of Tomorrow), Ọ̀labimtan laments

Àsìṣẹ̀ ọ̀ kan ọ̀gbọ̀n, ẹ̀ ma jáyà àṣìṣẹ̀
 Bọ̀mọ̀dé ṣubú a wo'wájú
 Bágbà ṣubú a si wẹ̀yìn,
 Agbà tó ṣubú tí ọ̀ wẹ̀yìn,
 A wẹ̀wù àṣubúlẹ̀bú, a si jin sí kòtò àilẹ̀bọ̀
 Ọ̀mọ̀dé tò kọ̀ tí ọ̀ wo'wájú a si mù nínú ọ̀gbun
 àṣìṣẹ̀

(Ọ̀lábímtán 1988:156)

Wisdom does not prevent mistakes, don't be
 afraid of making mistakes
 When a child falls, he looks forwards
 When an adult falls, he looks backwards
 The adult that falls and fails to look backwards
 Falls repeatedly and falls into a bottomless pit

A child that refuses to look forwards will be lost
in endless mistakes.

In this poem, Olabimtan examines the Nigeria politics of yesteryears and affirms that the Nigerian politicians do not always learn from their past mistakes. This, to him, has been the bane of the successive governments. Though the colonial masters had their own faults, he feels life was more bearable during their governance. To the poet, he feels that the civilian government is preferable to the military.

In the text, the poet says:

Wèrè àná lọgbón òní

- - -

Aiwẹyin, àirẹyin ló sòsèlú àná dọjẹlú

Aika wèrè àná sí ló sọlọgbón-ọn wa dòmùgọ

The folly of yesterday is the wisdom of today

- - -

The past politicians failed because they don't look
backwards and learn from the past
We become fools because we forgot the folly
of yesterday.

The poet is referring to the behaviour of the past Nigerian Governments. The military came into governance in 1966, because of the inadequacies of the politicians. After this military intervention which lasted thirteen years, the Second Republic politicians showed no sign of change from what ruined the First Republic. What is surprising is that there is no difference in governance between the politicians and the military which claims to be a corrective government. It is corruption and nepotism everywhere, hence the poet says :

Ìkamòdù ní balé jé ẹ másín wọlé

- - -

Ẹ lóòórùn ó kúò lágbègbè

Taní ò mò pàlápatà toun tọ̀dẹ̀ ọ̀kan-un !

Kín ní iyàtò arẹ̀níjẹ̀ àtapanijẹ̀?

(Ọlábímtán 1988:156).

When the stink-ant became a nuisance you
brought in the crocidura

- - -

You feel the bad odour will vanish

Who does not know that both the butcher and
the hunter are the same !

What is the difference between a cheat and a
killer?

Nigeria's past civilian and military governments are metaphorically referred to as ikamòdù (stink-ant), and asín (type of rats with very unpleasant odour) (crocidura); álápatà (butcher) and ode (hunter); arénije (cheat) and apanije (murderer) respectively. Both the crocidura and the stink-ant have very unpleasant odour but that of the crocidura is more offensive. Again the tendency to terminate life is more inherent in ode (hunter) (because he works with the gun) than in alápatà (butcher) (because he uses the knife). Lastly, apanije (murderer) is more destructive and more daring than arénije (cheat). Each of the combinations is in the same semantic range, represented thus :

ikamòdù and asín - both have unpleasant odour
alápatà and ode - both deal with animals
arénije and apanije - both have the tendency
to destroy their victims.

From the analysis, one is able to locate the two governments, the civilian and military in the poet's metaphor.

The corrupt tendency of the military is metaphorically depicted in :

Asín kabéré¹ baṣọ ikamòdù
È lásín ó padà sínú oko.

This literally means that the asín (military) tastes politics (aṣọ ikamòdù) and you now want him back into the bush (barracks).

From our observation, one is not left in doubt that out of the two evils presented in the example above, the poet prefers the lesser one when he concludes :

Èrù ibon bà mí jèrù àtimólé
Ewúré èyinkùlé kúkú sàń jàtíkè apanirun
I dread gun more than I dread detention
Goat at the backyard is safer than lethal
powder.

In the two-line example above, ibon (gun) denotes the military while àtimólé (detention) symbolizes the civilian government. But the military also detain

1. The abéré (niddle) refers to by the poet is the long narrow niddle-like mouth of asín (crocidura).

people. Ìbon and àtìmólé are two of the weapons of oppression used by the different governments to coerce their opponents.

During the political rancour in the Old Western Region of Nigeria in the Sixties, politicians planted live or dead goats, or corpses at their opponents' doorsteps so as to implicate them and blackmail them as thieves or murderers. People were thrown into jail for no just cause. Law suits that would normally take months to conclude for reasons of investigation were disposed of **within** hours on frivolous excuses by politicians. Similarly, the use of lethal weapons including powder and bombs to deal with critics of the military government by the military was a common knowledge. For instance, it is believed generally that it was the military that killed Dele Giwa, an investigative journalist on October 19, 1987 through a parcel bomb in an unusual circumstance. It is in the light of this analysis that the appropriateness of the use of ewúré èyinkùlé and àtíkè apanirun become clearer.

No doubt Ọlábímtán's political commentary in his latter poems shows evidence of a matured critic and artistic sensibility. Unlike his previous writings, he is more objective. This is probably so in view of his account of the 1980-89 politics which shows some unusual sophistication in the practice of politics in Nigeria.

Another notable poet whose works contribute to the theme of politics is Fálétí. His poem, 'Adélabú Kú' (Adélabú is dead) is more or less political cast in a traditional elegiac form. He says :

ADÉLABÚ ADÉGÒKÈ

Gbéra n'lè o dide !

Adélabú, atá-kéré yọ ni lẹnu

Àjànàkú sùn bí òkè

Erín wó, ọmọ ẹranko nkígbe

Adégòkè, Àtándá, ó şẹlẹ o ò sí laiye mọ.

(Fálétí 1969:124).

ADÉLABÚ ADÉGÒKÈ

Get up, stand up

Adélabú, small pepper that troubles one

The elephant lies down like a mountain

The elephant has fallen and the little

animals are crying

Adégòkè, Àtándá, it has happened, you are
no more.

Adélabú was a political stalwart in the Old Western Region of Nigeria. He had a turbulent political career. His power and influence were so enormous that his political followers did not believe he could die like that. The same idea is expressed by the poet. The title of the poem, "Adélabú Kú!" with the exclamation suggests the poet's apparent surprise. The poet is speaking the minds of the people. No one who knew Adélabú would ever believe he had really died. Further evidence of the poet's disbelief is seen in these lines :

Ọmọ Adélabú o ẹ se bẹẹ o rọrun

Ikú ẹe bí iré, ikú mú ọ lọ

Son of Adélabú, to have died just like that

Like a child's play, Death took you away.

If truly Adélabú is dead, according to the poet, then that Death must be very powerful. To show this, the poet lists other powerful politicians that Death had taken away :

Kò sènití ikú kò lè pa. Ikú tó pòjike
nílà Oòrun

Ikú tó pólábòdé Òyó

Ló tún pAdélabú aníyì n'Ìbàdàn.

There is no one Death cannot kill. The same
Death that killed Ojike in the
East

And killed Olábòdé of Òyó

The same it is that killed Adélabú, the
honourable man of Ìbàdàn.

The phrase, 'ikú tó pa' (The same death that killed) is suggestive of the questionable and mysterious manner of death of these great politicians like Olábòdé Thomas, Mbonu Ojike and Adégòkè Adélabú among others, who died in strange circumstances.

Despite the political nature of this poem, Fálétí re-enacts the performance of Yorùbá òkú-pípè (funeral dirge) in the first eight lines of the poem where the poet showers praises on Adélabú. Furthermore, images of death run through the poem. For instance, 'Àjànàkú Sùn bí òkè' : the elephant lies down like a mountain; and 'erín wó' : the elephant has

fallen; are repeated five times. The use of Àjànàkú is metaphorical, denoting "importance" or "greatness" of Adélabú. He was a member of the National Council of Nigeria and the Cameroons (NCNC) and leader of Opposition in the former Western House of Assembly. He was nicknamed "Lion of the West" because of his turbulent political activities in the West. It informed the use of the metaphor, Àjànàkú. It captures Adélabú's true image. He was a political "elephant" difficult to subdue and he was a "mountain" very hard to surmount by his political opponents.

The expression used by Fálétí to describe the exit of Adélabú presents an irreparable loss occasioned by his death. He says :

Èmọ́ kú, ojú òpó dí

Èèsún là, ó là dànù

Òpálámhá ọtí èèbó fọ, onígbànsọ kò ríí sọ !

The ẹmọ́ - rat dies, its track disappears

The èèsún ripened and dispersed its seeds but
they are of no use to anyone.

It is evident in this poem that Fálétí is familiar with rural life and farming. For instance, "ẹmọ́"

(a type of rat), "ojú-òpó" (special passage made by rats through the bush) and "èèsún" (type of grass) are common to the traditional Yorùbá.

Ọ̀pádọ̀tun (1987), another poet, also examines issues dealing with politics in his poem, 'Ọ̀mọ̀ Ìyá Kíí Yà' (Children of the same mother stay together) :

Bó bá worogún

Orogún le gbówọ́ fúnra wọn

Bọ̀bàkan si fẹ́

Ọ̀bàkan le sọ májèlé dákàrà

Bó bá dajúró aya le yalọ

Bọ̀rọ̀ ọ̀ wọ̀ mọ̀

Ọ̀mọ̀ baba le dàwátì

Şùgbọ̀n ayé ọ̀ níle tí tí

Kádiè jẹfun ara wọn

Ìgbà ọ̀ ní dàlàpà tí tí

Kọ̀mọ̀ iyá ó yọ̀mọ̀ya è

Àfi bó bá sọ̀mọ̀ iyá awùsá

Ọ̀mọ̀ awùsá ọ̀ finú han'ra wọn

Àfàwọ̀n obì ni wọn n fífẹ́ ló

Kí ló n ş̀Ọ̀gùn, Ondo pẹ̀lú Ọ̀yọ̀?

Şebí wọn loòduà ló ş̀ẹ̀ gbogbo wa

Ọ̀jọ̀ wo la pínnya ná

Tá ò tún le fifé lò?

- - -

̀Njé gbogbo àgbà tó jèsébi pátá

Gbogbo arúgbó t́aa jọ jẹran awo

Báyíí lójú wa wá rí

Lójọ́ t́aa ń jobi lójà ̀Ede?

(Ọ̀pádòtun 1987:14).

If it pleases the co-wives

The co-wives could compete in their
evil acts

If half-brothers so desire

The half-brothers could use poison as àkàrà
balls

If things do not work out fine, a wife
may run away

If the going is no more good

One's half-brother may do away with one

But no matter the circumstance

Hen will not eat another's intestine

No matter the time lapse

Children of the same mother will not desert
one another

Unless they are the children of the walnut

It is the walnut seeds that do not open
their hearts (lobes) to one another

It is only the kolanuts that deal with
one another with love

What is wrong with Ògùn, Ondo and Òyó States?
But they say Oduduwa is the ancestor of all of
us

When were we just divided into States?

That we cannot relate to one another in love?

- - -

Now all elders that partake in the ritual
eating of kolanut

All old people that share the ritual meat
together with us

Was this how things were

On the day we were taking oath with kolanut
at Èdẹ market?

This is an account of the aftermath of breaking the former Western State of Nigeria into Òyó, Ogun and Ondo States. The rivalry that ensued among them generated into open hostility. Òpádòtun therefore suggests a truce for purposes of the warring kinsmen and women.

In this poem, Òpádòtun gives us an account of the posteriority of the state creation of 1976. Nigeria formerly had three Regions - the Northern, Eastern and Western Regions. The Balewa - led Federal Government created the Mid-Western Region from the Western Region in 1963. On May 30, 1967, Gowon created

twelve States from the existing four Regions. Then came 1976 when on February 3, General Murtala Mohammed increased the number of States to nineteen. It was then that the former Western State was divided into Ọyó, Ògùn and Ondo States. The jubilation that greeted the news of the State creation was short-lived. Rivalry and hatred among the three States in particular, started almost immediately after their creation. The conflicts emanated from asset sharing. Before this time, they have been staying together as one people with common descendancy. This is why the poet asks in disbelief.:

Şebí wọn lOduduwa ló sẹ gbogbo wa?

Ọmọ iyá kíí yà.

But they say Oduduwa is our common ancestor?
Children of the same mother don't desert
one another.

The poet therefore wonders why Ọyó, Ògùn and Ondo States should become enemies over the State creation since they are all children of the same mother. He then cites the example of the walnut whose "children" do not see eye to eye despite the fact that they are of the same "mother." This is the Yorùbá interpretation

of walnut seeds who though are in a pod have distinct shells. The case of the walnut is an example of "children" of the same "mother" that are assumed not to be friendly in the light of this natural arrangement of its seeds with barriers and shells. From the poet's analysis, besides the walnut which is an exception to the rule, Òyó, Ògùn and Ondo which are considered to be children of the same origin, Oduduwa should not have exhibited the kind of hatred and violence that came in the wake of their creation into States.

In this poem, the poet is advocating for the unity of the Yorùbá. He therefore reminds them of the traditional Yorùbá way of sustaining their promise through the ritual kolanut taking as a form of covenant making. This is a Yorùbá traditional practice :

Njé gbogbo àgbà tó jèsébi pátá

Gbogbo arúgbó tá a jọ jẹran awo

Now all the elders that partake in the ritual
eating of kolanut

All the old people that shared the ritual meat
together.

Convenant making or oath-taking is a significant cultural practice that binds the people together on an agreement or decision made.

The poet therefore calls on the elders and the educated elite in the society to enlighten the people on the need for unity. He says :

Ñjé gbogbo àgbàgbà tó wà ní ipínlè wònyí
 Àtawon tó kadá tó tún kọpọlọ
 È jé ká sowópọ ká fòye hanra wa
 Ká şàlàyé ọrọ fún gbogbo ẹnì tí kò mò
 Lóòótọ la dípínlè repetẹ
 Èyí ọ dínà isòkan wa.

Now all the elders in these States
 Together with the learned that are wise
 Let's unite and enlighten ourselves
 Let us explain things to all that don't
 understand

It is true that we have become many States
 This should not disturb our unity.

The poet therefore calls on the Yorùbá Ọbas to intervene and foster unity among the Yorùbá. The Yorùbá paramount rulers mentioned include, Ọoni Àdímúlà, Alaafin Ìlú Ọyọ, Awùjalẹ, Àkàrigbò, Èwí Ilé Adó, Aláké Ilẹ̀ Ègbá, Olúbàdàn, Ọşemòwé, Olúkàrẹ̀

and Ọlówò. These are high-ranking Ọbas from Ọyó, Ondo and Ọ̀gùn States. The poet's appeal to them is in recognition of the Ọba's role in the society. They are second in importance to the òrìṣàs (the divinities). They are nearer their subjects than the government, hence, the poet feels the need for the monarchs to explain the socio-economic importance of the creation of States to their subjects.

Ọ̀pádòtun's language, particularly his use of wordplay, in this poem makes his message clearer. He says :

Ọmọ ìyá kíí yà.

There is a play on words between the noun, "ìyá" (mother) and the verb, "yà" (to separate) as if the noun "ìyá" is derived from the verb "yà". It is a false derivation. The same effect is got from :

Bó bá dojúrú aya le ya lẹ

"aya" and "ya lẹ" which suggest nominal derivation as a result of their phonological as well as their vocalic similarities. In these examples, the poet tends to create humour. It also makes his work more poetic.

Finally, the use of elements associated with the farm, and some other words used by the poet depict a

true traditional setting with which the poet is familiar. For instance, "àlàpà" (a standing mud-wall) is common sight in the rural areas where there are mud houses built with thatched roofs. Similarly, orogún (co-wives), "Obà-kan" (children of the same father but different mothers), májèlé (poison) are foregrounded by the polygamous practice common in Yorùbá traditional society. All this supports the argument in sociology of literature that the artist's cultural background is closely linked with his writings. The artist does not write in a vacuum. His society, his personality and his art are all interwoven.

Adépòjù, another notable poet is also involved in poetic discourse on politics in his works. Adépòjù is a fearless commentator on political issues and he has proved to be alive to the happenings in his contemporary society. He came out boldly in his poems waxed on discs between 1979 and 1987 to comment on political issues affecting the generality of the people.

The global economic recession was already biting hard when Buhari came into power and so he had to

face the problems of resuscitating the badly battered economy. Unlike Gowon who was head of Government during the oil-boom, Buhari had to be very prudent in his spendings. Having seen the achievement of the Gowon regime, who, according to Adépoju, had some civilian elders in his government, Adépoju (1985) in his poem, 'Tèmi Yé Mi', says,

Ṣebí a jagun abélé njó sí
 A à yá kòbò jagun Ojúku
 Baba tó ṣiṣé ọ̀un kò tíi kú
 È wí fún ṣọ̀jà kó fọ̀rọ̀ làgbà.

Didn't we fight a civil war the other time
 We did not borrow a single kobo to prosecute
 Ojukwu war

The man who performed that feat is still
 alive

Advise the soldiers to invite the elders.

The war the poet is referring to is the Nigerian civil war. The indigenous Yorùbá refer to it as 'Ogun Ojúku' (Ojukwu War) named after Colonel Odumegwu Ojukwu, Military Governor of Eastern Nigeria when the war broke out. The poet ^{refers} to Awólówò as 'bàbá' (Father) who was the Commissioner for Finance in Gowon's government during the Nigerian Civil War of 1967 - 1970. This seems to

lend credence to Olábímtán's submission that Awólówò is prudent. In the same disc, Adépojù, in what he thinks as inadequacies of the Buhari Government, declares :

È é ti jẹ o?

Gbà tí ò sógun mọ, tí ò sọtẹ mọ

Owó yíyá ẹ jẹ?

A ti ẹ tún jẹ gbèsè tó báun?

Şebí sílè kan ààbò là n ra mílíki láyé

Gowon?

What is happening?

When there is no more war,

Why are we borrowing money?

Why do we have so heavy debt to repay?

Is it not only fifteen kobo that we used to
buy a tin of milk during the
Gowon regime?

As we have pointed out, the economic recession was not peculiar to Nigeria, it was global. The oil-boom of the sixties cushioned the effect of the war. The purported fifteen kobo that the poet claims was the price of a tin of milk then has skyrocketed to forty naira now!

In another disc, 'Níbo Là N' Lọ?' (Where are we heading to?), Adéjọ̀jù raises a number of issues agitating the minds of millions of Nigerians. First, is the removal of oil subsidy. He says :

È gbọ́, kí ló dé o

Òótọ́ ni àbí irọ́ ni tepo mọtò tó fẹ́ lẹwó

Fífowókúnwó epo àbí nla?

Epo tẹ ẹ fowó kún níjọsí

Tí gbogbo ñ̀nkan torí rẹ́ tó lẹwó

Tó jẹ́ pé ohun tó dá sílẹ́

N' jà lẹwólẹwó

Bówó bá tún gorí epo

Wàlái ohun tó léwu ni

A, ọ̀gá wa Gbadamọ́sí Babangida

È jáwọ́ kúrò níbẹ́

- - -

È mọ́ dirù tó wúwo fún m̀kúnnù.

(LALPS 136, 1987).

Listen, what is happening?

Can it really be true that oil subsidy would
be removed?

You want to increase the cost of fuel or what?
The increase that was effected the other time,
And the price of every commodity went up

So more so that its effect
 Is still with us
 If there is another increase in the cost of
 fuel

Surely, it is dangerous
 Ah, Gbadamoṣi Babangida our leader,
 Forget about it

- - -

Don't put too much burden on the masses.

Before the release of this album in 1988, there had been an increase in the pump price of fuel from twenty-two kobo (22 kobo) per litre to forty-two kobo (42 kobo) in 1987. But when the album was released, the government did not increase the fuel price immediately thereafter but today the price of fuel has gone up to eleven naira per litre.

Another issue that Adépòjù touches is the issue of the Second Tier Exchange Market (SFEM) introduced by the government to improve the economy. Its introduction has brought untold hardship on the masses and reacting to this, Adépòjù in another poem, 'Níbo Là N' Lọ?', declares

È jòṣo kí ní SFEM àbàadi

Té ẹ gbé dé

A fẹ kẹ ẹ tùmò rẹ kedere
 Kó yé wa
 Ònà tó fi ẹ m̀kúnnù lóore
 A fẹ gbálàyé ẹ.

(Níbo Là N Lọ?, 1987).

Please, that useless SFEM
 That you have introduced
 We want you to explain it very well
 In what ways does it benefit the masses?
 We want an explanation.

As we said earlier in this work, the introduction of SFEM and other programmes like SAP have made the rich richer. And as the poet points out, it has not benefited the poor masses.

The poet's choice of "àbàadi" (outrageous) in this poem gives an ugly picture of SFEM and this is the intention of the poet. It is a carefully chosen diction that suggests the poet's utter disgust at the so called SFEM. It also depicts the posture of the poet, he is against the introduction of SFEM.

Adépojú is even more critical of the Babangida administration in 'Níbo Là N Lọ?' when he says :

A ti gbòminira nílẹ̀ yíí
 Ó ti tódún mètàdínlògbòn
 Níbo là n lọ?
 Omi ò kárfí
 Bíná ti n tàn ló n kú
 Owó wọn kò síbàlẹ̀ àyà mò
 Ojoojúmọ̀ là n pààrọ̀ ijọba
 Wí pé bóyá a jéé sà
 Ìjọba di méjọ ọtọ̀tọ̀
 Lẹnu ọdún mètàdínlògbòn

- - -
 Ìtìjù la à mò
 Ó tọ́ ká **ti** kúrò lómọ̀ rákò
 Owó tó n wọlé lórílẹ̀-èdè yíí
 Bá a bá tọ́jú ẹnu àpò
 Ó tó wa sẹ̀kọ̀ ọfẹ̀ tó níláárfí.

(Adéjọ̀jù, Níbo Là N Lọ 1987).

We have got our independence in Nigeria
 It's about 27 years now
 Where are we heading to?
 Pipe-borne water is inadequate
 Electricity is not stable
 Money is scarce, there is no rest of mind
 It is everyday we are changing government
 To see whether it will be better

We have had eight different governments
Just within 27 years

- - -

It is because we have no shame
We ought to have passed the stage of a baby
country

The income that is realised in this country
If we watch our purse
Is enough to prosecute free qualitative
education.

Here, Adépojú touches on some of the ills of the
country like lack of water, electricity and political
instability :

Ó tọ ká ti kúrò lómọ irákò

The poet likens Nigeria's slow pace of development
to that of a child that suffers from mongolism
(mental retardation). By the time Adépojú published
this poem in 1987, Nigeria was twenty-seven years old
as a sovereign nation. But she has got nothing to
show for it politically and economically. He says
further;

Ìjọba di méjọ ọtọọtọ

Lénu ọdún métàdínlọgbọn.

We have had eight different governments
Just within twenty-seven years.

In Nigeria, the constitution stipulates a four-year life span for Government for one term in office. But within the space of twenty-seven years, Nigeria has had eight different governments. This political instability does not encourage any meaningful economic development. Besides, the Government has not been prudent in financial management :

Owó tó n wólé lórílẹ̀ èdè yíí
 Báa bá tójú ẹnu àpò
 Ó tó wa ẹ̀kọ̀ ọ̀fẹ́ tó níláárí.

The English translation is already given above.

Fálọlá and Ihonvbere (1985) give insight into the Government financial recklessness:

Corruption (in Nigeria) was not however, limited to contract inflation. The second Republic was notorious for fraud :

Payment of huge sums of money to ghost workers, importation of fake products in order to obtain foreign exchange; outright stealing of government property, illegal transfer of money to private accounts (127).

This is how Nigeria's purse leaks and millions of naira got lost through several sources.

Adépojú again examines the question of human rights that Babangida promised to safeguard when he came to power in 1985. In his poem, 'Ètò Ọmọniyàn' (Human Rights), he says;

Ẹjẹ́ irẹ̀tí n bẹ́ fún mẹ̀kúnnù?

Ọ̀fin ojú dúdú n bẹ́ n'Íbàdàn àt'Èkó

Níbi a rò pọ́ yẹ kọ́jú ó gbé là

Kọ̀lájú ó gbé péẹ̀lì

Mímú ni wọ̀n n mọ̀mọ̀ èniyàn bíi igbà a

bá mẹranko

Ètò ọ̀mọ̀ èniyàn wá di mẹ̀ta ọ̀nínì

Igí dá kò sólùgbàlà

Nnkan n ẹ̀lẹ́ n'Íbàdàn àt'Èkó

Àwọ̀n ọ̀kọ̀ ijọ̀ba ibílẹ̀ tó jẹ́ pánúmọ̀

Wọ̀n n bẹ́ nígboro Èkó

Ise ti wọ̀n fi n ẹ̀ nígboro ọ̀ dáa

È jẹ́ a wí fúnra wa

Èyàn ni wọ̀n fi ọ̀kọ̀ wọ̀nyí kó lọ sátimólẹ̀

Ẹ ẹ́ ti gbọ̀rú ẹ́ nínú itàn?

Àwọ̀n èniyàn tó dúró jẹ́jẹ́ lójú títi

Ti wọ̀n fẹ́ wọ̀kọ̀ èrò

Bí pánúmọ̀ tá a wí wọ̀nyí bá dé

Wọn a ló yá ẹ máa wọlé

Nṣe la n kéré kiri

"Ilorin lẹ n lẹ àbí Jẹbú, bo jẹ Sokoto?"

"Ẹ máa bọ lẹkọ"

Àrà n ò rí ọ rí

Bí wọn ba ti kéré Oṣogbo àtìbàdàn tán

Ti wọn kó ti Sapele pọ mọ Kaduna

Wọn a lórí ọkọ sọná ígboro

"Kí ló dé?"

"Níbo lẹ n kó wa á rẹ?"

"Ẹṣẹ wo la a ṣẹ?"

Ká tó sẹjú péé

Wọn á kó wọn, iwọò ni kóòtù

Àwọn ẹni tí wọn ti yàn gégé bí adájọ ibòòsí

Wọn a lówó itanràn nkọ?

Ẹni tó ba ri owó itanràn san

Wọn a ni ko máa lẹ

Ẹni tówó tiẹ ò bá pé kíákíá

Ó dará àtimólé

Ṣe ẹ ti gbọrú ẹ tẹlẹ?

(Adépoju, Ètọ Oṣoniyàn 1986).

Is there any hope for the masses?
Uncivilized laws exist at Ibadan and Lagos
The place where we feel people are enlightened

That should be a bit more civilized
 They are driving human beings here and there
 like animals

Human right is ridiculously trampled upon
 It is a pity, there is no saviour
 Wonders are happening at Ìbàdàn and Lagos

- - -

The Local Government buses
 That exist in Lagos
 What they are being used for is horrible
 Let's be frank to ourselves
 They use them for conveying people to detention
 Have you ever heard that in history?
 Passengers that wait patiently by the road
 Waiting for commercial vehicles
 They will ask the people to board the vehicles
 That they are looking for passengers
 "Is it Ilorin or Ijebu or even Sokoto?"
 "Come inside the vehicle"
 Wonders will never end
 After loading passengers going to Oşogbo and
 Ibadan
 And those going to Sapele and Kaduna
 They will make a U-turn to Lagos
 "What is happening?"
 "Where are you taking us to?"
 "What is our offence?"
 Within a short spell
 They are arraigned in the court
 Those that have arranged to act as fake judges
 Will ask the people to bail out themselves

Those that have money to bail themselves out
 They will release
 Those that don't have enough money
 Will be remanded in custody
 Have you ever heard that before?

The above account reveals one of the corrupt practices perpetuated by some Local Government Officials in Ìbàdàn and Lagos during the Babangida regime of 1985 - 1989. The economy of Nigeria had gone so bad that the masses were reduced to almost destitutes.

Before the Babangida regime came to power, the populace was already tired of the highhandedness and violation of human rights that were characteristic of the Buhari government. Therefore, it was a welcome relief when the Babangida regime came in 1985 and promised a favourable human rights atmosphere. Unfortunately Babangida did not keep his promise as incidents of human rights violation were rampant. Adéppòjù therefore reminds the Babangida regime of this promise :

Ètò ọmọniyàn tólórí sọjà ní kẹ fún
 Wọn ti dojú ẹ délẹ
 Ìjọba tó ní nítorí ètò ọmọ èniyàn
 Lòun ẹ wa gbijà ilú.

The human rights the commander of Armed
 Forces is advocating
 They have destroyed it
 The Government that says that it is because
 of human rights
 That it has come to fight for the society.

The poet is evidently on the side of the masses.
 He is totally against the Local Government action.
 But the poet has overlooked one point. Motor parks
 which are meant for revenue generating are built all
 over the country, particularly in big cities like
 Ìbàdàn and Lagos. The commercial vehicles that
 patronize the motor parks pay certain levies to the
 Local Government in control of these motor parks.
 Those vehicles that pick their passengers from the
 roadsides evade such payments. Apart from this
 economic aspect, the obstruction caused by the vehicles
 picking road-side passengers can be dangerous to both
 the drivers and the passengers. The poet's account
 therefore seems biased for he deliberately ignores
 the economic side of the loss of revenue.

Apparently the masses appreciate Adépòjù's blunt
 utterances to check the government's excesses but such

utterances could ignite the masses to rise against the government, and if that happens, it can warrant the government's wrath on the poet. Adépòjù's approach appears to run contrary to Michael Riffaterre's (1974) view :

"Poetry expresses concepts and things by indirection."

But in case of Ọlábímtán, he is more discreet in his method. He comments freely on politics hiding his identity under the umbrella of metaphorical expressions.

Finally, Atiládé and Ọdúnjọ are seen as commentators on national politics. Having participated in the events that led to the Nigeria independence, they saw the need for national unity if Nigeria would survive. Ọlábímtán and Fálétí, on the other hand, deal with the tumultuous politics of the Old Western Region, Fálétí gives us the picture of a man, Adélabú, whose turbulent political activities in the Old Western Region cannot be easily forgotten. Ọlábímtán and Adépòjù on their own parts in their writings, have shown themselves as committed politicians. If the politics of the sixties was violent, then how do we describe the politics of

the seventies and eighties?

It seems nothing has changed even though the actors on the political scene of the fifties and sixties have changed hands, the 'hide and seek' political gymnastics are very much with us. From the submissions of the poets, the politicians seem not to have learnt any lesson from their past mistakes. The poets are trying their best in their political comments. They have shown signs of maturity in their approach to political issues but the politicians remain unchanged. There has not been anything to write home about any of the successive governments that Nigeria has had since independence. This is largely due to the fact that the military has ruled the country for the better part of this period. It is a known fact that soldiers are not trained to rule, hence the perpetual misgovernance in Nigeria. Perhaps if there has been any "improvement" on the politics of Nigeria since 1949 till 1989, it is the increased knowledge of election rigging and the sophisticated way of eliminating political opponents.

CHAPTER FOUR

TOPICALITY AND SIGNIFICANCE II

4.0 Introduction

Some social issues discussed by the poets are within the Yorùbá cultural context. Such issues include love and marriage, health, eulogy, elegy, cultural awareness and social vices and virtues. These socio-cultural issues are our pre-occupation in this chapter.

4.1 Love and Marriage

Yorùbá poets, like their counterparts all over the world, discuss love freely in their works. However, since "Yorùbá 'traditional' culture," according to Olabimtan (1981:3),

does not encourage public mention or discussion of physical aspects of romantic love and passion or the 'higher' feelings of love between a man and a woman,

they are careful the way they handle physical aspect of love. Since love preceeds marriage, and the two are social aspect of life, there is no way they can be avoided. For instance, in his poem, 'Gòkè-Àjàdí Nílé

Àbẹ̀nì - Mọ̀tẹ̀lẹ̀' (Gòkè-Àjàdí in the House of Àbẹ̀nì-Mọ̀tẹ̀lẹ̀), Ọ̀ládàpọ̀ resorts to the use of euphemism in :

Àmàlà yíí n̄sojú ròdòròdò

Ọ̀bẹ̀ yíí n̄sojú ròdóròdó

Mọ̀tẹ̀lẹ̀ mi Àbẹ̀nì, ó yá

Wẹ̀wọ̀ lómi o tara

Kó o jẹ́ á jẹun súnkunsí

Ká mumi sénmi

Tètè sísoọ lórí àmàlà ifé

Jẹ́ á jẹun ládùndórùn.

(Ọ̀ládàpọ̀ 1975:49).

This àmàlà is enticing

This soup is enticing

My Mọ̀tẹ̀lẹ̀ Àbẹ̀nì, get ready

Wash your hands, make haste

Let us eat the food of súnkunsí¹

Let us drink the water of senmi²

Quickly remove the cloth covering love's àmàlà

Let us eat the food of ládùndórùn³

Literally, the poem above shows us the pleasure we get from eating àmàlà with delicious soup in the company of a loved one. But the deep meaning which is the poet's

1, 2 & 3 are used in a special way denoting pleasure.

message, is the pleasure we derive from love-making with a loved one.

At times, in discussing love, the poets enumerate the virtues of a loved one as Olabimtan (1969) does in his poem, 'Èjídé' which is an account of the poet's personal experience. Èjídé is Olabimtan's (poet) wife. So he knows what he is saying when he says in the first six lines :

Adé ti mo ba ñfèhín kiri
 Ti mo sàì rílù ti mo ñjó
 Àní bí ng sàì jẹun daláyo
 Má pè mí lásíwín, orí mi kòyí
 Bí mo jí ti mo ñwọṣọ kiri
 Bí ng ò sì ọṣẹ ti mo ñfò
 Ọe ifẹ mo f'Èjídé kò tó jó?

Adé, if I am just laughing about,
 Dancing without any drumming
 I say if I don't eat and I am full
 Don't call me a lunatic, I am not insane
 If I wake up doing nothing
 And even if I don't work and I am jumping
 about
 Is my love for Èjídé not worth dancing for?

Though these lines sound hyperbolic to be true, the poet is able to express the point that his wife is his

source of joy and emotional stability.

No matter the social class of a person in the Yorùbá society, the cooperation and support of his wife is essential. In a typical Yorùbá family setting, the wife takes care of the home. Olabimtan was already a University graduate when he wrote this poem in 1969. His social class did not blindfold him from recognising the woman's responsibility to the family within the African society in general. Also, his view on a childless marriage is an indication that no matter our social class, tradition would over-ride civilization.

Ìṣòlá is another poet that discusses love in his poems, and in doing so, he focuses on the virtues in his loved ones. In 'Titilola', he says :

Bó o pọ o d́́a tó Títí

Ìwàà rẹ ò tó ti Títí

Bó o sí pọ o níwà tó pọ

Ogbón rẹ ò súnmọ tọrẹè mi.

(Ìṣòlá 1978:26).

If you say you are as beautiful as Títí
Your character is not as good as that of Títí
And if you claim to be of good character
Your intelligence cannot match that of my friend.

When it seems Ìṣòlá was lost in words to describe his lover in another poem, 'Àjòkẹ́', he says :

Ó joun pỌbàtálá ò sùn
Kò sùn lójọ́ tó n d'Àjòkẹ́

I feel Ọbàtálá did not sleep
He did not sleep when Àjòkẹ́ was being moulded.

In this example, the Yorùbá belief that God committed to Ọbàtálá the creation of the physical part of man is brought into focus. So, as the sculptor-divinity did overtime while creating Àjòkẹ́, she became extraordinarily beautiful. And in another poem, 'Ọláníkẹ́ẹ́' the poet is so intimately attached to Ọláníkẹ́ẹ́ that he could not imagine his separation, even in thought, from Ọláníkẹ́ẹ́ when he says :

Àwòrán rẹ́ a máa pé lágbárí
Ọláníkẹ́ẹ́, ni gbogbo igbà
Lojú-inú mi n wòyeè rẹ́

Your image lingers long in my memory
Ọláníkẹ́ẹ́, it is at all times
That my inner mind focuses on you.

The poet's exposure to foreign poetry is seen in the similarity in his expression above and Shakespeare's

Sonnet xxvii :

Save that my soul's imaginary sight
Presents thy shadow to my sightless view.

(Craig (ed.) 1905:1110).

Many other poets that touch on love theme include, Òpádòtun (1976) Oyerinde (1981) and Babalọlá, 1989. The extent of their discussion is determined by the limitation set by Yorùbá culture on such issues. Tradition even over-rides civilization as depicted in the examples given from Òladapọ (1975) and Íṣòlá (1976). This shows the commitment of the Yorùbá poets to their culture.

4.2 Issues on Hygiene

The sanitary situation of the traditional Yorùbá society was very poor during the 1949 - 59 decade. There were very few General Hospitals and the number of dispensary and maternity homes was inadequate. Therefore, many people had to trek long distance for their health care. The low level of education then did not help matters either. The causes of ill-health and the majority of diseases that were prevalent in the society then could be traced to ignorance. There was therefore the need for an enlightenment campaign

to combat this ignorance.

The school was in the fore-front of such campaigns and even though it was very effective it was limited to the school environment alone. The school children were taught to be neat to school everyday. Their body, finger-nails, hair and teeth were checked regularly. Oḍúnjọ uses his experience as a teacher and poet to remind the school children of the importance of cleanliness. In his poem, 'Bí mo bá jí' (When I wake up), he lists the early morning duties to be performed to avoid unnecessary illness.

Bí mo bá jí lówùúrọ
 Ma fomi mímọ bọjú
 Ma mórín senu
 Ma gbálẹ ọọdẹ
 Ma gbá tita pẹlú
 Ma kó pàntí dà sáatàn
 Ma fọṣọ tó rírí
 Ma tún fabọ óúnjẹ
 Ma kájẹkù ẹbà sílé ikólẹsí
 Ma gbómi tútù sí balùwẹ
 Ma bomi síké
 Ma ọara lóge
 Kí igbẹ-ọrin máa gbórèéré wò mí.
 Kí jeyínjeyín máa sá fún mí
 Mo ti pínயà pẹlú ọ̀bìyà

Èmi atónígbá-méjì tí dọ́tá
 Omi to dárogún ò sí níta tẹ̀mi
 Yànmùyánmù tí sọ̀lẹ̀è mi dàkọ̀tì.

(Ọdúnjọ, 1949b:29).

When I wake up in the morning
 I clean my face with clean water
 I use my chewing stick
 I sweep the floor
 And also the surrounding
 I pack the dirt into the dustbin
 I wash dirty clothes
 I wash the plates too
 I pack the left-over food into the dustbin
 I then put cold water in the bathroom
 I bathe
 I dress up
 Let dysentery keep a distance from me
 Let toothache disappear from my sight
 I have said bye bye to guinea worm
 I and cholera are now enemies
 Stagnant water is not in my own vicinity
 Mosquitoes have deserted my abode.

The use of the first person pronoun ('Ma') (I) makes the whole text a personal affair and this helps the message sink into the children's mind. The daily morning duties one has to perform are arranged in a systematic order. It is like climbing a ladder, if one skips one step, one is likely to lose one's balance. This makes the poem easy to memorize. This in effect may facilitate the transmission of the

message. The style of the poet is unique. The poem is divided into two parts. The first part contains what could be done to keep both the environment and the body clean. The expected result of cleanliness is expressed in the second part that concludes the poem.

In another poem, 'Ìmótótó Borí Àrùn' (Cleanliness Overcomes Disease), Oḍúnjọ (1949b:32) discusses the importance of cleanliness to a healthy living and the consequences of dirty habits. For instance, the opening two sentences :

Ìmótótó borí àrùn mólẹ̀
Bọ̀yẹ̀ tí í borí oorú.

capture the message of the poet. It is a simile that brings out the significance of cleanliness to healthy living. To appreciate the power of cleanliness over diseases, it is compared with the power of harmattan over heat. The wind that blows during the harmattan is chilly and it drives away the heat, thus ameliorating the atmospheric condition. So also cleanliness subdues diseases. This figurative expression makes the message clear.

The society is to blame for the death caused by these diseases tormenting man. When one dies of an attack by one disease, out of ignorance stemming from cultural beliefs, the Yorùbá attribute the cause to supernatural powers. They therefore make sacrifices to appease the gods whenever there is an outbreak of epidemic. It is this erroneous belief that the poet wants to correct:

Ajẹ kọ ló n fámódi gbogbo, ẹ kó èké sígbó
 Afínjú ni ka máa ẹ;
 Ìwà idòtí lẹrẹ àrùnkàrùn
 Ọwọ ara wa ló n ẹ ni.

It is not the witch that brings the different
 illness, stop lying
 Be very clean
 Dirty habit causes various diseases
 We are the architect of our own misfortune.

The sanitary situation of the forties and fifties is the subject matter in this poem. Ọdúnjọ believes that the dearth of adequate medical facilities then notwithstanding, it is possible to prevent the outbreak of common diseases so far the individual is able to keep the simple rules of hygiene.

The poem above therefore is a call to the people to take preventive health care delivery more seriously than the curative aspect. In other words, prevention is better than cure as an adage says.

These issues on hygiene are relevant to all time, hence Ọdúnjọ's poems are still read and committed to memory by the primary school pupils.

Another poet who touches on the importance of hygiene in his poem is Babalọlá (1956). The poem is titled 'Àbúrò Mi Gbínńísín' (My little young brother) (Babalọlá 1956:37). The poem can be considered at two levels, surface and deep levels. At the surface level, the poem is a conversation between the poet and his younger brother, Adisa who woke at midnight to ask for his 'breakfast.' He was denied his 'breakfast' because the timing was wrong. Eventually he enjoyed the 'breakfast' at the appropriate time and even promised to have his subsequent lunch and dinner at their right times. At the deep level, the poem can be given a metaphorical interpretation and which is the subject matter of the poem. The poet's intended message is that we should always do the right thing at the right time since there is time for everything in life. The 'breakfast' might

mean early 'marriage' to the poet. It was the custom in the fifties for the indigenous Yorùbá society to encourage their children to rush into untimely marriage because they want to see their children's children. One might say that it is this practice of early marriage that the poet is condemning.

Apart from the poet's main message, he also covertly emphasises the need for personal hygiene, which is inherent in the traditional Yorùbá culture:

Nígbà tí ilẹ̀ mọ̀ ya
 Tí gbogbo enia dide,
 Àdísá bọ̀jú rẹ̀ kíá
 Ó rorín rẹ̀; lakoko
 Ońjẹ ǎrọ̀, ó sì jẹun

(Babalọ́la 1956:37).

As soon as it was day break
 And everybody was awake
 Adisa washed his face quickly
 He cleaned his teeth; at the time
 For breakfast, he then ate.

Babalọ́lá is a teacher who, not only knows the importance of personal hygiene, but also teaches the pupils practically during the usual morning devotion in school.

It is usual in most schools to have daily morning inspection of the pupils' personal hygiene (the hair, the finger nails, the teeth, the body and the uniform). One sees a link between the personal hygiene he is preaching here and the theme of his poem (doing the right thing at the right time). As the young boy prepares very well (washing his face and teeth) to be able to enjoy his breakfast, so also is the need to prepare well for the challenges of life ahead.

It is evident in the works of the two poets, Qdúnjọ and Babalọlá that much of their submissions are a reflection of the numerous Yorùbá cultural beliefs. Though the colonial era brought conspicuous change of values and ideals in the Yorùbá society during this decade, 1949-59, the poets do not allow themselves to be blindfolded into disregarding their own traditional values as far as health matters are concerned. The two poets are not only teachers but also christian leaders (see Appendix) and this has tremendous influence on their work. The pedagogical and didactic nature of their poems that we have just examined is a testimony

to this fact.

4.3 Eulogy

The theme of eulogy is not common in the works of the poets under study. This neglect is a carry-over of the Yorùbá cultural belief:

Bá a kù làá dèrè
Èniyàn ò sunwòn láàyè.

It is when a man dies that he becomes
an admirable person
No man is perfect while alive.

But should we because of this age-long traditional belief close our eyes to the achievements of people that deserve commendation? Whereas it is the same Yorùbá philosophy that says,

Yinni yinni
Kéni ẹ mí sí.

Praise people
To elicit further achievements.

We believe that eulogy can encourage one to attain greater heights. This is what Olabimtan (1974) does for Bámgbóşé in his poem, Oríki Ọmọ Àlàdó (The Praise Poetry of the offspring of Àlàdó). He says :

Adúmáadán

Ajògbòdò lẹwà

Àgbà-Jẹbú tÉlédùà-ṣewà ran níṣé
Ó délé aiyé, ogbón ló úwá kiri

Dáraníbi

Ajògbòdọlẹwà, ọmọ Àlàdó

Ọmọ Agbágilábàrá pèpo

Agúntáṣọ̀lò, ọkọ Adé

Daráníjọ

Afèdè-òhún-bí-ẹni-fo-tihín.

(Ọlabimtan 1974:42).

The one who is black and shining

The one that is stout-and-handsome,
offspring of Àlàdó

An-elderly-Ìjẹbú-man that-God endows-with
handsomeness

He came into the world and started searching
for knowledge

He that-comes-from-a respectable-family

He that is stout and handsome, the offspring
of Àlàdó

Offspring of a great physician

He that is tall and well-built, the husband
of Adé

A socialite

He that speaks-the foreign language as-if
it-is his-indigenous-language.

The poem above gives an account of Professor Ayò Bámgbóṣé's¹ intellectual achievement.

The title of the poem, 'ORÍKÌ ÀLÀDÓ' links Bámgbóṣé with Ṣàngó, the Yorùbá god of thunder and lightning. ÀLÀDÓ is the Oríkì of Ṣàngó who is alleged to be spitting fire from the mouth. The link with Ṣàngó is a depiction of Bámgbóṣé as an erudite scholar. The poem is a commendation and homage to the superior intellectual ability of Bámgbóṣé. For instance, he is referred to as

Afèdè-òhún-bí-ẹní-fọ-tihín

He-who-speaks-the-foreign-language-as-he-
speaks-his-indigenous language.

1. Professor Bámgbóṣé was born on January 27, 1932. He obtained a B.A. degree in English in 1960 from the University of Ibadán and a doctorate in Linguistics from the University of Edinburgh in 1963. He joined the University of Ibadán in 1963. He was Head of the Department of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages 1969 - 75 and 1977 - 81. He was also once a Dean, Faculty of Arts. He retired in 1991 as a Professor Emeritus.

Professor Bámgbóṣé is an academic giant known all over the world. He was a visiting Professor at both the University of Illinois, Urbana, Linguistic Institute, Urbana 1975 at the Hamburg University, 1979-80. He was External Examiner to many West African Universities (Lagos, Ifè, Ilorin, Legon (Ghana) and Yaounde (Cameroon). Professor Bámgbóṣé is the first and only African member on the Executive Committee of the World Organization of Linguistics (CIPL). It is this giant scholar that the poet refers to as 'Omọ Àládó.'

In fact, Bámgbóṣé is a Linguist and researcher of note who has carried his intellectual ability beyond the shores of Africa. His academic credentials justify his being addressed by the poet as a researcher thus :

Ó délé aiye oḡbón ló nṵwá kírí

He was born and starts searching for knowledge all about.

This literally means that as soon as he was born he started searching for knowledge.

The poet also refers to Bámgbóṣé as :

A-gun-òkè-àgbà-má-sò

The one who became a Professor.

Apart from this, the poet presents Bámgbóṣé as someone that combines academic capability with good character which makes him likeable by all. It is this virtue that the poet refers to in these lines :

Dáraníbí

Dáraníjọ

Èní ò fáyọ ní bínú ọkọ Adé

Ọmọdé kíí báyọọ yodí

Àgbà kíí báyọọ sọtá.

He that comes from a respectable family
 The Socialite
 It is he that does not desire happiness
 that hates the husband of Adé
 Children don't keep malice with happiness
 Elders bear no enmity with happiness.

Naturally, nobody hates happiness as the excerpt depicts. Ironically, Bámbóṣé's first name is 'Ayò' which means happiness. It is the name of 'Ayò' as Bámbóṣé's first name that the poet plays upon to achieve his intended goal. His intention is to portray Bámbóṣé a likeable man and this he achieves through his language use.

4.4 Elegy

When a loved one is dead, songs of lamentation are sung. Such songs in poetry differentiate elegiac poems from other forms of poetry. In Yorùbá culture, elegiac poem originates from 'òkú-pípè' (funeral rites). Òkú-pípè (Amo 1983) is one of the indigenous Yorùbá oral genres. The content of òkú-pípè consists of mainly 'oríkì' (praise poetry) rendered by the poet in a manner that brings out the pathos in it. It is through the

performance of òkú-pípè that the dead is sent on errands to the relatives that had died before him. It is the imitation of this age-long Yorùbá custom of òkú-pípè that the present Yorùbá poets use in their poems to honour the dead. In the other cultures where elegiac tradition exists, messages of errands through the dead, like that of the Yorùbá, may not be present in their poetry but their poems will contain lamentations.

It is the belief of the Yorùbá that life continues after death in the world beyond. They (Yorùbá) therefore advise the dead on what to eat in the new abode. In mortal life, neither millipede nor earthworm is eaten by the Yorùbá. Awólàlú (1979:59) explains:

the philosophers among the Yorùbá do not fail to remind people that if they do not want to eat millipedes centipedes in the hereafter, they should behave well while still here on earth.

The awareness of this concept of life after death influences greatly, the value of living among the Yorùbá because as Awólàlú (1970) further explains, "men and women are held responsible for their action".

According to Ògúnṣínà (1980:42), Yorùbá poems in honour of the dead had been in practice as far back as 1890. These were the poems written to lament the loss of loved ones published in the early Yorùbá newspapers. They are patterned on Christian hymns and the contents of the poems were very shallow. Atiládé's attempt in 1950 brought into focus Yorùbá traditional cultural values of treating the dead. Under this theme, we would examine the works of Atiládé (1950), Qdúnjọ (1961), Qládàpọ (1973) and Ìṣọlá (1978).

In his poem on the death of David Livingstone,¹ Atiládé (1950:19) challenges the taking away of Livingstone's corpse to England for burial, after he had worked in African Continent. Atiládé may not be all justified since taking away of the corpse of Livingstone is in consonance with the Yorùbá traditional belief that

Orí adé kí í sùnta

The one that will wear a crown is not
buried outside his place of birth.

¹ David Livingstone was one of the early British explorers to Africa. He started his humanitarian work from South Africa where he died eventually and was buried in England on April 18, 1874.

For Yorùbá cultural belief is that one should be able to point to the grave of a dead relative. Therefore, no matter the distance, a Yorùbá that dies outside his town or village is usually brought home for burial. But by opposing the taking away of Livingstone's corpse to England, Atíládé is reacting to the Yorùbá practice of wasting money to bring home the corpse of someone who has spent all his life outside his place of birth. It is economically unwise. Atíládé therefore indirectly challenges the socio-economic situation that allows the corpse to be taken away to England. This is a portrayal of the pre-independence Yorùbá society as being controlled by the colonial ruling class.

Though the poem is elegiac, but one thing that is noticed about the whole poem is that it is devoid of usual showering of praises on the dead which is characteristic of Yorùbá modern poets to serve as vanguard might explain why this is so. Furthermore, the existing poets then were not adequately exposed. The poem was written in 1950 when there were very few poets and those few ones were Christians. These few privileged literates would not see anything good in the

traditional ways of the Yorùbá. It is only the first line of every verse,

È ma sọ fún mí pé

Do not tell me that

that evokes pathos in the manner it is repeated. The poet's refusal of the fact that Livingstone corpse is carried away to England also excites pity and sadness.

Atíládé also wrote another poem on the death of James Emman Kweggir Aggrey, an African nationalist who was born in Cape Coast, Ghana. He says:

A! ikú dóró! ikú dóró

Ikú pọba ó sí tún pa m̀̀kúnnu

Ikú polówó, ikú palágbe

A! ikú dóró! ikú dóró!

Ikú p̀̀lékọ́ òlá, ara ilẹ̀ wúrà;

Ọmọ́ afọpọ́n owó jẹun

A! ikú dóró! ikú dóró

Ikú p'Aggrey Africa t'awa:

Ọmọ́ Igbo elérin, igbẹ̀ ọpẹ̀.

(Atíládé 1951:12).

Ah! Death has caused pain! Death has caused agony!
 Death took away the Qba and the poor
 Death killed the rich, Death killed the begger

Ah! Death has caused pain! Death has caused agony!
 Death killed the great scholar, a native of the
 land of gold

The offspring of he who eats with the wooden
 tray of money.

Ah! Death has caused pain! Death has caused agony!
 Death killed our Aggrey of Africa

The offspring of the forest of elephant, the bush
 of oil palm.¹

This poem is more of an elegy than the previous
 one on Livingstone. The poet opens the poem with
 lamentation!

A! ikú dóró! ikú dóró!

Ah! Death has caused pain! Death has caused agony!

which is a common Yorùbá traditional elegiac utterance.

This is repeated three times in the poem to show the

¹ Atíládé composes this poem in honour of Dr. James
 Emman Kwegyir Aggrey, a Fanti by tribe from Cape
 Coast in the Gold Coast, now Republic of Ghana.
 Aggrey's love for humanity transcended the frontier
 of Ghana, hence he was referred to as Aggrey of
 Africa by the Africans.

gravity of the havoc Death did by taking away Aggrey. The comparison in lines two and three, that is

'Qba' (King) versus 'mẹkúnnù' (the poor) and 'Olówó' (the rich) versus 'alágbe' (the beggar)

respectively, shows that death is no respecter of person. It also puts Aggrey, 'ẹlẹkọ ńlá' (the great scholar) at a high pedestal which is parallel to that of an 'Qba' (King) and 'Olówó' (the rich). In the traditional Yorùbá society, the Qba is held in high esteem. The Yorùbá Qba is supreme to all the citizens in the society. It is educational attainment that makes the poet compare Aggrey to an Qba and Olówó. The exalted position of an Qba among the Yorùbá and the respect accorded olówó in the society is reflected in the recognition of educational achievement as a parallel. Aggrey attained the degree of Doctor of Philosophy before his death.

The oríkì (praise-poetry) given to Aggrey in the excerpt can be seen against the background of the growing African nationalist spirit of the 1940s and 50s. The nationalist spirit of those years was

spontaneous and it swept across the entire continent, all with a common goal - emancipation of the people. It is the socio-political situation that creates this relationship between the poet, a Yorùbá from Nigeria, and the African nationalist spirit by showering praise-poetry on Aggrey, a Fanti from Ghana. When the poet says,

Ikú p'Aggrey Africa tàwa

Death killed our Aggrey of Africa.

The poet's deep sense of patriotism is further depicted when he refers to Aggrey as

Ọmọ igbó elérin, igbé ọpẹ

The Offspring of the forest of elephant,
the bush of oil palm.

Here, the poet is referring to the continent of Africa which has thick Equatorial forest where elephants and luxuriant oil palms abound.

Ọdúnjọ (1961) also wrote in memory of the Aláàfin of Ọyó in his poem, Ọládìgbòlù Kínní, Ọba Aláàfin Ọyó (Ọládìgbòlù, the first, the Aláàfin of Ọyó). Two phases

of íkú (Death) are depicted in the poem. The first is the Yorùbá idea about íkú (Death) that no one is too great or too important for íkú (Death) to kill. This is evident in

Ikú tó pa Ládìgbòlù tíí ẹ̀ Aláàfin Ọ̀yọ̀
Bó bá délé tálákà yíó pàparun. (p. 28).

The Death that killed Ládìgbòlù, the
Aláàfin of Ọ̀yọ̀

If it was a commoner it would have ruined
the whole household.

The first ten lines of the poem are in praise of the Aláàfin, touching on his greatness and power. He is referred to as 'Ọ̀ba ńlá tíí fọ̀ba í jẹ́' (the great Ọ̀ba that instals other Ọ̀bas). He is also addressed as the 'Afámọ̀lórí fọ̀dà kùn ún' which literally translates as 'he who after having his hair shaved, also paints it with tar'. This shows him as someone whose absolute authority over his subjects could not be questioned. The Aláàfin is also 'Olówó ládugbo' which portrays him as a very rich Ọ̀ba; and to crown it all, he is 'ọ̀kọ

bòròkinní, ' bòròkinní is a respectable gentleman in the society who is in a secure financial position. The Yorùbá often say,

Bòròkinní òun ọlọrọ egbéra ni.

This in effect means that the bòròkinní and the wealthy are financially at par. The poet labels the Aláàfin as 'olówó ládugbo' and at the same time as 'ọkọ bòròkinní' which means he can subdue the 'bòròkinní.' Indeed, the Aláàfin Ọba Ládìgbòlù was great, powerful and rich. This was in addition to his exalted position as an Ọba, not just an ordinary Ọba, but the Aláàfin of Ọyọ, 'the supreme head of all the kings (Ọbas) and princes of the Yorùbá nation' (Johnson 1921:41).

It is against this background that one could appreciate the fact that Death, is no respecter of anyone. There is no one too great to be killed by ikú (Death). If with all the aforementioned credentials, the Aláàfin was killed by ikú (Death), then, the poet is justified to say,

Ikú tó pa Ládìgbòlù tí í ẹ Aláàfin Ọyọ

Bó bá délé tálákà yio pàparun.

Which in essence means that the Death that could subdue Ládìgbòlù with all his power, riches and authority, if it were to visit a poor man's house, it

would exterminate his household and leave the house in desolation.

The second phase of Death shown in the poem is that Death is wicked and it does not show any mercy when it strikes. The poet says:

Ikú kò gbẹ̀bẹ̀, ìkú kò gbọ̀ jọ̀wọ̀
Bó bá sọ̀mọ̀dẹ̀ ilé a máa mú u lọ̀.

Death does not listen to human pleadings,
does not accept any excuse
If it is a juvenile, it would take
him away.

In these two poems on 'Death' written by Atiládé and Qdúnjọ, Atiládé sees death as no respecter of persons and as such, a leveler. On the other hand, Qdúnjọ sees the effect of death on the rich and the poor as not being the same. Death that kills the king, if it was a commoner it would have ruined the whole household.

This same view about Death is expressed by Qlabimtan (1969) and Fálétí (1982). In his poem,

Sọjì Ògúnbòwálé, ó dígbà (Sọjì Ògúnbòwálé, Farewell)
 Qlabimtan says:

Há à ìkà ikú, o kú àìnítilójú
 Ìwọ àgbà ìkà aláíláànú, ẹni ibi
 Ẹni burúkú tí òsọlé kíkún dahoro
 (Qlabimtan 1969:57).

Ah! cruel Death, you that have no shame
 You old cruel man that has no pity, a
 devilish person
 You evil that turn a lively house into
 ruins

And this is what Fálétí has to say about Death:

Ikú níí débi tó dùn tí í bà á jẹ
 Bíkú wọlé ọlá, a balé ọlá jẹ
 Bíkú wọle ọ̀tòṣì yóò fí kúnú rẹ tí ọ̀ dùn.
 (Fálétí in Ọlátúnjì 1982:56).

It is Death that visits where there is
 happiness and spoils their joy
 If Death enters that is dignified, it
 spoils the dignity
 If Death enters a poor man's house, it
 adds to his sorrow.

This is the general view of the Yorùbá about Death.

Death is wicked.

The idea of begging ikú (Death) presupposes that ikú (Death) could have been assumed as a god that must be appeased. The Yorùbá fear Death because Death would not accept any pleading when it chooses to strike.

The last four lines of the poem on the death of Aláàfin that we are examining,

Olódìgbòlù, òrun ire o!

Kí o má jòkùn, kí o má jekòlò

Ohun tí wọn nǵẹ lájùlé òrun

Ní o máa bá wọn jẹ.

Oládìgbòlù, your after-life will be comfortable!

Do not eat the millipede, do not eat the
earthworm

Whatever they feed on in heaven

It is that you should partake in

Speak much on the Yorùbá world-view and the belief in after-life. It is a wish for a good life in the life after-life. It is also the belief of the Yorùbá that after life (experience) one could live a life of affluence or of poverty. The poor who at times, turn

into reptiles or beasts eat such things as earthworm and so on. But those who sustain their humanity in the spirit world live as kings in the after-life. This is what ^{the} lines suggest in this context. That is, do not lose your 'humanity', identify with your ancestors and be a part of them.

The use of this Yorùbá traditional farewell to the dead is a testimony of Qdúnjọ's love for the Yorùbá tradition and culture. His use of Oríkí of the Aláàfin is another example.

Qládàpò also wrote a poem on the death of Adékúnlé Fajuyi, one time Military Governor of Old Western Region. The poem is titled 'Bá a perí akọni' (When we mention a brave person). It is a comprehensive account of the politics of the death of Fajuyi.¹

1. After the first military coup of January 15, 1966 in Nigeria, Major-General Aguiyi Ironsi became the Nigeria Head of State and he appointed Military Governors for each of the four Regions. Lt. Col. Adekunle Fajuyi was appointed Military Governor of Western Region. He was well received by the people who had already felt dissatisfied with the civilian government of Chief Ladoke Akintola and were yearning for a change of government. The poet highlights what brought the military into government; what led to Fajuyi's premature death and his (Fajuyi) achievement in the West within the few months he stayed in office as the Governor.

On the death of Fajuyi, the poet speaks the mind of the people when he says:

Àwa la lóṣèlú ò ṣèlú mọ́ tó
 Lọ̀ràn fi yí bírí: La fi yígbà padà
 Tá a gbéṣé Ọba sọwọ́ Jagunjagun.

We found fault with the civilian government
 Everything changed: and governance changed
 And we welcome the military into government.

This shows the total support given to the Military by the people. But their joy was short-lived and their hope dashed by the sudden death of Fajuyi. This is expressed in these lines:

Ewúrẹ́ wá bojú wò rere: Nwọ̀n ò réléèpo
 Àgùntàn Ọ̀dùdùwà bojú wọ̀dẹ̀dẹ̀
 Nwọ̀n ò réléèrí mọ́
 Káàárọ̀-o-ò-jí-bí wòhín wọ̀hún
 A ò màrà rọ̀gbàgbà

The goats look up in vain, their caretaker
 is no more
 The sheep of Ọ̀dùdùwà look round the house

Their caretaker is gone
 Káàárò-o-ò-jí-bí look here and there
 We no longer see the deliverer.

Indeed, Fajuyi is a deliverer. As pointed out earlier, the situation in the Western Region immediately before the first coup that brought Fajuyi, was very unbearable. So, the people felt relieved with the arrival of the Military represented by Fajuyi.

The poet presents Fajuyi as a brave soldier;

Ọmọ ajagun dójú ikú

Ọmọ ajagun bógun lọ

Ọmọ iyá ìkòyí

Ọmọ a rẹrín rẹ é kokú lójú.¹

1. This is part of the oríkí of the ìkòyí people. They are warriors of the ancient Yorubá Kingdom; they are very militant and they are well known for their military valour. This comparison of Fajuyi with the famous Olukoyi lineage is in acknowledgement of Fajuyi's military prowess.

Offspring of the great one that fights
a war unto the point of death

Offspring of the great one that fights a
war and perished in the war

Offspring of the woman who hails from ìkòyí

Offspring of the great one who laughs to his
death

A further attestation of Fajuyi's bravery is seen in
these lines from the text.

Ng ò tún réèyàn tó le bọ̀rẹ̀ẹ̀ kú laiye

Àyàfí Yewande

Tó bOlukoyi wọ̀lẹ̀ nílẹ̀ Ilọ̀rín

Àyàtún fí tAdekunle ọ̀mọ̀ Fajuyi nílẹ̀ Ìbàdàn

I have not seen a person that could die
with his friend in the world

Except Yewande

That disappeared into the bottom of the
earth with Olukoyi at Ilọ̀rín

Except Adekunle the son of Fajuyi
at Ìbàdàn.

This is another historical allusion to the Olukoyi
lineage. How Fajuyi died is compared to Yewande's

feat at Ilorin, when she was alleged to have disappeared into the bottom of the earth with Olukoyi (Babalola 1966). It is also alleged that Fajuyi voluntarily surrendered himself to be killed by the coup plotters of July 29, 1966. It was speculated that he asked to be killed with his host, Major-General Inronsi who was on a State visit to the West then. He did not want to be seen as if he collaborated with the coup plotters to eliminate the Head of State. It is this speculation that the poet expressed in the text.

But no matter the way Fajuyi died, it is a surprise to the poet that he (Fajuyi) could die in such a way having survived tougher military actions before. He makes reference to this in the excerpt in these lines:

Ìjà tó o jà jà ni Kóngò
 Tó o fí gbàsiyá tẹ̀nìkan ò ní rí
 Ó wá jẹ̀ pẹ̀lé logun tí mú ọ̀ lọ!

The battle that you fought for long in Congo
 That earned you a medal that no one has
 ever had

How come that it is here at home that you died in the battle!

The battle the poet is referring to is the United Nations Peace Keeping Force that Nigeria joined to restore peace in the Republic of Congo in the late fifties. Fajuyi was one of the Nigerian soldiers that participated in that Peace Keeping Force. Also Ogun (battle) that took away Fajuyi according to the excerpt is the second military coup in Nigeria that occurred on July 29, 1966. In fact, this was not a real battle but to the Yorùbá, 'ilé ayé ogun ni' - which literally means that our life in this world is a battle; it is the survival of the fittest.

Apart from his role as a 'deliverer' and a 'caretaker' as expressed by the poet, Fajuyi left his footprint on the sand of time for his enviable achievement in his very short military tenure as the governor of the Western Region. First, he made the training for the Nigerian Certificate of Education (NCE) free. Hitherto, fees were charged when similar Institutions in other parts of Nigeria, at Lagos and Zaria were free.

He also increased the salary of NCE Graduates. Also, before then, NCE graduates in the West were paid less salary than their counterparts in other parts of Nigeria. This anomaly was corrected by Fajuyi as shown in the text.

Eni bá wà nílẹ̀-ẹ̀kọ̀-gíga Adéyẹmí (Ondo)
 Tí Fajuyi fi sọlẹ̀-ìwé dọpọ̀
 TÁdékúnlẹ̀ fi sọlẹ̀-ẹ̀kọ̀ dọfẹ̀
 Tó tún mbùkún owó oşù àwọ̀n olùkọ̀
 Yio mò wí pé
 Irú tí ọ̀ bá şaládùn ọ̀bẹ̀
 Un lekú wọlé: Un lekú gbé jẹ.

Whoever was at the Adeyemi College of
 Education, Ondo

When Fajuyi promoted the course of education
 When Adekunle made education free,
 And even increased the salary of teachers
 Will agree that
 The spice that would have enriched the soup
 Is the one that the rat entered: and the
 rat consumed.

This is one of the reasons why the people of the old

Western Region of Nigeria could not easily forget Fajuyi as voiced by the poet.

Finally, one is not left in doubt of the poet's intention to portray Fajuyi as a brave soldier, an invaluable administrator and an achiever. Fajuyi was in office as a Governor for just six months, January 1966 to July 1966 and he endeared himself to the people he governed. The poet, by his posture, presents himself as an admirer of the military as shown in his praises for Fajuyi.

Our last poet that writes on elegiac theme is Akínwùmi Ìṣòlá. What is unique about his own contribution is that he writes on two people who were very close to him when they were alive. One of them was his colleague and the other was once his teacher. Ìṣòlá's poem on Professor Ọ́jẹ̀dòkun is titled 'Ikú Ọ́lášùpọ̀ Ọ́jẹ̀dòkun (The Death of Ọ́lášùpọ̀ Ọ́jẹ̀dòkun) and is opened up thus:

È kú íbáńídàró

È mà mà kú íbáńídàró ẹnì wá:

Àńí Ọ́lášùpọ̀ Àrẹ̀mú ẹ̀mọ́ Ọ́jẹ̀dòkun

To sebí idán tó yọ nínú ẹ̀gbẹ́ẹ́ wá

Tó gbòná èbùrú, ó yoni sílẹ̀ láítọ́jọ́
 Ó rú ní lójú bó ẹ̀ sáré tẹ̀rígbaşọ
 (Ìşọlá 1978:11)

Thank you for your sympathy
 Thank you for sympathising with us on
 the death of our kinsman
 I am referring to Ọláşùpọ́ Arẹmu, the son
 of Ọjẹdokun
 Who, like a magic, vanished from our midst
 Who tricked us and left us stealthily
 prematurely
 We were bewildered by his premature death.

The poem is a funeral oration read by the poet on behalf of the University of Lagos at the grave-side of the late Professor Ọláşùpọ́ Ọjẹdòkun.¹ The oration touched on his virtues and the mysteries surrounding his untimely death.

This text is a further portrayal of the Yorùbá poet and the academics in the military era. It is

1. Professor Ọjẹdòkun was a lecturer in the History Department, University of Lagos between 1970 and 1974. He later became the Director General, Nigeria Institute of International Affairs (NIIA). The poet, Ìşọlá, was also a lecturer in the Department of African Languages and Literatures of the same University.

a concern for academic scholarship. Both the structure and language of the poem are tailored to achieve this goal. The academic issues raised in the text portray the type of audience at the disposal of the poet. What we want to emphasise is that the audience, to a large extent, determines the language of the poet. Majority of the audience are colleagues of the late Professor Ojédòkun at the University of Lagos. For instance, at the beginning of the excerpt, he says

A á ẹe é jagun láidúró méréú?

A á ẹe é ẹòwò láidúró jèrè?

A á ẹe é tajà ká má le è dúró gbowó
ka tóó máa lọ?

Why should one fight a war and fail to
search for captives?

Why should one trade and never wait for the
profit?

Why should one sell and not collect money
before leaving?

Ojédòkun was not a soldier neither was he a trader,
but why this analogy to describe an academic? It is a

deliberate use of language to elicit more sympathy and concern for the loss of Ọjẹdòkun. This analogy is very apt. It refers to Ọdẹdòkun that fought academic 'war' and performed great academic feats but like a soldier that takes no captive and a trader that waits for no profit, Ọjẹdòkun did not live long to enjoy the fruit of his labour.

The poet also brings Ọjẹdòkun's international academic recognition into focus in these lines:

Ó dé tán ó di baba-ńlá a-fòṣẹlú-pitàn
 Itàn ilẹ yí nikan kọ
 Baba Káyòdé mọ tilẹ míran mọ ọn
 Bo ti ń sọ ti Larubawa
 Ló ń fi ti Faranse kọrin
 Tílú Amẹrika ò bá ọ lájànbàkù
 Oòyì iwé dá lójú baba Káyòdé.

On his arrival, he became an acclaimed
 political historian

It is not only African history
 The father of Káyòdé is versed in other
 lands history

As he versed in that of the Arabs
That of America does not give him any
problem

Káyòdé's father is very skilled in the art.

And finally, the poet touches on Ọjédòkun's role as a lecturer and a researcher as part of his achievement in academics. He says:

Ọmọ Awèró akónimá kù síbikan
Ó ò ẹ̀ ẹ́ gbàgbé lágbègbè Akoka
Èkó ìjìnlẹ̀ yí nàà ló gbé ọ́ dẹ̀şẹ́. Ijọba

The son of Awèró he that teaches - without
leaving any part untouched

It is not easy to forget you in the
neighbourhood of Akoka

It is this same intellectual capability that
earned you a government assignment.¹

¹ As a renown researcher, Ọjédòkun was appointed by the government as the Director General of the Nigeria Institute of International Affairs (NIIA). This is what the poet refers to in the excerpt above.

Ìṣòlá's respect for academics is also shown in another poem, 'Àbú Olódodo.' Ìṣòlá in this poem, highlights Òjó's¹ personal intellectual capability, his teaching ability and his promotion of scholarship in his students. He also died prematurely. Ìṣòlá remarks that :

Òjó ló gboyè méjì pò

Tí gbogbo ayé wa ní pè é ni baba

Baba ní ṣe nínúu ká mowé

Baba ní ṣe nínúu ka mohun tó yẹ ni

Kò kúkú kúrò lóṣṣe tó fi gboyè méjì (M.A.).

It is Òjó that passed two degrees at the same time

And the whole world hailed him as a father

He is really a father in his intellectual ability

He is really a father in his ability to know what is right

He had his two degrees without venturing out of his corridor.

1. Chief Òjó was one time Principal of Wesley College, Ibadán. He was respected for his love for academics. He taught Ìṣòlá the poet, while at the Wesley College, Ibadán, 1957 - 58. Ìṣòlá was the Senior Prefect in 1958.

This apparently is a reference to his brilliant academic career. And as a teacher, Òjó excelled because he was dedicated to the cause he believed in, that is, academics. He goes further to strengthen the importance of honour to humanity over materialism as evident in the life of Òjó. He says :

Báráyé máa wí:

Wọn a lówon tó ní purọ́ ló ní jẹun ayé

Wọn léyànkéyàn ló lèrè ibẹ̀

Wọn ni pípẹ́ láyé nikan lèrè ayé

Mo gbọ́ títí, mo rín wọn rín wọn

Orúkọ rere lèrè ayé

(Ìṣòlá 1978:6).

When people would reason

They would assert that it is people with
dubious character that enjoy life

They would say it is the bad people that
gain from it

They would say that to live long is man's
only earthly gain.

When I heard this, I laughed and laughed at
them

To leave a good name behind is the gain
of life.

The poet's position is a depiction of another Yorùbá worldview. The poet is advocating for a change in

the orientation of the society towards material acquisition. Acquisition of wealth is associated with capitalism where good name is thrown overboard.

In the Ìṣòlá's two poems that we have just examined, Ìṣòlá has given us an insight into the lives of two personalities that were close to him in their life time. The poet, through his presentation of these two great Yorùbá scholars, has succeeded in presenting to us the new phenomenon of the growing importance of academics in the military era.

4.5 Cultural Awareness

The treatment of culture-related issues runs through the whole decades of our study period 1949 - 1989. Why this is so is obvious. Culture is dynamic, it continues changing and taking on new looks with time. But through the so called changes, the Yorùbá culture suffered miscegenation.

The indigenous people of Nigeria, including Yorùbá, had a culture and language of their own before the advent of British colonialism in 1861. Since our contact with the British culture, our culture has not been the same again till today despite the fact that Nigeria became politically independent in 1960. The

early poets started the cry to salvage and preserve the Yorùbá language and culture as shown by Ọlabimtan (1974). And in fact, the Yorùbá cultural emancipation was initiated by these early poets. Despite this early cry, the situation has hardly changed for the better. This is why the poets under study continue with the crusade.

Ìṣòlá (1978) frowns at the apathy of the Yorùbá youths to their native language in his poem, 'Èwe Ìwòyí' (Youths of Today). He says :

Bé ẹ dájùjọ àgbáyé

Bí wọn ni o kẹwì lédè rẹ

Wọn a máa ẹ bi alákoṛa

Wọn a fèdè bí ẹni a di lórùn.

(Ìṣòlá 1978:51).

At international conference
If asked to render a poem in native language
They will feel uneasy
They speak as one who is being strangled.

The last line,

Wọn a fèdè òyìnbó bí ẹni a di lórùn

They speak as one who is being strangled.

shows the poet's condemnation of the youths' imitation of how an English man speaks. Oyerrinde (1981) also

reiterates his disgust at the Yorùbá undue preference for foreign languages. He says :

Ọmọ ní fèdè Gẹ̀ẹ̀sì kí baba nínú ilé
 Ó ní fi Faransé sọ fún yèyè è
 Ẹun fẹ́ẹ́ jẹun !

A gbọ́ Jamani, a gbọ́ Rọ̀sía

A wáá gbàgbé èdè abíníbí wa !

(Oyerinde 1981:48).

The child is greeting his father at home in English

He also uses French to tell his mother that he wants to eat

We speak German, we speak Russian language

But we forget our indigenous language !

The contention of the poet in the above text is that we should not adopt foreign language and culture and abandon our own. Babalọ́lá (1989:20) also supports this opinion in his 'Ọ̀rọ̀ Ìyànjú' (Words of Advice). He is very categorical about the futility in giving preference to another man's language besides one's own language. He says :

Bí ẹ̀ kọ́ iwé kọ́ iwé kọ́ iwé

È ẹ̀ lè dọ̀yinbó funfun, ẹ̀ ẹ̀ sàimò bẹ̀ẹ̀

Èniyàn dúdú ọmọ̀ Nàìjíríà ní gbogbo yin porogodo

'Torí náà ẹ má gbàgbé ilé
 Ẹ má gbàgbé èdè ànà a jọ sọ

- - -

Ẹ má jé ká mọ èdè elédè
 Jù èdè ilẹẹ tiwa lọ.¹
 (Babalqlá 1989:20).

No matter how learned you may be
 You cannot transform yourself to a white man,
 that is obvious to you all
 You are all Nigerians
 Therefore don't forget your origin
 Don't forget our native language

- - -

Don't be more versed in another man's language
 Than our native language.

The three poets examined above have emphasised
 only the language aspect of culture, thereby neglecting
 other aspects that make up culture. However, Qlabimtan

¹ Babalqlá's message is an appeal he made to a group of
 Nigerian students in London during his student's days.
 His love for his mother tongue in far away London is
 a manifestation of his interest in his culture. It
 is evident from the text that Babalqla is not against
 the use of the English language by Nigerians but his
 argument is that Nigerians should not forget their
 own language.

goes a step further by condemning how the Yorùbá age-long respect for elders has been badly battered by the so-called modernity when he says in his poem, 'Ìlájú' (Modernity).

Ìlájú dé idòbálẹ̀ ò sí mọ̀
 Ìlájú dé, aya ní pọ̀kọ̀ lóókọ̀
 Ìlájú dé, àgbà ò lówò
 Tani ò mọ̀ páfọ̀jú nílájú
 Tó wọ̀lé bá gbogbo wa?
 (Ọlabimtan 1969:44).

Because of modernity, the youths no longer
 ...prostrate to greet elders
 Because of modernity, the wife calls her
 husband by his name
 Because of modernity, age is no more respected
 Who will say modernity is good
 This modernity that has come to stay?

This repetition of 'Ìlájú dé' in lines 1, 2 and 3 shows the seriousness and the contempt with which the poet takes the adverse effect of modernity on our culture. The fourth line is a metaphorical expression which shows modernity as being blind and so could not judge correctly.

In the same vein, this is corroborated by Oyerinde when he says :

Ọmọ ń dúró kí baba

Aya ò gbọ tọkọ

Ọmọge ò lè kúnlẹ kí yèyé ẹ

Obinrin ń dọkọ nínú ilé

(Oyerinde 1981:48).

The son no longer prostrate to greet
his father

The wife is disobedient to her husband

Daughters cannot kneel down to greet
their mothers

Women are lords in their matrimonial homes.

Awóyélé (1987) on his own, attacks the attitude of some Nigerians that import foreign culture to Nigeria. In one of his didactic poems, 'Alákòwé Òkè Ọhún,' the poet gives an account of the social malady of an educated elite that returns from overseas expecting his relatives, including his parents, to book an appointment to visit him. He says :

Ng ò ní hùwà bí alákòwé òkè ọhún

Tó kàwé ogóji tí ò gbọn

Ó kàwé ogóji ó sì fi lárá gbogbo ti

wọn yí i ka lọ

Èèbó bí Èlẹ̀-ngà níí fọ̀ ká
 Báráalé bá a lálẹ̀jò, Ajá ni fi í lé wọ̀n lọ.
 (Awóyẹ̀lé 1987b:77).

I won't behave like that educated man over
 there
 That is well read but senseless
 Being well read, he scares away all relations
 around him
 He speaks English about like the weaver bird
 Whenever relations visit him, he scares them
 away with his dog.

The poet's choice of number 'forty' in the phrase,
 Tó kàwé ogóji tí ò gbọ̀n
 is symbolic. It literally means despite his high level
 of education, he still behaves in an unthinkable
 manner.

The condemnation of this foreign culture by the
 poet is seen in his conclusion. He says :

Akọ̀wé ọ̀hún kú kò sẹ̀ni dé' bẹ̀ lọ̀ọ̀ sínkú

— — —

Ìyàwó èèbó ò mọ̀ọ̀yàn

Kò bẹ̀bí ọ̀kọ̀ ẹ̀ bẹ̀ẹ̀ wọ̀n ò mọ̀ ọ̀n

Ló bá múra ló ta kọ̀sọ̀

Ló kóhun gbogbo tó ní mọ̀ tọ̀kọ̀ ló lẹ̀

Ó kómọ ó kẹrù ó sì kówó

Lèèbó bá ẹ se ni yàjójó darí rẹlú ẹ.

The educated man died and no one attended
his burial

His wife was not sociable with people

She did not relate with her husband's
relations and nobody recognised her

So she got ready and went out stealthily

She packed all her belongings together
with those of her husband and went away

She took the children, took the belongings
plus money

And the white quickly returned to her
country.

This sad ending is indicative of the poet's rejection
of the practice that imbibes foreign culture. The
Yorùbá culture does not support this educated man's
behaviour. Changes in one's culture are desirable
but, using Nduka's (1964:vi) words,

There should be a more
discriminating blending of
foreign cultural elements
with the indigenous cultural
heritage.

4.6 Social Vices and Virtues

Several poets under study comment on social vices and virtues in the society during the time they wrote their poems. These poets include, Odúnjò (1949), Şowùnmi (1952), Oládàpò (1975), Fálétí (1982), Thompson (1988) and Awé (1989).

Odúnjò discusses some prevailing social issues in the society which are still relevant today. Take for instance, the issue of polygamy. Polygamy is valued in traditional Yorùbá society for social and economic reasons. A traditional Yorùbá man is basically a farmer. For economic reason, therefore, he marries two wives. In her article, 'Yorùbá Women In History,' Professor Bolanle Awé (1979:14) shows the invaluable assistance of women on their husband farms. She says :

A Yorùbá farmer's wife; although she hardly tills the ground, she often does the tedious job of getting farm products to the market.

Apart from this, the woman also helps her husband to carry the jam tubers for planting; she helps in the harvesting and the processing of the crops. The

larger the farms owned by the man, the greater the number of his wives. This economic reason encouraged and sustained polygamy in traditional Yorùbá society of the fifties. It is not only the wives that are involved in the help on the farms but also their large number of children. Socially, the status of the man is measured by the number of wives he has which in effect is indicative of a big household.

Despite these contributions to the socio-economic status of a man in the society, Qdúnjọ picks hole in polygamy in his poem, 'Aya bẹ̀rẹ̀, itiyà bẹ̀rẹ̀' (polygamy with its numerous problems). In the poem, problems such as rivalry, envy, and deceit that are common with polygamous homes are highlighted. To Qdúnjọ, polygamy is exploitative.

However, we discover from Qdúnjọ's submission that his posture on polygamy might have stemmed from two things. First, Qdúnjọ is a product of the missionary education which does not support polygamy. So, his sympathy lies with the colonialists. Secondly, the issue at stake is a conflict of the Yorùbá idea of marriage and the colonial imported form of marriage. It was the influence of Christianity that brought about the

marriage ordinance. It is the Marxist concept whereby the artists write to propagate and establish the ideology of the ruling class. By virtue of his education, Ọdúnjọ tends to take side with the ruling class thus ignoring the socio-economic factor of polygamy.

Ọdúnjọ provides a justification for his stand on polygamy when he concludes that :

Èkọ di wúrá lójá

Baba di ẹrú to nsin ọmọ tó bí gbogbo !

Education is expensive

Fathers are slaves that labour for their children.

Ọdúnjọ as a member of the society, is aware of the importance which education has attracted to itself. Because of his own education, he finds himself in the elitist class in his society. He believes the time children used to serve their parents on the farm had gone. The new social order is education which every parent strives to give to his children.

Ọdúnjọ does not attack the traditional culture without taking cognizance of the role of the husband in the family. This role is transmitted in the text above when the poet argues that :

Baba di ẹrú tó ńsain ọmọ tó bí gbogbo
 Fathers are slaves that labour for their
 children.

Ọdúnjọ reiterates his posture on polygamy in two other poems, 'Aya bẹẹrẹ ní da'lé rú' (It is polygamy that ruins the home) and 'Ọmọ bẹẹrẹ, ọpá bẹẹrẹ' (Too many children breed Destitution). In the first poem above, Ọdúnjọ attacks the women for being responsible for the destruction of homes, while in the second, he attributes the existence of useless children in polygamous homes to the production of too many children. The attack on women for being responsible for the destruction of homes is unfair on the female gender. Before the European contact, polygamy in the Yorùbá traditional society was well established, that usually it was devoid of any rancour among the co-wives. Its establishment has a deep-rooted Yorùbá customary practice.

Polygamy is not all that destructive as Ọdúnjọ has painted it in the two poems. It is a patriarchal verdict and it is partial. Women have their roles to play in a polygamous home in the Yorùbá traditional society and to play it successfully depends on the men's support and cooperation. Ọdúnjọ ignores the part men

could play to make polygamy work. If a man is alive to his responsibilities in the home, many of the vices inherent in polygamy could be averted. Oḍúnjọ's observation is personal and questionable. It is based on foreign culture already imbibed. It would thus seem Oḍúnjọ is an apologist of the colonialists, who happen to be the ruling class.

This leads us to another social issue discussed by Oḍúnjọ (1949b) and Sówúnmi (1952), which is Yorùbá ideology of hardwork. In 'Ìṣẹ́ Ní Ọ̀ògùn Ìṣẹ́' (Labour is the Remedy for Poverty) Oḍúnjọ says :

Ìṣẹ́ ní ọ̀ògùn ìṣẹ́
 Múra ẹ́ṣẹ́ ọ̀rẹ́ mí
 Ìṣẹ́ ní a fi í dẹni gíga

- - -
 Má fòwúrò ẹ́rẹ́ ọ̀rẹ́ mí
 Múra ẹ́ṣẹ́, ọ̀jọ́ n lẹ.

(Oḍúnjọ 1949b:14).

To labour is the remedy of poverty
 Strive to work hard, my friend
 It is labour that makes one great

- - -
 Do not gamble with the prime of your life,
 my friend
 Work hard, time is flying.

The title of the poem, 'Ìṣẹ́ ni oògùn ìṣẹ́' is philosophical. Baring all odds, the traditional Yorùbá believe that if one works hard, one will not be poor. And no matter what assistance one gets to become rich, it is one's personal hard work that can sustain one's lasting satisfaction.

Ṣowunmi also, like Ọdúnjọ, titles his poem 'Ìṣẹ́ Loògùn Ìṣẹ́'. He opens his own poem with a Bible quotation,

Òru mbò nígbà tí ẹnìkan kì ó le ṣíṣẹ́

John 9 ẹṣẹ 4.

The night cometh when no one can work

John 9 verse 4.

Then his message reads :

Ọṣìṣẹ́ kò ma kúkú ebi

Mo dojú kọṣẹ́ òkò n sọlẹ

- - -

Ìgbì mo ba jẹ iyán tán ma tún mọmu

Òkò nówó bíà àfi bọlugí

Ògùrẹ́ tẹ mi lẹrùn jọtí òfin lẹ

(Ṣowunmi 1952 :6).

One who labours will not die of hunger
I face my work, I am not lazy

- - -

When I finish eating pounded yam I will drink
 palm-wine
 I cannot afford beer except the native gin
 I prefer the wine obtained from raphia tree
 to the contraband alcohol.

The text above is a clear support for the Yorùbá ideology of hardwork. This is in line with Ọdúnjọ's (1949b) message. The poet presents himself as an example of a person that is hard working and at the same time not ashamed of his work.

Mo dojú kọşẹ ñko ñ sọlẹ

Mo ọmọ asọrọtà

I face my work, I am not lazy

I become one who trades in words

He is just a poet who derives his livelihood from talking. He presents himself as one who is self-sufficient through hardwork. He poses as an Ọba relaxing majestically in his own-made palace, his sitting-room . His contentment which is in line with the Christian doctrine favours the socio-political situation of that period. The opening Bible quotation is relevant to the content of this poem. It is a statement that shows that there is time for everything and therefore the right thing should be done at the

right time. A seriously minded person should work during the day because, 'the night cometh when no one can work.' There is time to work, there is time to rest.

The poet also presents a picture of a lawful citizen who is not ready to violate the law of the land. He says :

Ògùrò tẹ mí lẹrùn jọtí òfin lẹ
 Ñko rẹni gbọkẹlẹ pé 'Jọba líjà

I prefer palm-wine to contraband wine
 I have no one to trust to challenge the
 Government.

All this strict obedience to the law of the land is a pointer to being a good citizen which in effect promotes good governance. As such it might have paved the way for the smooth running of the colonial machinery. It is equally in conformity with traditional standard of behaviour.

Furthermore, the use of words ògùrò, bíà, bólugí, sigá and tábà is an indication of the socio-cultural changes in the society. It, in a covert way depicts the glaring effects of Western civilization on the Yorùbá community. The cultural drink of the Yorùbá is

ògùrò which is cheaper and within the reach of the middle class of which Şowunmi is a member. But beer is costly and it is for the higher echelon of the society. The Yorùbá were used to smoking tábà (tobacco) but with the effect of western civilization, they change to cigarette smoking which to them, is a mark of prestige. Thus the use of the words ògùrò and bíà; sigá and tábà does not only produce poetic beauty it is more importantly a strong portrayal of socio-economic changes in the pre-independence Yorùbá society.

Ọládàpọ on his own specifically exposes some of the social vices plaguing the Nigeria society in his poem, 'Àlá Ìnàwó' (Dream about a social party).

He says :

- - -

Lójú àlá mi òní;

Mo ba wọn débi nàwónáwó -

Tí ònàwó bówóo wọn ti tó

Mo lọ síbi àsè

Níbi olówó méjì gbe òtáákà

- - -

Ọpọ èrò ló dá dàrààsì lẹgbẹjọdá

Ọlátubòsun tí ò rówó lògbà lójú ayé
Mo tún mbá wọn dáṣọ ànkóò !

(Ọládàpọ 1975:103).

In my dream, today
I went to a party where rich people
Were squandering money to display their
wealth

I attended a party
Where two rich people were competing
- - -

Many people dressed alike in damask
Ọlátubòsun that has no money to maintain
himself in real life.

I joined them to wear identical dress !

In this poem, Ọládàpọ leads us into what operated at a night party he attended. He shows us the high calibre of people that were present at the party and how the people squandered money. The party ended abruptly in chaos. Ọládàpọ discovers it is all but a dream.

The galaxy of distinguished personalities in the excerpt, 'Adájọ nláńlá' (high-ranking judges), 'Dókítà àtiṣẹgùn (doctors and pharmacists), 'oníṣòwò kàńkà' (reputable merchants), 'olóri ilé-ẹkọ nláńlá àtọba Ọba' (heads of higher institutions and Ọbas),

'ògá Ṣójà, ògá Ọlópàá' (top military officers and police officers), 'lémòmù àgbààgbà àtoníwáásù' (Chief imams and top preachers) and agbẹjórò òlálá (reputable lawyers), is a pointer to the structure of the society. These are the people that matter in the society. They constitute the upper class structure of the society.

This assemblage of 'who is who' in the society portrays the changing socio-economic strata of the society in the seventies. It is unthinkable for religious leaders, top military and police officers, court judges and academics to be found at such night parties in the forties and fifties. It would look an unusual gathering then.

It is the result of the socio-political situation prevalent in the society then. It portrays a society that has lost its credibility. Those who are supposed to be good examples to the society were present at the party. For example, judges who are expected to be impeccable in character were there. The law-enforcement agents like the police were also dining at the party. These are government agents who are to arrest and prosecute people of dubious character who live above

their means like those spraying money at the party as expressed in the excerpt.

Judges do not normally attend such parties in real life. However, the poet has revealed the level of decadence in the military era. This was the oil-boom period of the seventies when there was a temporary buoyant Nigeria. As pointed out earlier in this work, the Adebọ Award of 1970/71 and the Udoji Award of 1974/75 increased the salaries of workers. This explains why there was too much spending here and there across the country as evident in this excerpt.

The presence of soldiers in such a gathering gives us a lucid picture of an economic and social change in the society. Soldiers used to live in barracks in the forties and the fifties. The seventies was a decade of the military era. We have said that this decade, 1970-72, is a military era. Before 1966 when Nigeria had the first military coup, soldiers were never seen on the streets talk less of attending civilian night parties. As we have pointed out earlier, they were restricted to the barracks and officers' Mess. Apart from the two coups that brought them out, the Biafran War of 1967-70 aggravated the situation.

There are other several revelations about the society in the military era contained in this excerpt. The poet elaborates on these in these lines :

Bá à kọle ká sílé -

A le nàwó igbeyàwó

A le nàwó ọmọ -

Ka nàwó gbígbéga;

A le ẹ̀nàwó ọjọ-ibí -

A le nàwó níbi òkú àgbà.

If we are not celebrating house-warming,
 We can be spending on wedding ceremony
 It can be a naming ceremony
 We can be celebrating a promotion
 It could be a birthday ceremony
 We can spend on burial ceremony of an old
 person.

This is a further depiction of the various government awards' influence on the society in the military era. These awards have left the society with greater improved incomes and conditions of service. The awards also created temporary relief to the society and so people could afford lavishing money on parties as depicted in the excerpt.

Similarly, the calibre of personalities present at the party in the excerpt reveals the type of society in the military era of 1970-79. The group of distinguished personalities in the excerpt is arranged by the poet thus :

Adájọ́ níláńlá tó mbẹ́ níbẹ́ tógóje
 Dókítà àtìsègùn tó mbẹ́ níbẹ́ tógófà
 Onísòwò kànkà tó mbẹ́ níbẹ́ tó'rínwó
 Olórí ilé-èkọ́ níláńlá àtọba Ọba
 Wọ́n lẹ́ lẹ́gbẹ́ bí omi
 Ọgá Sọjà, ọgá Ọlọpàá
 Lajọ́ nmutí níbi àjọyọ
 Lèmọmù àgbààgbà àtoníwàási, wọ́n péjú
 Agbẹjọrò níláńlá mbujó níwájú àwọ́n ọmọge.

Judges in attendance were about one hundred
 and forty

Doctors and pharmacists in attendance were
 about one hundred and twenty

Reputable merchants in attendance were about
 four hundred

Heads of higher institutions and Ọbas
 present

Were uncountable

Top military officers and Police officers
 Were dining and wining with us at the party

Chief Imams and top preachers were there
 Reputable lawyers were dancing merrily with
 ladies.

As we have already pointed out, this is a depiction of a roll-call of those that matter in the society. By associating these personalities with what the poet is attacking, is an indirect way of condemning the Nigerian leaders in the military era. The changing socio-economic situation in the military era is also shown in :

Şàdédé ni mo rẹni méjì ti òtáákà -

Ngò morúkọ wọ

Ọkan àgbà-akọ, ọkan àgbà-abo

Gbogbo èrò tó bá wọ dáşọ

Ni wọ mbùn lẹbùn

Àntí àgbà

Ló kọkọ òháke tó òhá kúpà rẹ ẹ ká.

Suddenly I saw two people competing -

I don't know their names

One is an elderly man, one is an elderly woman

All the people that dress alike in their special
 material

Were being given gifts

The elderly Aunty

Was the first to distribute her copper about.

I never knew it was not real life
It was all but a dream.

The chaos witnessed at the end of this party as evident in the excerpt above, needs some investigation. From where did the criminals get the sophisticated weapons they used for their operation? The Biafran war ended in 1970. To prosecute the war, both parties, Nigeria and Biafran recruited many soldiers. Most of these soldiers were discharged from the army after the war. This swelled up the unemployment market leaving many able-bodied men roaming the streets. The wave of criminality in the society in the seventies was therefore very alarming. There was an upsurge of highway robbery. Daylight robbery was very common while armed robbers killed and maimed innocent people. All these crimes were committed with all impunity. The socio-economic and political situation is the cause of the chaos at the party in the excerpt.

The affront caused by the distinguished personalities provoked the criminals or the aggrieved masses. It is this type of affront on the masses that is described by the Adébo Commission that looked into wage levels of the workers in 1970 as

quoted by (Isichei 1983:443)

- - - it is clear not only that there is intolerable suffering at the bottom of the income scale, because of the rise in the cost of living, but also that the suffering is made even more intolerable by manifestations of affluence and wasteful expenditure which cannot be explained on the basis of visible and legitimate means of income.

Finally, the language of the poet and the method he uses to deal with the actors at the social party is military in nature. The use of 'ibon' (gun), 'àgbá' (mortar) is very apt; both 'ibon' and àgbá are military weapons. So also is the use of òpáláábá (broken bottles) and 'ipón' (blood) are elements of war associated with the military era. Even though this excerpt, according to the poet, is a dream, his posture is a direct attack on the socio-economic policy of the military government and the wasteful expenditure characteristic of the military era.

The Dream-vision technique in poetry used by Ọláàpọ̀ in the poem we have just examined, can be traced

to the Medieval English Poetry, "The Dream of the Road" and others. It is characterised by a world where anything and everything is possible, structural illogicality, and it is allegorical (satirical). The poet employs the Dream-vision technique for some reasons. It is a means by which the poet makes a public comment on rather explosive issues without any threat to his personal security. In other words, it is a tool for self-defence. Since nobody has control over his/her dream, it is impossible to arrest anyone for narrating his dream.

This technique is evident in Qladapọ's poem, 'Alá Ináwó' (Dream about a Social party);

Lọjọ Tẹmẹdùn fẹ ẹlẹ
 Ó há mọtò, ó há dẹrẹbà
 Ohun o rí a bùn'yàn lọjọ òní

- - -

Niyá bá kúkú nńá 'wẹẹ ikólẹ ká -
 Lòún bá nńálẹ alájà méjí

(Qladapọ, 1975:105)

The day Tèmèdùn wanted to open his new building formally

He distributed motor cars and drivers to his guests as sourvenir

Whatever you wish you may distribute to your guests today

- - -

And so the old woman started distributing building plans

She was distributing two storey buildings

Distributing motor cars plus the drivers and distributing two-storey buildings to hundreds of guests at a party sound unimaginable in real life. It is an exaggeration of the custom that is rampat in the society where people distribute different items as sourvenir of the occasion they are celebrating.

This phenomenon reached an alarming stage during the military era in the 1974-79 decade. The irony of it is that the military was also involved. The poet says:

- - -
 Níbi olówó méji gbe ntaákà

- - -
 Ọgá ọ́jǎ, ọ́gá ọ́lọpàá
 La jọ́ nmutí níbi àjọyọ́
 (Ọladapọ, 1975:104)

- - -
 Where two rich people were competing

- - -
 Top military officers and police officers
 Were dining and wining with us at the
 party.

Ordinarily, Ọládàpọ́ would have suffered for revealing the presence of the military at such a gathering if it were not for the dream-vision technique used. Such public comment would have attracted a heavy punishment from the military. As it was pointed out earlier in our analysis, Ọladapọ́'s dream is a satire of what was going on in the society. He has successfully used the Dream-vision technique to send out his message.

Fálétí's poem, 'Gbajúmọ́ Ọde Ọní' (Famous people of Today) also reveals more of the social vices that are rampant in the society in the last decade 1980-89, of

our study period. He says:

- - -

Gbogbo akéwí, ẹ̀ tètè sètò
 Kí n tètè jẹ̀ gbajúmò, nílẹ̀ yíí
 Mo fẹ̀ máa bá wọ̀n nàwó bọ̀lugi lágbo
 Ọ̀rò náá n dún mí
 Mo fẹ̀ jẹ̀ gbajúmò - n̄ ò mọ̀nà

- - -

Ọ̀látúbòsún, Àrẹ̀mú
 Mo fẹ̀ jẹ̀ gbajúmò, Fálétí ò mọ̀nà.
 (Fálétí in Ọ̀látúnjì 1982c:63).

All poets, quickly set out the plan
 So that I could quickly become famous in
 this country
 I want to join them in spending illicit
 money at parties
 The matter is worrying me
 I want to be famous, I don't know how to
 come about it

- - -

Ọ̀látúbòsún, Àrẹ̀mú
 I want to be famous, Fálétí is a novice.

In this excerpt, Fálétí touches on the vices that plagued the Nigeria society in the seventies and eighties particularly the dubious ways people acquired wealth by all means. He compares what we now regard as

affluence and wealth with those of yester-years. He concludes with his preference for the fame of those days.

The present situation is depicted by the poet in these lines

Béniyàn bá fẹ́ jẹ́ gbajúmọ̀ nílẹ̀ yíí

Wọ̀n á wọ̀nú ẹ̀gbẹ́

Wọ̀n á dí gbọ̀mọ̀gbọ̀mọ̀

Wọ̀n á donífàyàwọ̀

Wọ̀n á di dánàdánà

Bí gbajúmọ̀ iwòyí fojú ọ̀sán ẹ̀niyàn

Bó wù wọ̀n, wọ̀n á solè bó dòru

Bí wọ̀n fẹ́ ní láárí dóríí gónḡó

Wọ̀n á fọ̀mọ̀ ọ̀lọ̀mọ̀ ẹ̀nṣẹ́.

When people want to be famous in this country
 They join secret cults
 They become kidnappers
 They become smugglers
 They become armed robbers
 If the famous people of today show up
 as responsible people during the day
 If they wish, they become robbers by night
 If they wish to be extremely rich
 They use other people's children to make
 money-making-sosp.

The desire of the Yorùbá to acquire money by all means is depicted in the excerpt above. It is the general belief of most African societies that one could use 'jùju' (West African Charm) to make money. A recent example is the eyes of a lady that were removed alive in Lagos, Nigeria to make money last month, that is, October, 1997. As we pointed out earlier, the economy of Nigeria since the beginning of the eighties have been very poor. There has been a high rate of unemployment. This has affected all sectors of the economy. But the rich who want to maintain their class in the society resort to those vices mentioned in the excerpt above.

Having succeeded in becoming famous, these rich people spend lavishly in a way that would make their source of acquiring such money questionable. This is how Fálétí puts it :

Gbajúmọ iwòyí, kò dà bíi gbajúmọ tàná-
 Gbajúmọ iwòyí, wọn n ẹ kísà lówùjọ- igi dá ni
 Bí wọn fẹ fowó yẹnisí
 Wọn a di abá owó rumọ wájú agbo
 Wọn á máa wá gbọn bebà kálẹ wẹrẹrẹẹ
 Bí iràwé bọ lulẹ lẹrùn

Ọ̀tò nímọ̀rí onílù láyàbá, ọ̀tò ní tẹ̀ni ń ẹ̀bọ
 Bí wọ̀n fowó mọ̀ni níwájú tán, wọ̀n á fowó

mọ̀gi imú ẹ̀ni

Wọ̀n á mọ̀pàkọ

Wọ̀n á mọ̀dẹ̀tí

Wọ̀n á mọ̀bàdí

Wọ̀n a sí tún mọ̀ni ní bẹ̀bà nígbà àyà

Owóo bẹ̀bà ń gbọ̀n wẹ̀rẹ̀.

(Fálétí in Ọ̀látúnjì 1982c:63-64).

The famous people of today are not like those of
 yester-years

The famous people of today perform incredible
 acts in the society, it is beyond
 description

When they want to honour someone with money

They would employ a boy to carry bails of
 currency notes to the party

They would spray currency notes all about

Like dry leaves in the dry season

The money for the artists is different, that of
 the celebrant is different

After pasting money on one's fore-head, they
 would paste on the person's nose

They would paste money on the back of the head

They would paste money on the buttocks

They also paste currency notes on one's chest

Currency notes are sprayed all about.

This account of what is depicted above is not common in the yester-years as shown in the excerpt above. That was in the fifties and sixties when the society was relatively disciplined in money - spending. Honesty was their watch-word then. It was from their hard-earned money that they would spend. Therefore, they were prudent in their spending.

The spraying of currency notes on other parts of the body besides the fore-head is a further evidence of squander. The poet's use of short sentences of identical structure, N. + V + N (Noun + Verb + Noun) in

Wọn á mọ̀pàkọ̀

Wọn á mọ̀dètí

Wọn á mọ̀bàdí

shows the poet's disdain for the practice. It is a mockery to condemn the society's practice of ridiculous waste.

The use of ebo (sacrifice) in the excerpt is a further testimony of the poet's closeness to his society. He says,

Ọ̀tọ̀ nímọ̀rí onílù láyàbá, ọ̀tọ̀ ní tẹ̀nì tí á ẹ̀bọ̀

The spraying of money on the artist is different that of celebrant is different.

'Sebo' is to perform rituals. But its use has become an acceptable terminology for parties in the Yorùbá society. The use of ebo for parties began in the sixties when throwing of parties became increasingly common with the people.

The whole excerpt is a reflection of the society. The poet's reaction is shown in his resentment of the craze for money. Fálétí belongs to the new social order. Fálétí is one of the educated elite. He is a University graduate of long standing and an accomplished administrator. The educated elite would not like to be associated with these vices no matter the condition of their social states.

Adébí sí Thompson, another poet under study is very critical of the unpatriotic attitude of the Nigerian leaders who stock their ill-gotten money into foreign accounts. In her poem, 'Ìlú Le' (The Country is Hard), she says:

Owó epo á bẹ ní bǎńkí ilú òkèèrè
 Owó ọmọ ilẹ̀ yíí yarọ sínú bǎńkí òyínbó
 Ẹ ba mi forí tálákà bẹ wọn
 Kí àwọn alágbára dákun dábọ
 Ẹ ba ni forí mèkúnnù ẹ̀pẹ̀ fún wọn
 Kí wọn dákun kó owó ilú yíí padà

Kí ohun gbogbo le dèrò.

(Thompson in Qlabimtan 1988:128).

The proceeds from petroleum products is stocked
in foreign banks

The country's money is too much in
European banks

Help beg them for the poor people's sake

Let the powers-that-be show mercy

Help beg them for the masses' sake

That they bring back the country's money

So as to alleviate the people's sufferings.

The point the poet is making is that the economy of
the nation was ruined by the inordinate ambition of
those in power.

She then goes on to elaborate on how the masses
suffer. She says:

Gbogbo ohun ẹnu n jẹ ló dawaàrì

Gbogbo wọn ló di gòólù tó wọn bí ojù

Garawa gààrì di náìrà méjílá

Gààrì kúrò lóúnjẹ tálákà ó di tolówó

Tálákà tó jẹ búrẹdì

Awọ orí ẹ ló n jẹ tí ò mọ.

Everything edible became scarce

Everything became gold that is costly like an eye

A tin of gààrí rose to twelve naira
 Gààrí was no longer for the poor, it became
 the rich man's food
 The poor that eats bread
 It is the skin of his head that he is
 eating unknowingly.

In the excerpt above, Thompson criticises how the prices of foodstuff rise everyday particularly gààrí. Before 1988, gààrí was about the cheapest of all Nigerian foodstuffs. It was the most easily available food and it was widely known among the Yorùbá as the 'oúnjẹ mẹkúnnù' (masses food). Gààrí could be easily prepared from the cassava tuber. After its production, it can be made into eba or soaked in water for immediate consumption. So, it was an easy source of food for the masses. But suddenly after the collapse of the Nigerian economy in the early eighties, gààrí went out of the reach of the masses. It is this that Thompson refers to in the excerpt above.

Adebisi Thompson is the only woman poet in our work. Her feminine touch runs through her poetry. In the Yorùbá culture, it is the woman that handles the purchase of the food items mentioned in the excerpt above. It is evident

that Thompson, being a woman, is familiar with the price of each item. Her use of language depicts the characteristics of a woman. Women are noted for their soft and persuasive language as found in:

È ba mi forí tálákà bẹ wọn
 Kí àwọn alágbára dákun, dábò
 È bá mi forí mẹkúunù şípẹ fun wọn
 Kí wọn dákun kó owó ìlú yíí padà.

Help us beg them for the sake of the poor
 Let the power that be show mercy
 Help us beg them for the sake of the masses
 That they should bring back the country's
 money

This is a feminine way of settling a knotty matter. Unlike her male counterparts, her soft utterances do not suggest any punishment for those saboteurs of the Nigeria economy. Nevertheless, Thompson has succeeded in exposing those who enriched themselves through their corrupt practices. Her posture is a total rejection of these vices.

Our last discussion before we close this chapter is on some social virtues which touch on the unity of Nigeria. Babalọlá, in his poem, 'Òşómàáló Şe bẹbẹ' (Òşómàáló performed Wonders), says :

- - -

"Òşómàáló lẹ fẹ fọmọ yín fún?

Ìjẹşà - Oníjẹşà

Ó şòwò şòwò ní'lùú wa tán

Ẹ tún wáá fẹẹ faya şèni fún un

- - -

(Babalọlá 1989:12).

It is Òşómàáló that you want to give your daughter to as wife?

A mere Ìjẹşà

After trading for a long time in our town

You again want to give him your daughter as a makeweight.

Babalọlá grew up in the Yorùbá traditional society of the fifties and sixties which abhorred marrying from outside one's village. The society had reason for this. According to Fadipe (1970:71) there is the intricacy of

setting discreet inquiries on foot for the purpose of making sure that there was no hereditary

diseases in the kindred of father or mother.

This presupposes that either parents reside in the same town. Though it is not a rule, but a Yorùbá societal practice. It is this age-long practice that the poet is reacting against.

The Àgbìgbò townspeople in the text want to maintain the status quo. They therefore criticize the Headwoman for giving her daughter in marriage to a 'nere' 'Òṣómàáló'¹

The response of those who are in support of giving the Headwoman's daughter to Òṣómàáló as wife is significant to our analysis. They reacted thus :

- - -

Ìjẹ̀ṣà ni, kíí ṣọmọ Àgbìgbò

- - -

1. Òṣómàáló is the name given to the Ijẹ̀ṣa who went from village to village in the recent past selling clothes. It was a common phenomenon in the fifties and sixties. Òṣómàáló is the nickname for Ijẹ̀ṣa traders, that is 'Òṣó ni maa ló gbowó mi.' This means "I will not get up from where I squat down until I collect my money. Usually they would not sit down at all.

Ṣùgbón ọmọlúàbí ní

Ọmọ Oduduwa ní

Ọmọ Nàìjíríà ní.

He is an Ìjẹṣà, he is not from Àgbìgbò
- - -

But he is of good character

He is a descendant of Oduduwa

He is a Nigerian.

The Yorùbá traditional society cherishes an ọmọlúàbí and this was a recognised qualification that earned Òṣómàáló the support of his admirers to marry Araoti. Two characteristic qualities of ọmọlúàbí evoked in the poem are hardwork and wealth through honest means.

For example, he says :

Èní tó wù wá l'a ó fún-ún ní aya

Òṣómàáló onípètẹ̀ẹ̀si

Baba Adégbéngá.

Whoever pleases us is the one we would
give a wife

Òṣómàáló, owner of the storey-building

Father of Adegbenga

By the time Babalọlá wrote this poem, that is, 1964, by all standard, whoever could afford to build a storey-building, was regarded as a wealthy person. The poet again says of the Òṣómàáló,

Baálé ilé tó tó baáléé ẹ
 Ó dọlọrọ l'Ágbigbò
 Nípa iṣé àṣekára ní.

A family head that is worthy of being a
 family head

He became rich in Agbigbo
 Through hardwork.

All these credentials earn the Òṣómàáló the qualification of an omolúàbí.

That the Òṣómàáló is an Ìjẹṣà is insignificant but rather his being a son of Oduduwa and more importantly a Nigerian is the concern of the poet. The poet is patriotic in his quest to foster national unity. No matter the Òṣómàáló's ethnic group, what is paramount is that he is a Nigerian and as a Nigerian, as far as the poet is concerned, he is qualified to marry from any part of the country.

This excerpt is a reflection of what was going on in Nigeria in the fifties and sixties. The Igbo would not like to give their daughters to either Yorùbá or Hausa and vice versa. The poet himself is a Yorùbá and he was aware of the Yorùbá traditional society's scepticism about inter-tribal marriage in Nigeria. He therefore uses this case of the Òṣómàáló to reject this system of tribal discrimination in marriage.

The poet also succinctly expresses another traditional quality that qualifies the Òṣémááló to have the hands of the Headman's daughter in marriage. The Òṣémááló has three wives, Mopélólá, Fèhintólá and Ketólání. Polygamy is socially approved by the Yorùbá society. It is a mark of prestige and hardwork. The poet capitalises on this traditional quality to support the Òṣémááló's candidature as the husband of Àràòtí, therefore supporting polygamy indirectly.

The poet, in his poem, has successfully shown that a work of art has links with various aspects of the society that produces it. His cultural background, his personality and the ideology of his society, all have influence on his poem.

The social vices that we have just examined in this chapter, have contributed to the collapse of the Nigeria economy. The capitalist economy of Nigeria is an influence on the social structure of the society. It encourages the ever-increasing quest for the pursuit of wealth which consequently leads to the concern for money. The poets have exposed the culprits, they are the politicians and the civil servants working in government offices. It is the responsibility

of the various governments to curb the excesses of those involved in the sabotage of the economy.

..... This malicious destruction of the economy became very evident in the post-independence Nigeria as revealed by the poets under study. Comments on such social vices are therefore not common in the works of the pre-independence Yorùbá poets.

But at the same time, the poets also highlight some social virtues in their poems. *Ọdúnjọ* (1949) and *Şówùnmi* (1952) emphasise the importance of hard-work while *Babalọlá* (1989) shows how hardwork and honesty are rewarded in the poem he gave as illustration. His submission lends credence to these social virtues.

CHAPTER FIVE

METAPHYSICAL AND PHILOSOPHICAL TOPICALITY

5.0 Introduction

The term metaphysical is used in this work to describe the poets who write on topics that deal with general abstract reasoning, whether on animate or inanimate objects. These also include the poems that are absorbed in thoughts of death and religious devotion. By their nature, both metaphysical and philosophical poems are interwoven. The metaphysical poets engage in high level philosophical thought using nature and religion as part of their focus.

According to Ogunpitan (1999:20), the term metaphysical was coined by Samuel Johnson in the 18th century in his book Life of Cowley to describe the poetry of John Donne, George Herbert, and others of the 17th century who wrote in a similar style. Ogunpitan explains that these poets used their intellectual ingenuity and fanciful notions expressed through elaborate analogues. He further points out that these analogues always point to striking parallels between two seemingly dissimilar things. This is also applicable

to works of our poets under consideration.

Man, including Yorùbá, is guided and motivated by an uneasiness about what the world they live in is all about. He is concerned with the causes of specific events in his life such as untimely death and more importantly the occurrence of happenings that cannot be explained within the sphere of human knowledge. This has been the concern of man down the ages and it is in an attempt to unravel this fear that philosophy was born.

Efforts have been made by several great Greek philosophers to offer explanations to the mysteries of the world. For instance, Thales was the first Greek philosopher to explain the eclipse of the sun and the moon, while Anaximander gave the size and shape of Earth, the sun and the moon (Allen 1966). Others such as Socrates, Plato and Aristotle also contributed to finding why things were as they were.

There are other aspects of human life that are beyond human comprehension. To the

Yorùbá, their philosophy is entrenched in their daily sayings, that is, their proverbs, idioms and so on. But the core of their philosophy is their belief in Olodumare, destiny, human character and creation.

The Yorùbá acknowledge the supremacy of God over all things both living and non-living, both on Earth and in Heaven. They therefore put their thought in Him. The Yorùbá depend on Him for everything.

The Yorùbá also have absolute confidence in destiny. They believe that it is destiny that makes one succeed or otherwise in life. Abimbola (1976:151) corroborates this;

- - - the Yorùbá believe that those who have chosen good destinies and are aided by the supernatural powers will, if they work hard, become successful in life - - -

Such is the Yorùbá belief in destiny that they have come to accept whatever is their lot.

Another aspect of Yorùbá philosophy is the emphasis they put on good character. Whatever one might become in life, without good character, one is not complete.

A Yorùbá aphorism confirms this:

Ká mú rǎgbá, ká fi ta rǎgbá

Ìwà, ìwà là n wá, ìwà

Ká mú rǎgbà ká fi ta rǎgbà

Ìwà, ìwà là n wá, ìwà

Ká mú rǎgbá ká fi tàkúta

Ìwà, ìwà là n wá, ìwà.

Whatever one does

Character, it is character that matters,
character

Whatever one achieves

Character, it is character that matters,
character

Whatever one becomes in life

Character, it is character that matters,
character.

The Yorùbá believe it is good character that makes one live a good meaningful life. Awóniyì in Abímbólá (1975:364) has this to say :

Good character, in the Yorùbá sense includes respect for old age, loyalty to one's parents and local traditions, honesty in all public and private dealings, devotion to duty, readiness to assist the needy and the infirm, sympathy,

sociability, courage, and itching desire for work and many other desirable qualities.

Thus, under metaphysical and philosophical theme, we would discuss Religion, Animate and Inanimate objects.

5.1 Religious Theme

Ṣówùnmí (1952)¹ was very popular with his religious writings in his poetry. His poetry is not significantly different from those of the early poets, both in content and form. His poems are essentially didactic with Christian overtones. He begins each of his poems with a verse from the Bible and also incorporates Christian songs and traditional songs in between the poems. In his poem 'Ọ̀rò Ịṣítí Fún Ịkèrèkú' (Words of Advice For Ịkèrèkú), he characteristically opens with a Bible verse,

Sọ fún àwọn Israel kí nwọ́n kí ó tẹ

àtẹ̀síwájú.

Eks. Orí 14 ẹsẹ 15.

(Ṣówùnmí 1952:8).

¹ See the Appendix

Speak unto the Children of Israel, that
they go forward.

(Exodus, Chapter 14 verse 15)

He then goes on to give his words of advice to the
Ìkèrèkú people. He says,

Ọmọ nyin nṣe lóyà wọn ọba isẹgùn

Iyi wa burú n'nu rẹ nka wi ẹ na

Ṣọṣi Ìkèrèkú dára to'yi

Tawa (Tower) kò nágogo ó ọ́ábùkù

Ọba yi ko nàdé lórí

Àti Tawa yi kò nágogo ọgbọgbà.

(Ṣówùnmi 1952:9).

Your sons and daughters are lawyers and
obtain degrees in medicine

Will I not tell you the deficiency in it

The church at Ìkèrèkú is as good as this

Its tower has no bell, it is a disgrace

An Ọba without a crown

And the tower that has no bell are the same.

The imagery in this text lies in the last two lines.

In Yorùbá society, not every Ọba wears a crown and an

Ọba without a crown is not recognised as paramount.

This shows how important the crown is to an Ọba. By

comparing a church tower that has no bell to an Ọba who has no crown, the poet has shown the significance of a bell to a tower.

Furthermore, the reference to children of Ịkèrèkú as lawyers and doctors is a pointer to the growing elitism and materialism in the society. At the period of writing, travelling overseas in search of the golden fleece was the vogue and the people of Abeokuta, Ijebu and Lagos were in the forefront in the acquisition of Western Education. In the pre-independence Yorùbá society, the attainment of western education was a mark of social distinction and economic elevation. It was a pride of many parents and communities to have sons and daughters who qualified as lawyers and doctors. Attainment of degrees in medicine and law, presupposes lucrative jobs which would lead to financial and material wealth.

Thus if Ịkèrèkú Community could boast of eminent doctors and lawyers, they are a rich Community, not only academically but also financially and materially. How then could such a Community build a church which had a tower without a bell? To Ọsówúnmí, it was simply disgraceful. Moreover, the focus on church

building with towers is an indication of prominence. It shows the growing influence of Western architecture in the society which was positively inspiring the Christian Community to improve the quality and beauty of their church buildings.

The poet then goes further to expose the Ìkèrèkú Community's low level of Christianity which may possibly be responsible for the lukeworm attitude in purchasing a jingle bell for the church.

Igbi Igbein ndáwó sòòṣì

A ndáwó ẹbọ, ó mà pọ kẹ o -

Ọdún egúngún à dàbí Kérésì lójú ọmọ òkùnkùn.

When Igbein people were contributing towards
building a church

We were contributing towards making sacrifice,
this is unedifying

Egúngún festival would look like Christmas to
the unbelievers.

The import of Ṣówùnmí's message becomes clearer if we bear in mind Scholes' (1974:1) notion that "writer's work cannot be treated in isolation". To understand the implication of Ṣówùnmí's poetry therefore, we must understand his relationship with his society. He was a member of his society and his point of view does not

exist in isolation. He is not from Ikereku but he acknowledges Ikereku as his benefactor. He says,

Emi Ọṣọ ko ma sàròfò kí nḡbagbe olóore
Ó mà tí kẹ o

È ko dẹ bí mí lébi ipotiṣe i

Òkè-ọ̀nà re mo ti nḡogbọn a ti tọwọ̀ bẹnu

Ibẹ re mo kọ ẹ tísà anọmọ-jẹun alùlùtà.

I, Ọṣọ will not write poetry and forget
my benefactor

It cannot be so

Why not ask from me why it is so

It is at Òkè-ọ̀nà that I am managing to earn
my living

It is there I first worked as a teacher as one
who beat the pupils to earn his
living and entertain the people
with the drum for a reward.

Before Christianity came to Ègbáland, Ọ̀wùnmí's society was dominated by the traditional religion. When Christianity came, it was not easy to convert the unbelievers because of the people's lets-wait-and-see attitude. The people found it difficult to change from their old ways of worship. Before the advent of Christianity, the traditional festivals, including Egúngún were always celebrated elaborately. Farmers

came home from their farms to join the townspeople to celebrate Egúngún Festival. But from time immemorial, Christmas has always been celebrated with fun-fare. The crux of the matter is that while other areas such as Aké, Igbein and Ikereku were building their churches, Itoko¹ was relishing in idolatry.

By the time Şówùnmí was writing, Christianity was still spreading and to the christians the unbelievers are 'omọ òkùnkùn,' literally (children of darkness). That was the language of Şówùnmí's society by that time. This is in consonance with the message of the church hymn quoted by Şówùnmí,

ORIN : YHB 136

Okun bolẹ síbẹ

Ní ilẹ Kẹfẹrí

Dide 'Ràwọ orọ

Dide, ma ẹ wọ mọ.

HYMN : MHB 811

O'er heathen lands afar

Thick darkness broodeth yet !

Arise, O morning star,

Arise, and never set.

1. All these areas, Ake, Igbein, Ikereku and Itoko are different areas in Abeokuta with their separate Obas.

Christians generally believe that whoever does not accept Jesus is in darkness : Jesus is the 'Light' and also the 'Morning Star.' The lukeworm attitude of some parts of Abeokuta towards Christianity might have made him use this Church hymn, M.H.B. 811. It is true that inserted songs and hymns may not do any damage if removed. However, there is no doubt that the incorporated hymns and songs have some psychological effect on the society. The only defect we notice is the monotony the incorporated songs might have on the audience.

Finally, Şówùnmí's writings were under the political dispensation of the Colonialists and Şówùnmí himself was a product of the Mission School. The atmosphere was therefore very conducive for his type of poetry, evangelization.

Şówùnmí also treats some philosophical issues that probe into the uncertainty of man's abode in the world. In 'Ìgbésí Aiye Èdá' (Man's Sojourn on Earth). Şówùnmí, in his stereo-typed way of preservation, opens the poem with a quotation from the Bible,

"Ènití ó bá şégun yio jogún ohun gbogbo"
Ìfihàn, 21 ẹşẹ 7.

He that overcometh shall inherit all things
Revelation 21, verse 7.

before going into the body of his message. He says :

Nínú oyún wunre a ti bẹ̀rẹ̀ itiyà

Ìgbésí aiye ẹ̀dá ẹ̀kiki ẹ̀tiri àti jòngbòn

Bó o lówó 'wa gbòtá dede

- - -

Bó o kò dẹ̀ n'ówó wa dẹ̀ni àbùkù.

(Şówùnmi 1952:13).

It is from the womb that we start suffering

Man's life is full of trouble and worry

If you are rich, you will have enemies here
and there

And even if you don't have anything, they will
castigate you.

This text above is a depiction of the Yorùbá thought
that says :

Kò sẹ̀ni tó lè taiye lórùn

No one can please the world.

The Yorùbá reaction to this is that since one cannot
satisfy mankind, then one should leave everything to
God. In presenting this Yorùbá worldview, consciously
or otherwise, Şówùnmi is in acceptance of the principles

of the colonial ruling class. Sówùnmi's relationship with his society is conformist.

5.2 Animate and Inanimate Objects

It is not only in human behaviour or action that the poet explains Yorùbá philosophy, he uses non-human objects, both animate and inanimate.

5.2.1 Animate Objects

Atiládé (1961) uses the animal world to reflect on Yorùbá philosophy. In his poem, 'Ànikànjẹ̀ Ìjímèrè' (Lonely Brown Monkey), Atiládé explains the Yorùbá way of life of living together:

Kíni o ń ẹ̀ nígà igò igi
 Ànikànjẹ̀ Ìjímèrè?
 Èni tó nìkàn wà
 Dàbí ẹ̀nití kò sí láiyé rárá;
 Nítorí ohunkóhun tó bá a
 Ó bá a ni on nìkan soṣo
 Láí lólùmòràn, láí lólùràn-lọ̀wọ̀.

(Atiládé 1961:33).

What are you doing in the hollow of the tree?
 Lonely Brown Monkey?
 He who isolates himself

Is like someone who is dead
 Because whatever befalls him
 It is he alone that will bear the
 consequence
 Without a confidant, without a helper.

This is an expression of surprise of the poet's observation on the animal world. To see a patagnenon monkey sitting down alone is abnormality because, from the observation of the Yorùbá these animals move in a herd. It is risky for the monkey to be alone and it can spell its doom as the poet warns,

Nítorí ohunkóhun tó bá dé bá a
 Ó bá a ni on nìkan soṣo

Because whatever befalls him
 It is he alone that will bear the consequence.

The brown monkey family cherishes its safety so much that it has a mechanism for its protection. One of the monkeys always acts as an alóre (outpost/lookout) when they are preying on a farmer's crops. It climbs to the top of the tallest tree in the area of the forest watching out in order to be able to warn the others about any imminent danger in the person of the farmer or a hunter (Ọlátúnjí 1982a:19). This observation is culturally bound. The message of the poet in his

usage of metaphorical analogy of the animal world is brought out more vividly in the second stanza :

Kíni o nṣe nígà'gò igi

Anìkànje Ìjímèrè?

Eni tí kò ni aláré ti o le ba síré,

Tí kò láláwàdà to le ba jèwò pò

Níjò tòḍe ba mbò t'on tàdá àti kùmò

Pèlú ibon ọlọta àtètù, iná ọmọ ọrara

Tani yio tè ọ lésè péwa dé?

What are you doing in the hollow of the tree?

Lonley Brown Monkey?

He who has no playmate to play with,

That has no friend to joke with

The day the hunter is coming with his cutlass

and cudgel

Plus his loaded gun, ready to fire

Who will hint you of the impending danger?

This stanza further reinforces the need for an alóre (outpost) whose assignment is to alert others of any danger. It is not only in the animal world that there is need for them to stay together to avoid the uncomfortable repercussion of being alone, it is also relevant to the human beings. The concluding stanza of the poem is more explicit about the poet's message :

Eni tí kò lẹni ó lè gbálẹ́ fún un
 Lọjọ́ ogbó bá wọlé dé :

Eni tí kò lẹnitó le gbẹlẹ́ fún un
 Lọjọ́ ikú ba tẹsẹ́ bọ ọdẹdẹ́ :

A dẹran gúnnugún àti tàkàlà ráúrúú

One who has no one to take care of the house
 for him

When one grows old

One who has no one to dig his grave

When death comes

Will be consumed by the vulture and the bird
 ground horn bill.

The text above reinforces the Yorùbá saying

Orí mi má jẹ́ n ẹ̀nikẹ̀ngbẹ́

God forbid that I should live alone.

This is the Yorùbá philosophy the poet is driving at. Africa in general and the Yorùbá in particular believe in being one's brother's keeper. They believe it is only a person that has human relation problem that isolates himself.

The whole poem sounds like a sermon and this can be attributed to the background of the poet. He was a

teacher but he was also a priest.¹ He reflects on the Yorùbá society of his time and enumerates the danger inherent in staying alone. He uses the animal world only as an illustration to reflect on the Yorùbá worldview of communality.

As mentioned earlier, the Yorùbá are a race that cherishes communal living. According to Mábògùnjé (1962) in Yorùbáland, large urban agglomerations predated the advent of Europeans. It is this system that the poet is making case for its sustenance. His observation is not just philosophical but also political. The time he wrote this poem was immediate post-independence period when the colonial masters had just quit the Nigeria political scene. The poet is stressing the need for unity. To him, all hands must be on deck. With the exit of the colonialists, the poet uses the need for Nigerians to come together to move the country forward. To achieve this, the poet recommends the Yorùbá system of communalism.

1. Atiládé retired as an Archbishop of the Baptist Gospel Church Organisation in Lagos.

The blending of Yorùbá traditional belief with Christian language shows Atiládé as a liberal poet. He acknowledges the efficacy of Yorùbá traditional medicine in curing some ailment. This posture is depicted in :

Enití ko lénitó le-wa'gbò àgúnmu
 Lọjọ'nu rírun bá wọlé wa
 Tí kò lénitó le jáwé àgbo
 Lọjọ akọ ibà bá yà kàn'lẹkùn

(Atiládé 1961:34).

One who has no one to prepare herbal powder
 On the day he would have stomach ache
 And does not have anyone to prepare concoction
 On the day he would have high fever.

The use of àgúnmu and àgbo to cure illness was very popular in the fifties in Yorùbáland. It is still used by Yorùbá traditional society. The poet is seen as playing double role in this text effectively as he incorporates a Bible verse side by side with his support for the Yorùbá traditional use of herbs. The phrase, ikekùn àwọn peiyepiye (the snare of the fowler) is taken from Psalm 91, verse 3. This effective handling of Yorùbá culture and Christian belief depicts Atiládé as a traditionalist and a religionist. His religious

belief does not stop him from propagating the Yorùbá traditional culture. Both have some influence on his poetry.

In his use of language, Atiládé employs personification effectively in this poem as he continuously asks the monkey :

Kíni o nṣe níga'gò'gi

Ànikànjẹ Ìjímèrè?

What are you doing in the hollow of the tree
Lonely Brown Monkey?

as if it is a human being that is expected to answer. The poet even continues to give the monkey reasons why it should not continue to stay alone. By so doing the poet uses the animal world to exemplify the advantages of communal living. Apart from the main central figure, "Ìjímèrè" that is personified, *ogbó* (old age) and "ikú" (Death) are also personified as capable of having mobility in :

Lọjọ ogbó bá wọlé dé

Lọjọ ikú ba tẹsẹ bọ ọdèdè

When one grows old

When death comes.

These expressions keep the poem moving.

Finally, Atiládé has shown in this poem that the Yorùbá are very close to nature. This has enabled them to give human attribute to objects and creatures of nature, who are made to express various feelings characteristic of human beings. The personified Brown Monkey reflects what is going on in the society.

Awé (1989) is another poet that uses the animal world to express Yorùbá philosophy. In 'Alákàn yíí Sòra - - -' (This crab behave - - -) he says :

Omi kan n bẹ lábúlé wa
Kíí ṣodò nlá téyàn ti le lúwẹ́

- - -
Àmọ̀ alákàn-kán wà níbẹ̀,
Aláfojúdí ẹ̀dá ni.

There is a river in our village
It is not a river big enough for swimming

- - -
But there is one crab in it
It is impertinent.

In the poem, Awé narrates his several encounters with a crab that lives in a rivulet that passes through their cottage. Because he failed on several occasions to capture the crab, Awé resulted to raining abuses

The two lines suggest a prayer for success of the poet, that is, he would succeed as the crab succeeds in its oil-making. The line, 'Àṣeyè lalákàn í sepo'¹ literally means, the crab always accomplishes its task of making palm-oil. The supposed palm-oil allegedly prepared by the crab is the reddish oil-like substance usually found at the entrance of the hole where the crab uses as its 'home.' The continuous maintenance of the oil-like substance in the crab's hole is an evidence of success ascribed to the crab's hardwork.

The second Yorùbá philosophical saying found in the text above is

Eja ni àbí akàn?

Is it fish or crab?

The answer to this question is not based on the actual element demanded. The answer is found in the cultural convention of the Yorùbá. For instance, if the answer

1. Though the Yorùbá recognise the production of the 'palm-oil' by the crab, nevertheless, they do not accept it (oil) as beneficial to mankind. It is from this unacceptability of the 'oil' that another Yorùbá incantatory assertion emanates :

Kò sèni tíí fi epo alákan sebè

No one uses the palm-oil prepared by the crab for soup.

to this question is Eja (fish) it means the message or what one desires is unfavourable but if it is akàn (crab) it is favourable. It is symbolic. Fish is very difficult to catch by hand because it swims fast and it is slippery. Also, it lives in the deeps of the water. It can only be caught with either the hook or the net. On the other hand, crab is relatively easy to catch, because it is slow and could be easily and safely handled by its pincers. By interpretation, eja (fish) is not 'pleasant' (because it is difficult to capture) while akàn (crab) is very 'pleasant' (it is made easier to subdue). The poet refuses the intended meanings of these two creatures, eja and akàn and instead decides to play on their interpretations. This deliberate twisting of meanings is punning. The effect of the pun on the whole text is to create humour.

In another poem, 'iṣẹ́ Ọlórún pọ́' (God's work is Great), Awé shows his appreciation of the different animals created by God :

Erin tí ń bẹ nínú igbó réré
 Èfòn tí ń bẹ lódàn abijà wàrà
 Kinniún olóólà ijù
 Àwọn ẹdun agorí-igi référéfé

Ọ̀rẹ́ Táyé-lolú Èjiré

Iṣẹ́ Ọlórún ní

Iṣẹ́ rẹ̀ pọ̀.

(Awé 1989:26).

The elephant that lives far in the thick
forest

The bushcow that lives in the grassland

The lion, the cutter of tribal marks in the
forest

The colobus monkey that climbs to the apex
of the tallest tree

The friend of Táyé-lolú Èjiré

It is the creation of God

His work is wonderful.

Ọ̀rẹ́ Táyé-lolú Èjiré in the excerpt is a symbolism. Táyé-lolú Èjiré refers to twins in Yorùbá and the colobus monkeys are always seen together in twos like twins. There is therefore a semantic relationship of the number two between Táyé-lolú and "Èdun" (Colobus Monkey).

Like Atiládé that we have just examined, Awé also addresses a 'crab' as a human being in his poem. He reveals that :

Alákàn yí a gbéwù àibikítà wò

(p. 35).

This crab will look contemptuously.

That the "alákàn," (Crab) put on a garment is a personification. And in 'Iṣé Olórún Pò' (God's work is Wonderful), Awé again personifies "Òṣùpá" (Moon) when he asks;

Òṣùpá, ajá rẹ́ òkó?

Moon, where is your dog?

The poet asks a question from the moon as if the moon is a human. And in any case, the moon is not expected to have a dog. This makes the personification more concrete.

The poet's submission on all these non-human objects, like that of Atiládé (1961), is philosophical as he constantly reminds us that they are the handiwork of God who fends for them all. All the attributes of the different creatures mentioned by the poet are wonders of creation. The poet's religious background contributes to his appreciation of nature. Awé grew up under his devout christian parents and he himself ends up being a pastor. The trait of a pastor is very evident in his presentation and language in his

poems on nature. In all his submissions, God is exalted. Awé's discussion, to use Abimbola's (1976:195) words, "shows the high capacity of the Yorùbá for the appreciation of nature in all its aspects."

5.2.2 Inanimate Objects :

Apart from animals, birds, and insects non-human objects that are inanimate are also discussed by the poets under study to highlight Yorùbá philosophy. On this issue, we would examine Atiládé (1961), Fálétí (1964), Olabimtan (1969) and Awé (1989).

In his poem, 'Ìwà Òtítọ́' (Honest Character), Atiládé says,

Òtítọ́ níí tọ́ni s'ọ́lá
 Ìtànje ọkàn níí tanni sẹ̀wọ̀n;
 Bí a gbé òtítọ́ gun àgùtàn láro,
 Tí a sí gbé irọ́ gẹ̀şin
 Kí ó tó dí'rọ̀lẹ̀
 Nwọ̀n yio şe pàşípàrọ̀ ipò wọ̀n,
 Òtítọ́ dọ́jà ó kùtà,
 Lówó lówó l'a ñrèke;
 A s'òtítọ́ kò ní filà
 Èni ba ñpurọ̀
 Ni nwọ̀n ma ngbe gorí ẹşin

though bitter, leads one to honour. But how does the poet put across his message? He uses figurative expressions to show that Yorùbá philosophy is entrenched in their sayings. He says,

Bí a gbe òtító gun àgùtàn l'arọ

Tí a sí gbé irọ gẹsin

Kí ó tó dì'rọlẹ

Nwọn yio ẹe pàşipàrọ ipò wọn.

If deception mounts a sheep in the morning
And falsehood mounts a horse
Before the evening time
They would swop their positions.

This sums up the Yorùbá traditional belief on the futility of telling lies. Literally, the excerpt above means that, no matter how fast falsehood is disseminated, truth will still prevail. Àgùtàn (Sheep) is a slow sluggish animal. It can hardly run. Whereas, esin (horse) is known for its speed and power. It is a misnomer therefore for àgùtàn (sheep) to overtake esin (horse). But the intended message is the triumph of truth over falsehood.

The correct Yorùbá expression of this Yorùbá idiom is,

Ṣàgùn ọmọ kò láyọlé-

Eni ọmọ sin ló bímọ.

(Fálétí in OLÓKUN, 1964:12)

The bachelor is crying for want
of children

The barren is fasting to get children

The aged is crying to have children

But one should not rejoice over one's children

It is a man who is buried by his children
that has children.

In the Yorùbá culture, the desire to have children is to get someone that will bury one when one dies. So, it is only those who can accomplish this, that is, those who are actually buried by their children that are recognised as parents. Hence the Yorùbá saying :

Ọmọ kò láyọlé

Eni ọmọ sin ló bímọ

which means 'the end crowns the deed'.

Fálétí's support for this age-long culture is not in doubt as he piles up traditional Yorùbá burial rites performed on the dead by their children in the poem. For example, the use of adiẹ irànà¹ is a very

1. Adiẹ-irànà is a special hen used for rites to herald the corpse of a person that died on the farm back home.

important rite for the dead. The significance of these rites is evident in this Yorùbá saying,

Ká kú lómọ́dé kó yẹ ni

Ṣànjú ká dàgbà ka ma ladiẹ irànà lọ.

It is better to die a befitting death in the
flower of youth

Than to live long without the necessary burial
rituals on one's corpse.

The Yoruba's belief in life after death is also depicted in :

Níjọ tá baa sùn láipàhàdà

Tọmọ wa sún mọ kòtò, tó sẹkọ lù wá.

The day we are laid down dead

And our children move to our grave and
throw èkó (solid pap) on us in
the grave.

When a Yorùbá man or woman dies a 'good' death all burial rites are performed for the dead. One of such rites is burying food items with the dead. This, according to Yorùbá belief, is what the dead would be feeding on on his or her journey to the 'new world.'

Another Yorùbá culture associated with burial ceremonies is the elaborate party for the dead. When the poet says,

Tómọ ní sukún owó nítorí wa.

And our children are crying on how to get
money for our burial.

he is referring to the dilemma in which the children of the deceased find themselves on how and where to get money for the expected ceremonial party for their dead parent. The poet is silent on the desirability of the custom lavishing money on parties for the deceased. But he acknowledges the fact that it is a Yorùbá custom. So, the children of the deceased weep not only because their father is dead but more importantly because of the financial burden ahead of them.

All the philosophical expressions that run through the poem take their root from the Yorùbá culture. Their use keeps the poem alive and makes them realistic.

Fálétí writes most of his poems from personal experience. He stayed long on the farm and in rural areas around Òyó and Ìbàdàn from where he imbibed the Yorùbá culture exhibited in the text under consideration.

Ọlábímtán, like other poets that we have examined, has some poems on philosophical issues. Most of the

issues discussed by Ọlábímtán are on inanimate objects. For example, in his poem, 'Owó' (Money) he says :

Bọmọdẹ bá lówó lówó, a gbàgbé ọjọ orí
- - -

Bówó bágbà rẹ, a sọ ọ dọmọdẹ
- - -

Bówó bá bọmọdẹ rìn a dàgbà ọjẹ
- - -

Owó tí nsàbúrò dọgá ègbón
- - -

Owó, gbòngbò èşẹ.

(Ọlábímtán 1969:30).

When a child is rich, he would overlook age
- - -

If a man is in money, he becomes rejuvenated
- - -

If a young person finds himself in money
he becomes an elder
- - -

Money that makes a junior lord over his brother
- - -

Money, the root of evil.

This poem gives us an insight into the Yorùbá world-view. By and large, all these attributes of money are not complimentary since they do not conform with the normal life procedure. A critical analysis will

reveal this uncomplimentary nature of these attributes. For instance, money should not necessarily make one an adult. Adulthood is a function of age. It is equally unthinkable for a young person to turn round and assume the position of leadership over the elders. It is against Yorùbá societal norms. But becoming an 'adult' is to be imbued with the respect and regard usually accorded an adult. This is also as true as the above as a wretched elder who speaks in the society is like a mere barking dog and whose opinion is not received with honour, regard and respect. So, both are a true philosophy and true to life.

Any of the attributes of money as contained in the poem, is a sin since it is a negation of Yorùbá norms. The whole poem is a reflection of Yorùbá society, where, because of money, age is no longer respected.

Our discussion on the metaphysical and philosophical issues reveals that this theme runs through our entire study period, 1949 - 1989. It shows the importance the Yorùbá society attaches to it. Yorùbá philosophy is the ware-house of their wisdom as it guides their actions and thought. It remains constant and it will, perhaps, continue to engage the attention of Yorùbá future poets.

CHAPTER SIX

CONCLUSION

6.1 Summary

This study has attempted a critical study of the Yorùbá written poetry from 1949 to 1989. In this work, we have studied four decades of Yorùbá written poetry. Apart from the work of Olábímtán (1974), such an elaborate study of Yorùbá written poetry has not been available.

In this work, we have adopted sociology of literature. Our theory has given us the opportunity of looking at the various aspects of Yorùbá written poetry, that is, the poet, the poetry and the society.

This study covers the various stages of Yorùbá political history : from the colonial era, through the immediate post-independence period to the military era. It allows us to see the indepth thinking of the Yorùbá people. It becomes clear that Yorùbá poets do not just write to reflect, they oppose, they reject and they support the changing economic, social and political situation of their society.

There is now a difference in their thinking and in their approach to issues. We notice a sense of autonomy and courage after independence. Most of the

Yorùbá early poets were teachers. These include Atiládé, Ṣówùnmí and Ọdúnjọ that wrote between 1949 and 1960. The emergence of those poets that commercialize their art and which we called 'commercial poets' in this work such as Ọládàpọ and Adepoju, add more colour to the development of Yorùbá written poetry as shown in our analysis. So also is the writings of the intellectuals, that is, 'academic poets' such as Babalọlá, Ọlábímtán, Fálétí and Ìṣọlá that change the attitude of the poets. The Yorùbá poets become more confident and have the moral courage to challenge even the military. They realise the value of their weapon (poetry) and they use it to write freely on politics, culture and nature. Younger poets are now springing up, among whom is Awé. Women are not left out. An example is Adebisi Thompson who is one of the contributors to Àkójopọ Ewi Àbáláyé àti Ewi Àpilèko (1988) edited by Ọlábímtán. We could see the feminist tendency in their approach and language to show that Yorùbá poetry is growing steadily.

The development of Yorùbá written poetry stage to stage ^{media} and age to age is vivid in the influence of the electronic/ on the Yorùbá poets. This gives birth to the phenomenon

of poetry on discs and radio poetry. The work also brings into focus the growth of intellectualism and militarism in the political and social sphere of the Yorùbá society. The respect for the academics by the military is evident in the increasing number of academics in government, particularly the military government.

Yorùbá poetry is a source of information about the society. It is a strong weapon to oppose the government and express the mind of the people. We are able to see how the poets use language to achieve almost everything. Their simplicity of expression enables them to reach a large audience. From our observation, poetry is linked with the school syllabus in the forties and fifties. The main function of poetry then was purely didacticism. Its intention was to teach morals in schools. This is no longer so as poetry is no more restricted to schools. Poetry is now used to attack, to oppose and to criticise the evils of the society; to reflect on nature.

Karin Barber (1979) applies the sociology of literature for the analysis of oríkì in Òkukù, a Yorùbá town. Ògúnṣínà (1987) also shows how the theory of sociology of literature could yield a fuller and richer understanding of the novelist, his art and his society.

Our own application of the theory of sociology of literature has taken the study of Yorùbá written poetry to a limelight. We have shown in our analysis the need for proper scrutiny of the life of the poet whose life is part of the life of the society that produces him to be able to grasp the poet's message. Our work validates the fact that no literature can transcend its society.

6.2 Neglected Areas

The military have ruled Nigeria for the better part of the country's thirty-nine years of independence which is part of our study period. There have been serious allegations of corruption against the various military governments in Nigeria. The poets, who are supposed to be the watch-dog for the society have failed to use their literary weapon to call the military government to order. The reason for this failure is clear. As pointed out earlier, there have been more years of military administration in Nigeria than civilian and again, the rulers are not Yorùbá, hence the fear of arrest and punishment. Olanrewaju Adepọju, one of the poets under study, dares the military and pays dearly for it. According to him, he was interrogated several times by government agencies

and many of his albums and cassettes were either seized or destroyed by the law enforcement officers. As for Ọlábímtán, one of our poets hides under the canopy of figurative use of language. He is very subtle in his writings.

Apart from the corrupt military governments, the frequent wanton destruction of lives and properties by the soldiers living in and outside the barracks whenever they feel like exhibiting their might is something that should attract the attention of the poets. These recruits are always swollen-headed because the military is in power and so take laws into their hands. They have always been a nuisance to the public. For example, there have been instances where soldiers deliberately beat up commercial drivers in Lagos simply because they refuse to give them free ride. It is a phenomenon of the military era. Such incident could be effectively satirized by the poets to show the public's indignation of their (soldiers) act.

There are also some ills of the society that have defied any solution which the poets could also address. These include, child theft, armed robbery, hired assassin, examination malpractice, drug peddling and drug abuse

and the newly-arrived cult activities in Nigeria institutions.

6.3 Suggestions

Idòwú (1978) worked on Yorùbá poetry on discs and since then, there have been a lot more of Yorùbá poetry on discs. Audio and video recordings of poetry have also added to the abundant available discs poetry. Apart from all these, the video recordings of poetry on the June 12 episode¹ deserves a distinct study from the point of sociological perspective.

The influence of poetry and poets in the society needs further investigations and the results of such a venture will be very illuminating. The use of our theory, Sociology of literature has given us a good understanding of the relationship between literature and society. We have also shown the dependence of the poet, his art and the society on one another in our analysis which hitherto had been neglected by past works on poetry. Other researchers can experiment with semiotics. All these will enrich our knowledge and expand our understanding of the poet and the society.

¹ The Federal Military Government of Babangida annuled the Nigeria Presidential elections of June 12, 1993. This has generated a lot of argument that still ranges on.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Abimbola, Wáńdé (1968) Ìjìnlẹ̀ Ohùn Ènu Ifá, Apá Kííńí
Glasgow; Collins Sons and Co. Ltd.
- _____ (1976), Ifá, An Exposition of Ifá Literary Corpus, Ìbàdàn: Oxford University Press.
- _____ (1972), Sixteen Great Poems of Ifá
UNESCO.
- Abraham, R.C. (1976), Dictionary of Modern Yorùbá,
London: Hodder and Stoughton.
- Achike, O. (1978), Groundwork of Military Law and Military Rule in Nigeria, Enugu: Fourth Dimension Publishers.
- Adékanyè, J. Bayo (1993), Military Occupation and Social Stratification, Inaugural Lecture, Ibadan: University of Ìbàdàn, Vantage Publishers (Int.) Ltd.
- Adélékè, D.A. (1995), "Audience Reception of Yorùbá Films: Ìbàdàn as a Case Study", Ph.D. Thesis, Dept of Linguistics and African Languages, University of Ibadan, Ibadan.
- Adémóyèga, A. (1981), Why We Struck: The Story of the First Nigerian Coup, Ibadan: Evans Brothers (Nig. Publishers) Ltd.

- Adépojú, O. (1972), *Ìrónú Akéwí*, Ìbàdàn: Onibon-òjé Press, (Nig.) Ltd.
- Ajàó, D. (1936), Òrò Iyùn Lí Èdè Odùduà, Apá Èkííńí Mimeography.
- _____ (1940), Òrò Iyùn Lí Èdè Odùduà, Apá Kejí Mimeograph.
- Akínjógbín, A. (ed.) (1969), Ewí Ìwòyí, Glasgow: Collins Sons and Co. Ltd.
- Akínyemí, A. (1986), Déńrelé Àdèètímíkàn Qbasá (1927-1945) Akéwí Aláròjínlè, Ilé-Ifè: M.A. Thesis, Qbafèmi Awólówò University.
- _____ (1991), "Ìlò Oríkí Láwùjọ Ìlú Qyọ", Ph.D. Thesis, Ilé-Ifè: Qbafèmi Awólówò University.
- Akpan, N.V. (1972), The Struggle For Secession, 1960-1970, New York: Frank Cass and Co. Ltd.
- Àlàbá, I.O. (1985), "A Socio-Stylistic Analysis of Orin Agbè: A Multi Modal Genre of Yorùbá Oral Poetry", Ph.D. Thesis, Dept of African Languages and Literatures, University of Lagos.

- Ale, E.O. (1989), "Ifá Dídá Ní Ìlú Ilorin", M.A. Thesis, Dept of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages, University of Ilorin.
- Allen, R.E. (1966), Greek Philosophy: Thales to Aristotle, (ed.); London: Collier Macmillan Publishers.
- Àmòó, A. (1983), Àròfò Òkú Pípè, Ìbàdàn: Longman Nigeria Ltd.
- Amuta, C. (1986), Towards a Sociology of African Literature, Oguta: Zim Pan African Publishers.
- Arẹmu, F.B. (1988), "The Content and Form of Ọlabimtan's Àádọta Àròfò and Ewí Oríṣiríṣi", M.A. Thesis Dept of African Languages and Literatures, University of Lagos.
- Atẹrẹ and Ọlágbẹmí (1997), Introduction to Basic Sociology, Ìbàdàn: Enmí Press.
- Atiládé, E.A. (1950), Àkókà Yorùbá, Apá Kẹrin, Lagos: New Nigeria Press.
- _____ (1952) Àkókà Yorùbá, Apá Karun, Lagos: New Nigeria Press.
- _____ (1961), Àkókà Yorùbá, Apá Kẹfà, Lagos: New Nigeria Press.

- Awẹ, Bọlanle (1979), "Yorùbá Women in History" in Gangan, a Magazine of Oyo State of Nigeria, Ibadan: Issue No.8, October, 1979, pp 12-16.
- Awẹ, Débò (1989), Ewí Àmóríyá, Iléshà: Jọla Publishing Co. Ltd.
- Awólàlú, J.O. (1979), Yorùbá Beliefs and Sacrificial Rites, Burnt Mill: Longman House.
- Awólówò, O. (1981), Awo On the Nigerian Civil War, Ikeja: John West Publications Ltd.
- Awóníyí, T.A. (1975), "Ọmọlúàbí: The Fundamental Basis of Yorùbá Traditional Education" in Yorùbá Oral Tradition, Abimbọla (ed.), Ilé-Ifẹ: Department of African Languages and Literatures, University of Ibadan.
- _____ (1978), Yorùbá Language in Education, Ibadan: Oxford University Press.
- Awóyẹlé, O. (1987), Akéwí Ló Nitàn, Apá Kínní, Ibadan: Oníbọ̀nòjé.
- Àyándélé, E.A. (1966), The Missionary Impact on Modern Nigeria, 1842-1914, London: Longman Group Ltd.
- Babalọlá, A. (1956), 'Abúrò Mí Gbinní-sin' in ODU, Ibadan: Journal of Yorùbá, No. 2, pp 32-38.

Babalọlá, A. (1966), *The Content and Form of Yorùbá Ìjálá, Ìbàdàn*: Oxford University Press.

(1973a), "Afọlábí Johnson (1900-1943): Akéwí Akòwé L'Eko Àketè", in YORÙBÁ, A Journal of the Yorùbá Studies Association of Nigeria, Vol. 1, No. 1 pp 62-74.

(1973b), 'Yorùbá Poetic Language: Transition from Oral To Written Forms', in SPECTRUM, Vol. 3, U.S.A.: Georgia State University, pp 37-54.

Babalọlá, A. and Gerard, A. (1971) "A brief survey of Creative Writing in Yorùbá", in Review of National Literatures, Vol. II, No. 2.

Babalọlá, A. (1989), Ewé Ọmísínmísín, Ìkẹjà, Lagos: Longman Nigeria Ltd.

Barber, K. (1979), "Gríkí in Ọkukù Town: Relations between verbal and Social Structures", Doctoral Thesis, Ilé-Ifẹ̀: University of Ifẹ̀.

(1991), I could speak Until Tomorrow: Oríkí, Women and the Past in a Yorùbá Town. London: Edinburgh University Press.

- Bauman, Z. (1978), Hermeneutics and Social Sciences, London: Hutchinson University Library.
- Collier, P. and Geyer-Ryan (eds.) (1990), Literary Theory Today, London: T.J. Press.
- Craig, W. J. (ed.), 'Sonnet XXVII' in Shakespeare: Complete Works, London: Oxford University Press, 1925, Reprinted, 1966, p. 1046.
- Crowder, M. (1962), The Story of Nigeria, London, Faber and Faber.
- Dáre, J.O. (1989), The Praetorian Trap: The Problems and Prospects of Military Disengagement, Inaugural Lecture, Ilé-Ifè.
- Dasyilva, A.O. (1995) "The Beauty of the Ugly: A Perspective on Albert Camus and the Absurd", in OBITUN: Journal of Humanities, Vol. 1, No.1 pp 81-90.
- Dike, K.O. (1956), Trade and Politics on the Niger Delta, London.
- Eagleton, T. (1990), The Ideology of the Aesthetic, Oxford: Basil Blackwell Ltd.

- Escarpit, R. (1971), Sociology of Literature, London: Frank Cass and Co. Ltd.
- Fádípè, N.A. (1970), The Sociology of the Yorùbá, Ìbàdàn: University Press.
- Fafunwa, A.B. (1967), New Perspectives in African Education, Lagos: Macmillan and Co. (Nig.) Ltd.
- Fálétí, A. (1967), "Yorùbá Poets, Past and Present: the Poem Recorders," in HORIZON, Ìbàdàn, Students Magazine, Dept of English, University of Ìbàdàn.
- Fálolá and Ihonvbere (1985), The Rise and Fall of Nigeria's Second Republic (1979-1984), London: Zed Books Ltd.
- Finnegan, Ruth (1970), Oral Literature in Africa, Nairobi: Oxford University Press.
- Forgacs, David (1982), 'Marxist Literary Theories', in A. Jefferson and D. Robey (eds.). Modern Literary Theory, London: Batsford, 2nd edn.
- Gbadamọṣi, M.A. (1992), "Ipa ti Ẹgbé Ijínlẹ Yorùbá Kó Nínú Idàgbàsókè Ẹkọ̀ Imọ̀ Yorùbá," B.A.

Long Essay, Dept of Linguistics and
Nigerian Languages, University of Ilorin.

Geoffrey, S. (1981), Structuralist or Criticism?
Cambridge: Cambridge University Press:

Graham, D. (1968), Introduction to Poetry, London:
Oxford University Press.

Ìdòwú, Bọlaji (1962), Olódumarè: God in Yorùbá Belief,
Ìkẹjà: Longman Nig. Ltd.

Ìdòwú, S.A. (1978), "Modern Poetry On Discs," B.A.
Long Essay, Dept of Linguistics and
Nigerian Languages, University of Ìbàdàn.

Isichei, E. (1983), A History of Nigeria; London: Lagos
New York, Longman.

Ìṣòlá, A. (1987a), "The Writer's Art In The Modern
Yorùbá Novel," Ph.D. Thesis, University
of Ìbàdàn, Ìbàdàn.

(1987b), Àfàimò àti Àwọn Àròfò Mííràn,
Ibadan: Ibadan University Press.

Jayéọlá, C.O. (1988), "Ìhà tí Adéoyè kọ sí Ìmò Ìjìnlẹ̀
Èrò Yorùbá Nínú Ẹ́dá Ọmọ Ọduá," M.A.
Thesis, Ilorin: University of Ilorin.

- Jefferson and Robey (eds.) (1982), Modern Literary Theory: A Comparative Introduction, London: B.T. Batsford Ltd.
- Johnson, S. (1921), The History of the Yorùbá, The Oxford Norfolk: Lowe and Brydore Printers Ltd.
- Laurenson, D. and Swingewood, A. (1977), The Sociology of Literature, London: WacGibbon and Kee Publishers.
- Lowenthal, L. (1957), Literature and Image of Man, Boston: Beacon Press.
- Mabogunṣe, A.L. (1962), Yorùbá Towns, Ìbàdàn University Press.
- Maina Sara (1982), The Five Majors - Why They Struck, Zaria: Hudahudo Publishing Company.
- Marlowe, C. (1972), The Passimate Shepherd to His Love in Gardner, H. (ed.) The New Oxford Book of English Verse 1250-1950, Oxford Clarendon Press.
- Miller and Currie (1970), The Language of Poetry, London Heinemann Educational Books.

Nduka, O. (1964), Western Education and the Nigerian Cultural Background, Ibadan: Oxford University Press.

Ọdúnjọ, J.F. (1949a), Aláwífíyẹ, Ìwé Kejí, Lagos: Longman.

_____ (1949b), Aláwífíyẹ, Ìwé Kẹta, Lagos: Longman.

_____ (1961), Àkójọpọ Ewí Aladùn, Lagos: Longman.

Ọgúndẹjí, P.A. (1988), "A Semantic Study of Dúró Ládíípọ's Mythico-Historical Plays," Ph.D. Thesis, Ìbàdàn: University of Ibadan.

Ọgúnpítàn, S.A. (1999), A Comprehensive Grammar of Literary Studies, Lagos: Arimus Int. pp. 28-29.

Ọgúnşínà, B. (1980), Ipa tí Àwọ̀n Iwéé Iròhìn Yorùbá Àtíjọ́ Kó Nínú Ìdàgbàsókè Lítírésọ́ Àpílẹ̀kọ́ Yorùbá" in YORÙBÁ GBÒDE, Ìbàdàn: Ìwé Àtígbàdégbà Tí Ègbé Akómọ̀lédè Yorùbá pp 37-53.

_____ (1987), "The Sociology of the Yorùbá Novel: A Study of Isaac Thomas, D.O. Fagunwa and Ọládẹ̀jọ́ Ọ̀kédíjí," Ph.D. Thesis, Ìbàdàn: University of Ibadan.

Ògúnṣínà, B. (1988), Ònkòwé Yorùbá àti Ìdàgbàsókè Orílẹ̀-Èdè Naijiria, in IFE, Annals of the Institute of Cultural Studies, Ilé-Ife: Ọbáfẹ́mi Awólọ́wọ́ University. pp 84-93.

_____ (1992), The Development of the Yorùbá Novel (1930-1975), Ilorin: Gospel Faith Mission Press.

_____ (1996), "Gender Ideology, Portrayal of Women in Yorùbá Ìjálá" in African Languages and Culture 9.1, pp 84-93.

Oguntuyi, A. (1979), History of Èkitì, Ìbàdàn: Bisi Books and Co. Ltd.

Òjó, G.I. (1952), Ọlọrun Èsan, Ìbàdàn: Ministry of Education (GPS).

Ọlabimtan, A. (1969), Àádọta Àròfọ, Ìbàdàn: Macmillan.

_____ (1974a), "A Critical Study of Yorùbá Written Poetry (1848-1948)", Ph.D. Thesis, Lagos: University of Lagos.

_____ (1974b), Èwí Oríṣiríṣi, Ìbàdàn: Longman.

_____ (1983), "The Theme of Love In The Poetry of Ọlátúbọ̀sún Ọládàpọ̀," 4th Annual Conference of the Linguistic Association of Nigeria, University of Ibadan.

- Ọlábímtán, A. (ed.) (1988), Àkójopò Ewi Àbáláyé Àti Ewi Àpilèko, Ìbàdàn : Paperback Publishers Ltd.
- Ọlábòdé, A. (1981), "The Semantic Basis of Metaphors And Related Tropes In Yorùbá," Ph.D. Thesis, Ìbàdàn : University of Ìbàdàn.
- Ọládàpò, O. (1973), Àròyé Akéwì, Apá Kínní, Ìbàdàn : Oníbonòje Press.
- _____ (1975), Àròyé Akéwì, Apá Kejí, Ìbàdàn : Oníbonòje Press.
- Ọlágbèmí, B. T. (1980), "The Disc Poetry of Ọlatunbosun Ọládàpò," M.A. Thesis, Ilé-Ifè : University of Ifè (Now Ọbáfémi Awólówò University).
- Ọlájubù, C. (1975), 'Iwì : Egúngún Chants - An Introduction in Lindfors, B.(ed.), Critical Perspectives on Nigerian Literatures, London : Heinemann. pp 3-25.
- Ọlátúnjí, O. (1981), Features of Yorùbá Oral Poetry, Ìbàdàn : Ìbàdàn University Press.
- _____ (1982a), Adébáyò Fálétí : A Study of His Poems, Ìbàdàn : Heinemann Educational Books Ltd.
- _____ (1982b), Ewi Adébáyò Fálétí, Ìwé Kínní, Ìbàdàn : Heinemann Educational Books Ltd.

- Ọlátúnjí, O. (1982c), Ewí Adébáyò Fálétí, Ìwé Kejì, Ìbàdàn: Heinemann Educational Books Ltd.
- Olúránkínṣẹ́, O. (1987), Ìjì Ayé, Ìbàdàn: Oníbòṅòjé Press.
- Ọpádòtun, Fúnjì (1976), Àròfò Ọpádòtun, Lagos: Longman.
- _____ (1981), Ewí Àsíkò, Ìbàdàn: Abiprint and Pak Ltd.
- _____ (1987), Àròfò Eléwí-Odò, Ìbàdàn: Oníbòṅòjé.
- Ọṣọ́, J.O. (1977), "Radio Poetry," B.A. Long Essay, Ìbàdàn: Dept of Linguistics and Nigerian Languages, University of Ìbàdàn.
- Oyerinde, O. (1981), Àròfò Akéwí Akòwé, Lagos: Thomas Nelson Ltd.
- Cyewesọ, Siyan (ed.) (1992), Perspectives on the Nigerian Civil War, Lagos: CAP Publications.
- Scholes, R. (1974), Structuralism In Literature, New Haven and London: Yale University Press.
- Scott, W. (1962), Five Approaches of Literary Criticism, London: Collier Macmillan Publishers.

- Selden, R. (1985), A Reader's Guide To Contemporary Literary Theory, Kentucky: The University of Kentucky.
- Ṣówùní, G.A. (1952), Ìwé Àròfò Tí Anóyínlóhùn-bí-Ọmọge-Ìmàrò (Monography).
- Stewart, E.W. (1981), Sociology: The Human Science, New York: McGraw-Hill Book Company.
- Thompson, D. (1978), The Use of Poetry, Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Welleck and Warren (1949), Theory of Literature, London: Penguin Books.

A P P E N D I X

THE POETS

A brief biography of some of our poets is given here to highlight relevant position of their lives that influence their literary works.

A. Emmanuel Adékúnlé Atiládé :

Atiládé was born at Aáwé in Òyó State of Nigeria. There is no record of his birth but he was about ten to twelve years old when he started his elementary school education in 1917. So, he might have been born in about 1905.

He spent his primary school days with two different missionaries. After reading up to Standard I at Òyó, he went to Abẹokuta with an American missionary, Mrs. Ukilts. He read Standard III at the Baptist Day School, Ìjàyè. He followed another Missionary Dr. & Mrs. C. N. Salleh to Ògbómòṣṣó in 1922 where he completed his primary education.

He attended the Baptist Teacher Training College, Ògbómòṣṣó from 1927. He started his teaching career at the Baptist Day School, Ògbómòṣṣó in 1928. He left to teach at the Baptist Girls' High School, Abẹòkúta in

1930.

Atiládé went for training as an evangelist at the Baptist Theological Seminary, Ògbómòṣṣó from 1932 to 1934. Thereafter, he worked as a teacher in various institutions between 1935 and 1948. He was ordained a clergyman, Reverend Pastor in 1938. He finally left teaching for full pastoral work in 1949.

He was made a Minister of the Union Baptist Church, Lagos in 1950. He founded his own branch of Baptist which he named Gospel Baptist Church. The Headquarters of the Church is now the Gospel Baptist Cathedral, Lagos. The Gospel Baptist Church became autonomous in 1974 and separated from the Nigerian Baptist Convention. He rose to the enviable position of Archbishop before he retired in 1970.

Atiládé started his literary career in 1931 while he was at the Baptist Girls' School, Abéòkúta. It was then he wrote a novel, Omodele Àbèké Ogun. This spurred him to start his then popular Àkókà Yorùbá Books I - VI. Àkókà Yorùbá series contain all aspects of Yorùbá studies - Grammar, Culture and Literature (Prose, Drama and Poetry).

It is pertinent to state here that it was the publication of the Àkòkà Yorùbá series that earned Atiládé a Commonwealth Scholarship in 1964 for a full-time course in Writing, Production and Distribution of textbooks at the Department of Education in Tropical Areas at the University of London.

We interviewed Atiládé on July 28, 1997 and he died on November 2, 1997 before our next appointment within him. May his soul rest in peace.

B. Albert Gbádébò Awé :

Awé was born in 1952 at Ileṣa in Òṣun State of Nigeria. Both his father and mother were Òṣómàáló traders before becoming farmers. Awé finished his primary education in 1963 and obtained the Modern School Certificate in 1967. He also attended the Methodist High School, Òwó from 1968 - 1975. He also holds a Teachers' Grade II Certificate from the Government Teachers' College, Ileṣa.

Awé taught briefly at the N.U.D. Primary School, Òbaàgùn, near Ikirun and at the Hope Grammar School, Iléṣà from where he gained admission to the University of Ifè, now Òbáfémí Awólówò University, Ilé-Ifè. He

graduated in 1983. He also obtained his Masters' Degree in Yorùbá Literature in 1986 from the University of Ìbàdàn.

Awé has written several Yorùbá books among which are Ewí Amóríyá (1987) and Pápá Njó (1990). They are both poetry books. The first one falls into our period of study.

C. Solomon Adébóyè Babalọlá :

Babalọlá was born on December 17, 1926 at Ìpetumodù, Òşun State of Nigeria. His father, Joseph Omówùmí Babalọlá was a carpenter and a farmer. More importantly, he was a devout and dedicated Christian. His mother, Owólabí Babalọlá was the first of his father's two wives.

Babalọlá attended Christ Church School, Ìpetumodù for his primary education between 1931 and 1937. He started his secondary education at Igbóbì College, Lagos in January 1938 and passed out in December 1943 with distinction in nine subjects! He was at the Achimota College, Ghana for his Intermediate Bachelor of Arts Degree between 1944 and 1946. Babalọlá returned to Igbóbì College as a teacher on August 8, 1946. He taught briefly before returning to the Queen's College,

Cambridge in 1949 for his full Degree Course in English.

He finally returned to Igbóbi College, Lagos on Tuesday, February 12, 1952 with the Degree of B.A. (Cantab.). He rose to the post of Principal in 1958 and served in this capacity till 1961 when he went to the University of London for his Ph.D. which he successfully completed in 1963. On his return to Nigeria in 1963, he joined the University of Ifè, now Obáfèmi Awólówò University before crossing to the University of Lagos, Akoka, Lagos from where he retired as a Professor Emeritus in 1989.

Babalolá began his literary career as a poet in the fifties when he wrote a poem, 'Àbúrò Mi Gbínńísín' (My Young Junior Brother) in ODÚ, Journal of Yorùbá and Related Studies No. 2, Edited by S. O. Bíòbákú, H. U. Beier and L. Levi, 1956. Babalolá wrote several poems in OLÓKUN between 1970 and 1975. He is also one of the contributors to the poems in Ewí Ìwòyí, edited by Akínjógbín, 1969. His main collections of poems came out in a book, Ewé Òmísínmísín in 1989. Babalolá has also written some other Yorùbá books besides poetry. He has written some Yorùbá Plays and Novels. His contribution to Yorùbá studies in his book, The Content and Form of Yorùbá Ìjálá (1974) is noteworthy.

D. Joseph Fọláhàn Ọdúnjọ :

Ọdúnjọ was born in 1904 at Ìbarà, Abẹ̀òkúta, Ọ̀gùn State of Nigeria. He had his elementary education at Abẹ̀òkúta and his Teacher Training at Ìbàdàn. By the time of his birth and the period of his elementary and teacher training education, polygamy was flourishing in Yorùbáland. Having grown into it, Ọdúnjọ is aware of the prestige attached to polygamy in the Yorùbá traditional society. The prevailing social condition during Ọdúnjọ's birth and early life, was to surface in his literary work.

Ọdúnjọ later acquired a Certificate in Education at the Institute of Education, London. He worked for twenty-seven years, that is from 1924 to 1957 as a teacher, a Headmaster and an Inspector of Education (Ọlátúnjí 1988:5). This explains his handling of the theme of education in his poetry. This long teaching service also equipped him for his work, because, according to him, he pleaded with the then Senior Education Officer of the then Colonial Administration in the West in 1943 for the need for suitable Yorùbá readers. He based his observation on two premises. One was that the existing Yorùbá readers were grossly inadequate in quality. Secondly, the second World War

(1939 - 1945) made it difficult to secure the Yorùbá readers which were being printed in England then. The restrictions created by the war made things difficult.¹

It was as a result of Ọdúnjọ's effort to find a solution to this problem that he came out with his book Ìwé Kínní ABD Alawiye in 1943. This was how the new popular Alawiye series came into being. Books two, three, four and five were published in 1949 while Book Six came out in 1961. When asked by the Happy Home Magazine Correspondent the effect Ọdúnjọ's experience as a teacher has got on his writings, Ọdúnjọ said,

It was my experience as a teacher that I felt back on in choosing the category of people I was writing for. It was through this experience that I was able to know which words or sentences were appropriate in writing for the audience I had chosen, and my experience as a teacher had tremendous effect on my writings.²

This revelation is evident in his poems published in the Alawiye series. The school children were his main

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1. From an interview Ọdúnjọ granted the Happy Home Magazine, October, 1976, p. 36.
 2. Ibid., p. 37.

audience. He brought out his keen interest in infant work in his poems. As a teacher, he understood the appropriate language of the school children. Hence, his use of simple sentences to convey his message. The thematic simplicity and revealing topics of each poem is employed by the poet to make his points apparent to his school audience.

Religion also has a significant impact on Ọdúnjọ's works. He was a Choirmaster for many years and a church leader. He was made Knight of St. Gregory the Great in 1966 and Knight of Nullioma later. All these sterling qualities are a testimony to his religious steadfastness. The pedagogical and didactic nature of most of his poems is traceable to his religious and professional background.

Directly or indirectly, Ọdúnjọ was one of the nationalists that fought for Nigeria Independence. One is not surprised therefore that he was a Minister in the Old Western Region Government of Nigeria from 1952 to 1956.

Apart from the poems in the Alawiye series, most of the poems were published in a poetry book, Àkójọpò Ewì Aládùn in 1961. Ọdúnjọ also ^{had} some Yorùbá Novels and

Plays to his credit. He died at the age of Seventy-Six on 19th April, 1980.

E. Emmanuel Atanda Afolábí Olábímtán :

Olábímtán was born about 1932 at Ilaro in Ogun State of Nigeria. He hails from a family that was devoted to the Egúngún cult. His father was Òjèlabí Àdió Olábímtán and his mother was Oyíndàolá Olábímtán. After his primary education at Ilaro, he attended Methodist Boys High School^{Lagos} from 1947 - 1953. He worked as a clerk in the Federal Ministry of Health from 1954 to 1958.

Olábímtán attended the University of Ìbàdàn from 1958 - 1961 where he obtained the B.A. Degree in English. He proceeded to the Trinity College, Dublin for the Higher Diploma in Education. He joined the staff of the Methodist Boys' High School, Lagos, his Alma Mater where he was until 1969, when he joined the University of Lagos as a lecturer. He finished his Masters' Degree in Yorùbá at the University of Lagos in 1971 and his Ph.D. Degree at the same University in 1974. Olábímtán rose to the post of Professor before retiring from service in 1988.

Ọlábímtán is also a politician. He did not declare for any Political Party initially but he does not hide his sympathy for the former Action Group Party (AG) as evident in many of his poems in Àádóta Àròfò. He served as a Commissioner for Local Government and Information under the Military Administration in Ògùn State of Nigeria between 1976 and 1978. He was a Unity Party of Nigeria (UPN) gubernatorial contestant in the 1989 Nigeria election.

Ọlábímtán started his literary career in 1957 when he served as the Editor of Ìròyin Ìmólè, a weekly newspaper. He had a column in the Newspaper, 'Yẹyẹnátù Oníyẹyẹ Èkó.' He published some of his early poems in this Newspaper. For instance, some of these poems were, 'Báyé Bá Já,' 'Jesu Jínde,' 'Tó Ọmọ rẹ' and 'Ìyàwò' in 1962; and 'Ìgbẹyìn Ló Jù' in 1963. He wrote these poems under his pen-name, Afọlábí Ọjẹlábí. In 1969, six of his poems, 'Èkó,' 'Ọbalólo,' 'Èjidé,' 'Afòtẹjoyè,' 'Ebi,' and 'Ọwọ' appeared in Ewí Ìwòyí, edited by Adéagbo Akínjógbin. His own first poetry book, Àádóta Àròfò was published in 1969 while the second, Ewí Órísírísí was published in 1974. He edited another poetry book, Àkójopò Ewí Àbáláyé.

Àti Àpilèko in 1988 in which he has some poems too.

Ọlábímtán was born into a family of poets. His grand-father was a traditional Yorùbá poet, so also was his father, Ọjẹlabi Ọlabimtan. He also has access to the family traditional songs heritage like Gẹlẹdẹ, Èfẹ and Àgàṣá. All this has a tremendous impact on his literary career as a poet.

Ọlábímtán has also written several Yorùbá Novels and plays.

F. Olatubosun Ọládàpò :

Ọládàpò was born in September, 1943 to Pa Daniel Àkànjí Ọládàpò and Madam Maria Şegilọla Ọládàpò. It is customary for every Ìbàdàn indigene to be identified with one village from where one takes his root. Pa Daniel Àkànjí hails from Ládunní Village which is about thirty-eight kilometre from Ìbàdàn. Papa was the head of this village during his life time. He was also a devout Christian.

The main occupation then was farming. Ọlatubosun's father was also a farmer and he used to follow his father to the farm. His father could read and write and this was very advantageous to Ọládàpò because his father taught him how to read and write ever before he

started schooling. He was able to read the alphabets, ABD fluently. Furthermore, his father used to read Ajisafe's Ayé Àkamarà and the poems of Şóbò Aróbíodu to his hearing. This was to be an inspiration for Ọládàpò as a poet in his later years.

After his primary and modern school education, he obtained the Grade III Teachers' Certificate in 1967. As a trained teacher, Ọládàpò worked at St. David's Primary School, Kúdetí, Ìbàdàn from 1968 - 1970.

Ọládàpò started his work as a journalist with the Sketch Publishing Company as the Editor of one of its weekly newspapers, GBOHÙNGBOHÙN. He later joined the former Western Nigeria Broadcasting Corporation (WNTV-WNBS), Ìbàdàn. From there, he went for a Diploma in Yorùbá Studies at the University of Lagos, 1974 - 1975. He returned to the WNTV-WNBS as the Editor of Yorùbá Programmes; such as 'Agbòràndùn,' 'Tiwa-ñ-tiwa' and 'Èdà Sòrò Yíí'.

Ọládàpò retired from the Broadcasting Corporation of Ọyọ State (Radio O-Y-O) in 1977 to set up his own recording company. He waxes his own poems as well as those of others.

He has published many works, out of which are his poetry works in two volumes, Àròyé Akéwí, Apá Kínní,

1973 and Àròyé Akéwì, Apá Kejí, 1975. Ọlátúnjí (1982a) describes Ọládàpò as a "famous contemporary Yorùbá poet, the most prolific in print and on disc."

G. Oyedemi Oyerinde :

Oyerinde was born on October 7, 1925 at Igbóọrà in Ọyó State of Nigeria. He was well over fifteen years old before he started his primary school education. After his primary education, he worked as a teacher for five years at Igbóọrà. He later went for his Grade III Teachers' Certificate in 1954 and also his Grade II Teachers' Certificate in 1958. After his course, he taught in a modern school in Abẹ̀òkúta and later at the Nawairudeen Grammar School, Abẹ̀òkúta.

Oyerinde came back to Lagos in 1967 and returned to the Primary School to teach. Between 1959 and 1960, he passed some papers in the GCE O/L and A/L. He was later admitted to the University of Lagos for a one-year full-time Diploma Course in Yorùbá Studies. He went back into teaching at the Jubril Martins Memorial Grammar School, Iponri where he retired.

Oyerinde went back to his home town, Igbóọrà where he began to practise full scale farming.

He is a co-author of the Èkó Èdè Yorùbá Titun for JSS I - III and SSS I - III. His own contribution is the culture section. Oyerinde is more known with his poetry book, Àròfò Akéwí Akòwé, which was published in 1981.

H. George Sówùmí :

George Adédayò Sówùmí, alias Anóyínlóhùn-bí-Ọmọge-Ìmàrò was born in 1914 in Sówùmí village, very near Abẹ̀òkúta. He attended different primary schools but the major one is CMS Central School, Ìpóró Aké.

Very little is known about his early life but Sówùmí lay his hands on different jobs to earn his living. First, he was a trader and later, he became a photographer. He was at one time a wood-carver and also a goldsmith. He was a teacher from 1933 - 1960, first at Bólá Memorial School, Onígbòngbò, Lagos and at St. Judes School, Èbúté-Méta, Lagos.

His published poetry books include,

1. Ìwé Àròfò (Apá Kínní) 1946
2. Ìwé Àròfò (Apá Keji) 1950
3. Ìwé Àròfò (Apá Kẹta) 1952.

He died on 14th April, 1980.

I. Adébísí Thompson :

Thompson was born on 23rd December, 1932 in Iléṣà. She started her primary education at the Methodist Primary School, Ọtapètẹ, Iléṣà and finished at the Princess School, Lagos in 1948. She was admitted to the Queen's College, Lagos in 1946 and finished in 1950. She did her Grade II Teachers' Course at the United Missionary College (UMC), Ìbàdàn from 1951 - 1952.

After working for a while, Mrs. Thompson left Nigeria for the Southlands College, Winbleam, London where she studied from 1955 to 1957. When she got back to Nigeria, she worked as a teacher at the Queen's School, Èḍẹ from 1958 to 1968. She left for the University of Ìbàdàn in 1968 and graduated in 1971.

Her first literary work is her poems in Àkójọpọ Ewí Àbáláyé àti Ewí Àpilẹkọ, edited by Ọlábímtán in 1988. She wrote another book, Bòsún Omo Ọdòfin, a novel.

Mrs. Adébísí Thompson died in December, 1995.

J. Oyetunde Awoyele :

Awóyẹlẹ was born on the 18th of December, 1944 in Alasa Compound, Ìrẹmọ, Ilé-Ifẹ. His father was a

farmer and he used to follow him to the farm when he was young.

Awóyèlé had his primary school education at St. Peter's Anglican Primary School, Ìrẹ̀mọ̀, Ilé-Ifẹ̀ between 1951 and 1957. He attended the Seventh-Day Adventist Secondary Modern School, Ilé-Ifẹ̀ between 1958 and 1960 and also Adventist Grammar School, Èdẹ̀ from 1961 - 1965. He had his Nigeria Certificate in Education (NCE) in 1968.

He worked briefly at the African Church Grammar School, Iléșà from where he was admitted to the University of Ifẹ̀ in 1970. He graduated in 1973. After his National Youth Service at the Zaria Teachers' College, Zaria in 1974, he registered as a part-time post-graduate student in the Faculty of Education, Ahmadu Bello University, Zaria and obtained his Masters' Degree in Educational Administration in 1977.

After his Masters' Degree, he joined the University of Ilorin as an Assistant Lecturer. He later left for the Ogun State College of Education, Ìjẹ̀bú-Ode in 1979 where he is currently working. He had his Doctorate Degree in Educational Planning in 1988 from the University of Benin, Benin City.

Awóyèlé is a Novelist, a playwright and a Poet. He has written several literary texts among which are his two poetry books, Akéwì Ló Nitàn Book I (1987) and Akéwì Ló Nitàn, Book II (1987).

INTERVIEW WITH PEOPLE

The poets that I have chosen to publish my interview with me are representatives of all the poets I visited. I interviewed the poets, not on their poems per se, but on their life history to see the impact it has on their works. Also, some of the poets I used for this work are already dead, but I was able to collect their biographies from other sources. For example, I got that of Qdúnjọ from the J.F. Qdúnjọ Memorial Lectures Series edited by Qlatunji (1988 and 1996). Professor Adéboýè Babalọlá is very kind to give me that of Gabriel Şówùmf.

There are other persons I interviewed who are not poets but their interview has relevance with our work. For example, Pa Adégbóyèga Şóbándé who was once the editor of ÓLÓKÚN and Mr. Qládifọ Yémítàn who was also a member of the editorial board of OLÓKUN. I also include my visits to the media houses and publishing companies from where I collected some poems for our analysis.

INTERVIEW WITH PEOPLE

N A M E	AGE	VENUE OF INTERVIEW	DATE
1. Prof Adeboye Babalola A Poet and a critic.	71	His Residence at 43, Ahaji Tookan St., Alaka Estate Surulere, Lagos	1. May 27, 1997 2. June 5, 1977 3. July 10, 1997 4. August 17, 1997
2. Pa Adegboyega Sobande A retired school teacher, He was once the Editor of <u>OLÓKUN</u>	80	His Residence at 13, Coats Street, Ebute-Meta, Lagos	1. 30-04-96 2. 07-05-96 3. 10-05-96
3. Mr. Qladiipo Yémiftàn	60	His Residence at 27, Raufu Williams Creence, Surulere, Lagos	1. 06-05-96 2. 06-06-96
4. Arch Bishop Emmanuel Adekunle Atilade	97	His Residence at 6, Ashabi Street, Mushin, Lagos.	1. 28-07-97 (Died on Nov. 2, 1997 before my next visit to him)
5. Pa Oyedemi Cyerinde	68	At Oşogbo during the Egbé Akçmçlede Yorùba Conference	1. 18-08-97
6. Prof. Mkinwumi Işçle	65	At the University of Ibadan, in the Senior Staff Room.	1. 06-06-97
7. Evangelist Débç Awé	55	At Oşogbo during the Egbé Akçmçlede Yorùba Conference	1. 15-08-97